

**The impact of changing workplace conditions and employee engagement on
employee productivity in the context of Hero MotoCorp India**

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Declaration

This thesis is a result of my own research work and none of it has been submitted to any other institutions or universities of higher learning. The content of this thesis are not done in collaboration with anyone and the author is fully responsible for any errors produced.

Table of contents

Abstract	7
Chapter one: Introduction	8
1.1 Background of Study	8
1.2 Industry Background.....	9
1.3 Hero MotoCorp.....	10
1.4 Problem Statement	13
1.5 Rationale	14
1.6 Significance.....	14
1.7 Aim and objectives.	15
1.7.1 Aim	15
1.7.2 Objectives	15
1.8 Research Questions	15
1.8.1 Main Questions	15
1.8.2. Sub Questions	15
1.9 Research Methodology	16
1.10 Thesis Structure	16
1.11 Chapter Summary	17
Chapter two: Literature Review.....	18
2.1. Introduction.....	18
2.2. Change Management	18
2.3. Employee engagement.....	20
2.4. Employee Productivity.....	21
2.5. Changing Workplace Conditions.....	23
2.6. Factors of Employee Engagement	25
2.6.1. Vigour	26
2.6.2. Dedication	27
2.6.3. Absorption	28
2.7 Factors Associated with Working Conditions driving Employee Productivity.....	29
2.7.1 Working Hours	29

2.7.2 Workload	30
2.7.3 Technology and Facilities	31
2.8 Review of articles	32
2.9. The relationship between Employee Engagement and Employee Productivity	47
2.10. The relationship between Changing Workplace Conditions and Employee Productivity	51
2.11. Impact of Changing Workplace Conditions on Employee Productivity	55
2.12. Impact of Employee Engagement on Employee Productivity	57
2.13. Theoretical Framework	61
2.14.1 The Zinger Model of Engagement	61
1. Achieve Results	62
2. Maximise Performance	63
3. Path Progress.....	64
4. Building Relationships.....	66
5. Foster Recognition	69
6. Master Moments	71
7. Leverage Strengths.....	75
8. Make Meaning	78
9. Enhance Well-being.....	80
10. Enliven Energy.....	84
2.12.2 ADKAR model	86
2.14 Conceptual Framework.....	88
2.15. Conclusion	89
Chapter Three: Research Methodology	91
3.1 Chapter Introduction	91
3.2 Research onion.....	91
3.2 Research Philosophy (Interpretive Constructionism)	93
3.3 Research Methods (Qualitative research method)	94
3.4 Research Approach	96
3.5 Research Population.....	97
3.6 Sampling Techniques and Sample Size	97
3.7 Sample Size INTERVIEWS SURVEY	98

3.8 Methods of Data Collection	99
3.9 Data Analysis and Presentation	102
3.10 Ethical Considerations	103
3.11 Chapter Conclusion.....	104
CHAPTER FOUR: Analysis of Results	105
4.1: Introduction.....	105
4.1.1 List of interview questions	105
4.2: Interview and Responses	106
4.2.1 Effects of employee engagement in Hero Moto Corp India	106
4.2.2 Strategies used by Hero MotoCorp India for employee engagement including both positive and negative effects.	108
4.2.3 Effects of disengaged employees on their personal performance, organisational performance, and co-workers in Hero MotoCorp India.....	111
4.2.4 Roles of trust and leadership in employee engagement including behavioural and attitude changes.....	113
4.3 Thematic analysis.....	115
Conclusion	116
CHAPTER FIVE: Discussion and Interpretation of Findings.....	118
5.1 Introduction.....	118
5.2 Analysed data based on Objective 1	118
5.3 Analysed data based on Objective 2	119
5.4 Analysed data based on Objective 3	121
5.5 Analysed data based on Objective 4	125
5.6 Analysed data based on Objective 5	129
5.7 Analysed data based on Objective 6	134
5.7.1 Conclusion	134
5.7.2 Recommendation.....	137
5.7.3 Research Limitations	138
5.7.4 Future Research	139
References.....	140
Appendix 1: Consent Form.....	155

Appendix 2: Ethical Form.....	157
Appendix 3: Interview and Responses.....	159
Appendix 4: Respondent Profile.....	194

Table of figures

Figure 1 Hero MotoCorp Talent Management Framework.....	12
Figure 2 Schaufeli and Bakker (2010).....	26
Figure 3 Conceptual Framework	88
Figure 4 Research Onion Source: Thornhill, Saunders and Lewis (2009)	91
Figure 5 Practised engagement and changing workplace components in Hero MotoCorp.....	130
Figure 6 Improvised conceptual framework.	136

Abstract

The study analyses the impact of changing workplace conditions and employee engagement on employee productivity in the context of Hero MotoCorp India. Hero MotoCorp is the largest manufacturer of two-wheelers in the world and has six manufacturing facilities, capable of manufacturing 11.6 million units annually. In 1984, Hero MotoCorp decided to go down the route of a joint venture and entered into a contract with the Honda Motor Company of Japan and formed Hero Honda Motor Limited. The joint venture not only led to the creation of the world’s largest two-wheeler manufacturer but also was a most successful joint venture, between India's Hero Group and Japan’s Honda Motor Company. Finally, on December 16, 2010, the Hero Group and Honda Motor Co. decided to dissolve their partnership, bringing a close to one of the most successful joint ventures in the world in the automobile industry. Hero MotoCorp has entered new partnerships; for instance, on July 1, 2013, Hero MotoCorp, bought a 49.2% stake in Erik Buell Racing, an American motorcycle sport company for \$25 million. Hero MotoCorp is at the cusp of huge expansion, after coming out of the shackles of Honda Motors which deterred the expansion of Hero MotoCorp due to joint venture conditions. This has given a unique opportunity to analyse

the impact of changing workplace conditions and employee engagement on employee productivity. This scenario has never been explored before, in the case of an automobile company. To analyse the impact of changing workplace conditions and employee engagement on employee productivity in the case of Hero MotoCorp, this study utilised the Zinger Model on Employee Engagement and ADKAR model. These two models have never been utilised in tandem to analyse employee productivity and a change management proposition. The study has taken an interpretivist approach, which gave the opportunity to explore different facets of changing workplace conditions and employee engagement. The study took an inductive approach in conducting the research, that is a bottom-up approach, moving from the specific scenario of Hero MotorCorp to a general phenomenon of organisations. Twenty respondents were interviewed and were asked 14 open-ended questions; all the respondents were current employees of Hero MotoCorp, sharing their fresh perspective of the company. The data generated gave rise to ten different themes, in which productivity was the main theme, which is in line with Hero MotoCorp's vision. Data generated were analysed based on six different objectives listed at the start of the thesis, which gave rise to a set of conclusions and recommendations. One of the major recommendations is to enhance the well-being of employees by launching initiatives based on the authenticity of relationship, the safety of the financial component, the energy of our physical health, and the pleasure taken in contributing towards society.

Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Background of Study

Doppelt (2017) shared that in the beginning of the 1990s, the global competition was increasing at an exponential rate due to the development of new markets, expansion of business globally, availability of e-commerce and development of technology. As mentioned by Kondalkar (2013), today in a competitive environment, the global economy has created a significant impact on the business environment and ways through which organisations operate. The successful organisations are those organisations that are often implementing continuous change (Cameron and Green, 2015). Today about 80% of organisations have sought to transform their business and respond to change by restructuring their organisational strategies. Regardless of this benefit of change, it is

noted that when changes occur then it is associated with uncertainty, loss of status, unfamiliarity and control, and these concerns create a domino effect and result in employee resistance. According to Goetsch and Davis (2014), about 70% of change initiatives taken by companies fail due to negative employee attitude and unproductive behaviour of management. Simoes and Esposito (2014) shared that in the context of organisational change, employee resistance is the most common issue which decreases the effectiveness of change. This resistance can be due to the collective culture which creates barriers during change implementation. In this way, the application of employee engagement programmes ensures the involvement of employees so that strategic change initiatives can be implemented (Ashkenas, 2013). Organisational change plays a significant role in enhancing employee productivity, involvement, and firm performance. This study is entitled as analysing the role of employee engagement in initiating organisational change and its impact on firm performance in the Hero Moto Corporation India (Kash, Spaulding, Johnson and Gamm, 2014). In human resource management, change is determined as the strategy which helps organisations to focus on innovation and growth (Hechanova and Cementina-Olpoc, 2013). The innovation and growth within the firm can be due to several expansion strategies adopted by the company, which leads towards profitability and increased return on investment (ROI). Especially, in the automobile sector, change refers to the organisational development which can be in the business structure, processes, strategies, employees or throughout value stream (Vora, 2013).

1.2 Industry Background

As per Statista (2020), the population of India is 1.38 billion and, over the past 5 years, the Indian economy has grown at an average rate of 9% and it is expected that this growth will be doubled in coming years (World Bank, 2020). This shows the increase in population and growth in GDP (Gross Domestic Product) are the key drivers in driving sales in the automobile industry. According to a report of IBEF global, the automobile sector of India is the largest sector in the world with annual production of more than 23.96 million vehicles (Karunakar, 2017). From 2015 to 2016, about 2.57% growth was noted and the industry accounts for more than 7.6 % of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (*Economic Times*, 2016). In the automobile sector, the two-wheeler sector accounts for 81% of the market share in the overall automobile sector (Miglani, 2019). The majority of two wheelers are owned by a young population and middle-class people in India. Due

to the industrial competitiveness and constant growth, companies such as Ford, Autoliv Inc, General Motors, Mercedes, Mahindra and BMW are continuously involved in investing in establishing new plants which increase the effectiveness of the Indian automobile sector. Besides this, the government also encourages FDI and announced various plans to make the automobile available to every person living in India. Hence, India has become the centre of all leading brands of the automobile and according to statistics shared by SIAM, it is noted that the sales of passenger vehicle grew by 9.23%; meanwhile, two-wheeler sales grew by 6.89% which includes motorcycles, scooters, and mopeds (SESEI, 2020). Besides this, the two wheelers and three wheelers declined by (-) 32.77% and (-) 5.78% respectively during March 2016 till March 2017 (Miglani, 2019). Given a sudden decline in the two-wheeler market in India, it is necessary for an Indian two-wheeler company like Hero MotoCorp to explore new markets to hedge its risks. The global two-wheeler segment is expected to grow to 62.6 million by 2025, though this growth is facing severe constraints due to the Covid-19 pandemic, but the situation is expected to improve sharply, post pandemic and the demand may exceed expectations. Findings published by MotorCyclesData (2020) suggest that the global motorcycle industry may have lost around 7 million in sales in 2020 due to the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. However, the same study by MotorCyclesData (2020) also confirms a strong emergence of two-wheeler demand globally due to increasing need for individual mobility.

1.3 Hero MotoCorp

Hero MotoCorp is ranked as the single largest manufacturer of two-wheeler motorcycles in the world. The journey of Hero MotoCorp started as Hero cycles in 1956 and by 1975 it became largest manufacturer of bicycles in India (NDTV, 2021). In 1984, it decided to go down the route of a joint venture and entered into a contract with the Honda Motor Company of Japan and formed Hero Honda Motor Limited. The joint venture not only led to the creation of the world's largest two-wheeler manufacturer but was also a most successful joint venture, between India's Hero Group and Japan's Honda Motor Company. Over a period of years, Hero Honda Motor Limited kept on launching different two-wheeler variants. Some of its most popular variants were "Splendor", launched in 1994 and "CBZ" launched in 1999 (Nandi, 1994).

Finally, on December 16, 2010, the Hero Group and Honda Motor Co. decided to dissolve their partnership, bringing a close to one of the most successful joint ventures in the world in the automobile industry (DNA, 2010). Hero Group's strategy can be fathom from Ansoff Matrix, (2015), where the single largest manufacturer of two-wheeler motorcycles in the world was not able to export its products to international markets, which was of one of the contentious issues, leading to the end of the relationship with Honda Motors because as per the terms of the joint venture, the Hero Group could only sell its two-wheelers to Sri Lanka and Nepal. It can be implicated that the Hero Group had reached a peak in the Indian market where further market penetration was becoming cumbersome, hence the Hero Group wanted to go for market development but the agreement with Honda Motors was acting as a major obstacle. Moreover, there was excessive reliance on Honda Motors for technology and Hero MotoCorp wanted to move away from this dependence. There were a number of aberrations that started emerging in the joint venture; for instance, Honda's reluctance to freely share technology and the high royalties charged by Honda Motors was hurting the Hero Group's vision.

With closure of the contract, Hero MotoCorp was free to export its products to any international market. The brand-new logo for Hero MotoCorp was designed by the British firm Wolf Ollins and was revealed on August 9, 2011 (Hindu, 2011). After dissolving of the contract with Honda Motors, the Hero Group launched a number of variants under the brand name, "Hero MotoCorp", for instance Glamour and Karizma were launched in 2011 (*Economic Times*, 2013). Hero MotoCorp also launched Impulse in 2011, an off-road variant, to explore the dirt bike segment. On July 1, 2013, Hero MotoCorp, bought a 49.2% stake in Erik Buell Racing, an American motorcycle sport company for \$25 million (LiveMint, 2013).

Leadership motivates the employees to an enhanced level of output through their powerful relationship building. It is a crucial activity of management which helps to increase efficiency and to achieve a company's goal. The top tier of Hero MotoCorp's leadership can be seen in Figure 3 that is propelling the company to greater heights. It is only because of this leadership that Hero MotoCorp is able to maintain its position as the largest manufacturer of two-wheelers in the world. Hero MotoCorp has five manufacturing units based at Dharuhera, Gurugram, Neemrana, Haridwar, and Halol. These manufacturing facilities together have a rolling-out capacity of over 90 lakh (9 million) two-wheelers per year (Hero MotoCorp, 2020). During FY 2019-20, Hero

MotoCorp touched sales of 63.98 lakh units (Business Standard, 2020). Hero MotoCorp, which is the second largest manufacture of two-wheelers in the world has a market cap of 46% in the two-wheeler category and clocked a sale of US\$9.6 billion as of December 31, 2020 (Business Today, 2021). Hero MotoCorp had an employee strength of 8,599 on the roll and 21,091 off the roll as of October 2020 (Hero MotoCorp, 2020).

Figure 1 Hero MotoCorp Talent Management Framework

Source: (Hero MotoCorp, 2020)

Figure 4 shows the use of talent management and development as a strategic tool employed by Hero MotoCorp to accomplish its long-term goals (Hero MotoCorp, 2020). The framework consists of 12 components: 1) Goal setting, 2) Sales competency framework 3) Vendor identification and contracts 4) HR competency framework 5) Excellerator club 6) Talent review 7) Managerial capability building programmes 8) Job evaluation 9) Success factors and e-learning 10) Hero universe 11) System streamlining and digitalisation and 12) Individual development plan creation.

1.4 Problem Statement

This research will help other automobile companies in identifying the importance of employee engagement while initiating change or adopting market development strategy. Successful change is implemented when organisational employees are mutually involved at every level (Hayes, 2014). In previous years, Hero Honda Motors Ltd signed a joint venture agreement with Japan-Honda Motors Corporation, which resulted in change at the corporate, business, functional and individual levels. The change due to a joint venture agreement caused several difficulties and hinderances which resulted in negative ROI. However, slowly, and gradually Hero MotoCorp successfully managed the change through engaging employees by sharing values, making mutual decisions, adopting leadership practices, providing growth opportunities, and creating a positive work environment (Booth, 2015).

Hero MotoCorp intends to overhaul every department to meet its global ambitions. To achieve this, Hero MotoCorp has acquired a 49.2% stake in Erik Buell Racing, an American motorcycle sport company (LiveMint, 2013). Hero MotoCorp intends to form new international alliances to complement its global vision. Hero MotoCorp is also changing the landscape of the workplace by bringing in new standards to best suit the company and employees. As per the most recent annual report published by Hero MotoCorp, the company is spending enormous capital on learning and development and employee engagement. As per the annual report of 2019-2020, Hero MotoCorp spent around US\$ 2.6 million on learning and development for its employees and US\$ 13.7 million on employee engagement initiatives (Hero MotoCorp, 2020). Hence, this scenario offers an opportunity to analyse the impact of changing workplace conditions and employee engagement on employee productivity in the context of Hero MotoCorp. The findings from this study can then be extrapolated to understand the impact of changing workplace conditions and employee engagement on employee productivity in the case of the automobile industry and organisation. Therefore, the problem statement of this study explores the impact of changing workplace conditions and employee engagement strategy implemented by Hero MotoCorp while initiating change and creating partnership agreements with new firms and the impact on the firm performance.

1.5 Rationale

Today, Hero MotoCorp is at the cusp of huge expansion, after coming out of the shackles of Honda Motors which deterred the expansion of Hero MotoCorp due to joint venture conditions. This has given a unique opportunity to analyse the impact of changing workplace conditions and employee engagement on employee productivity. This scenario has never been explored before, in the case of an automobile company. Hero MotoCorp is the world's largest manufacturer of two-wheelers. Hero MotoCorp is entering into new partnership and each company has its unique way of functioning; for instance, Hero MotoCorp has entered into a partnership with an automobile company which will explicitly or implicitly influence the basic characteristics of Hero MotoCorp employees. Hence the study in hand gives a novel opportunity to explore these aspects that together contribute to employee productivity.

1.6 Significance

The study is significant because it analyses the impact of changing workplace conditions and employee engagement on employee productivity by utilising the Zinger Model on Employee Engagement and ADKAR model. These two models have never been utilised in tandem to analyse employee productivity and a change management proposition. The Zinger Model on Employee Engagement focuses on ten key areas: Achieving Results, Maximising Performance, Path Progress, Building Relationships, Fostering Recognition, Mastering Moments, Leveraging Strengths, Making Meaning, Enhancing Well-being, and Enlivening Energy. Analysing these ten factors on employee engagement in relation to Hero MotoCorp adds to the significance of the study. The ADKAR model, considers: Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability, and Reinforcement parameters that employees need to attain for lasting change. Analysing these five factors in terms of changing workplace conditions in relation to Hero MotoCorp further adds to the significance of the study. Interpretivism, often referred to as an interpretivist approach, involves researchers interpreting elements of the analysis, thereby bringing human interest into a study of interpretivism. The study has taken an interpretivist approach, which offers the opportunity to explore different facets of changing workplace conditions and employee engagement. The study under consideration has taken an inductive approach in conducting the research, that is a bottom-up approach, moving from the specific scenario of Hero Motor Corp to a general phenomenon of organisations.

1.7 Aim and Objectives

1.7.1 Aim

- ✚ The aim of this study is to analyse the impact of changing workplace conditions in the context of Hero MotoCorp India.
- ✚ A further aim is to evaluate employee engagement on employee productivity in the context of Hero MotoCorp India.

1.7.2 Objectives

The main objectives of the study are:

1. To critically evaluate the literature on organisational change and identify the role of employee engagement in initiating change.
2. To evaluate and identify the effects of employee engagement in Hero MotoCorp.
3. To identify the strategies used by Hero MotoCorp India for employee engagement.
4. To examine the effects of disengaged employees on their personal performance, organisational performance, and co-workers in Hero MotoCorp India.
5. To recommend solutions based on the findings for developing employee engagement programmes to enhance the process of organisational change.
6. To develop a conceptual framework for employee engagement, based on employee engagement elements practised at Hero MotoCorp.

1.8 Research Questions

1.8.1 Main Questions

What is the role played by employee engagement in initiating organisational change successfully and how does a strategic framework help in enhancing firm performance in Hero MotoCorp?

1.8.2. Sub Questions

The below are the research questions for the study:

1. What is organisational change and what is the role of employee engagement in initiating change?
2. What is the association among role of employee engagement, organisational change, and firm performance?
3. What is the impact of employees' engagement on organisational change and firm performance in Hero MotoCorp?
4. What is solution based on the findings for developing employee engagement programmes to enhance the process of organisational change?

1.9 Research Methodology

Taking an interpretivist position, the author selected the inductive approach to gain knowledge about changing workplace conditions and employee engagement on employee productivity in Hero MotoCorp India. This study has been designed along the lines of a qualitative investigation. The research strategy chosen is contextual in nature and the focus of the entire investigation is Hero MotoCorp India. The researcher conducted 20 in-depth interviews to analyse the research phenomena, change management, employee engagement and employee productivity within the specific context of Hero Moto. The researcher will be using thematic analysis and this study has analysed interview transcripts to extract answers for research questions.

1.10 Thesis Structure

The research study mainly consists of six chapters that support an illustration of the overall study. The chapters that are divided into the study are a common structure in several of the studies. The first chapter that had been currently followed is an introduction in which the chapter has highlighted the study's background, the research gaps and thesis structure. Moreover, the aims and objectives have also been designed to explain to the readers what the research aims to achieved.

The next chapter is focused on the literature review in which it is crucial that the study is compared and discussed through highlighting the previous study. Thus, the previous studies related to the following research are compared and critically analysed. The literature also supports the achievement of the first developed objective of the study.

The third chapter is the research methodology which is a critical part of the research as it seeks to determine and identify the methods implemented in the study to complete the overall research. Moreover, the methodology is given to provide guidance for completing the overall study.

Data analysis and discussions of the results are the fourth and fifth chapter of the study respectively in which the raw data are presented in the form of interpretation and these results are significantly analysed and interpreted while also comparing them with previous studies to reach an overall conclusion.

The last chapter comprises a conclusion to the study and an overall and main view of the study gained from the previous chapter is extracted in this chapter. Moreover, recommendations are also provided in the last chapter which is one of the research objectives.

1.11 Chapter Summary

On a concluding note, it can be said that the first chapter of the research study was based upon headings such as the background of the study, research gaps, research aims, research objectives, research questions, and the structure of this thesis. In the first chapter of the study, the importance of changing workplace conditions was highlighted because business dynamics have greatly changed over the last few years. In addition to this, it was also discussed in the first section of the study that the inability on the part of organisations to adapt to changes in the external environment ultimately lead to failure in operations as the needs and wants of customers and the business world are not met. In addition to this, the background of the study also indicated the fact that employee engagement and senior management level in organisations have an extensive role to play in managing employee productivity. The statement can further be concluded in the sense that the loyalty and satisfaction levels of employees are directly linked with efficient workplace conditions and effective employee engagement.

Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1. Introduction

The main purpose of this chapter is to demonstrate the theoretical underpinnings associated with the area of the study. For this purpose, the chapter has been divided into various sections and sub sections leading towards the theoretical and conceptual framework of the study. Considering the importance of the study in filling the gap identified in the literature, the main variables have been included to understand how previously conducted studies have defined the main themes of the study such as change management, employee engagement, changing workplace conditions and employee productivity. Moreover, the literature review has also incorporated a detailed description of the main variables of employee engagement such as vigour, absorption and dedication that have further helped in generating the conceptual framework of the study. In addition, the chapter has been important for identifying gaps existing in the study area and due to these, allied main themes have also been included. These themes are the relationship between employee engagement and employee productivity, the relationship between changing workplace conditions and employee productivity, the impact of changing workplace conditions on employee productivity and the impact of changing employee engagement on employee productivity. Lastly, the theoretical framework of the research includes the Zinger Model of Engagement and the ADKAR model.

2.2. Change Management

The concept of change management has been taken into consideration to move towards growth and development. Different studies are conducted in this domain to understand and explain change and the causes for which change is implemented. However, before approaching the causes

and need for change, it is necessary to understand what change is and what is meant by the concept of change management. Considering the study conducted by Hechanova (2012), change can be described as the crystallisation of new possibilities in the form of new behaviours, patterns, development of products or services or simply the invention of a process which differs from others. Furthermore, it has also been further elaborated by the same researcher that change is nothing but the architecture that comprises new patterns, reconceptualisation of an old phenomenon with the new one for productive actions and better solutions. To further investigate the above definition of change, it can be stated that change is the process of moving from the unknown to the known state. It is evident that the implementation of change brings uncertainty in terms of the future of the possible change as its effectiveness cannot be predicted.

It is evident from the historical perspective that the concept of change management has progressively developed in the last 40 to 50 years (Rasche and Rehder, 2018). Considering the study conducted by Parker (2013), the concept of change management was misused and mistrusted when it was initially developed. The concept of change management was devalued in terms of complex business structures. However, the study presented by Parker has provided sufficient evidence in relation to how change becomes essential for the survival and effective progression of businesses. It was highlighted in the study conducted by Parker et al. (2013) that the rapid changes in technology have forced the business structures to become less complex to meet the demand and challenges of operating with conventional business approaches and strategies. It has been identified in the respective research that mass production in the 1960s demanded the use of technology to form a balance between demand and production (Gersick, 2019).

The role of change management is important in the identification of the weaknesses and flaws of an organisation. The rationale behind this is the fact that leadership, through effective change management policy, first identifies and assesses the entire business operation and implements such policies as can fulfil the cause for which the change has been implemented. Several studies have been conducted in this domain in relation to the importance of change management in developing businesses and helping them to strive for progressive and continuous development. For instance, the arguments presented by MacKay (2013) and Lehmann (2017) are convincing enough regarding the role of change management in elevating declining business.

According to MacKay (2013), the role of strategic change or change management is instrumental in delivering and achieving purposeful aims and targets for businesses.

This can be observed in the strategy of Hero MotoCorp; the company, in 2020, decided to overhaul the top tier of management to implement the management (Hero MotoCorp, 2020). Hero MotoCorp created a new position, Chief of Staff, and recruited Rajat Bhargav to streamline the company's international strategy. Rajat Bhargav has experience in international mergers and acquisitions, and has worked extensively with Mckinsey (Ghosh, 2020). Hired in 2020, Rajat Bhargav was instrumental in the Harley-Davidson & Hero MotoCorp agreement (Pal, 2020).

2.3. Employee Engagement

Gaining employee engagement has been an important objective of the management and a major priority for the leadership and therefore, various techniques have been adopted, and a high emphasis is laid on keeping employees engaged (Osborne and Hammoud, 2017; Thomas, 2020). Turnover rate within the industries worldwide is becoming a major problem for the organisations (Iqbal, 2010; Thomas, 2020) as increased job switching is observed which is costly as well as being consuming in terms of time and effort for the firms. Therefore, the pressure upon the management to execute the policies of the company along with keeping the workforce engaged is gaining momentum. Hence, it is observed that the engagement and retention of employees are becoming difficult tasks due to the unhinged economic conditions (Chandani et al., 2016; Gallup, 2021). Due to the importance of employee engagement to the organisation, several studies around the globe are being compiled to identify the factors that affect employee engagement negatively or positively.

Employee engagement can be explained in various ways. An involved employee can be described as an ambassador of the organisation, who other than producing effective results, does not switch jobs regularly and is of immense value to the firm (Koskinen, 2015; Valamis, 2021). The productivity of an engaged worker is attained through motivation for work which eventually leads to the success of the organisation (Dalal et al. 2012; Valamis, 2021). To achieve this, the organisation must offer an appropriate working environment for the employee for whom the job specifications are clearly defined and united with the firm's objectives. Engagement of three different levels can be experienced by a worker within an organisation; an employee can either be

engaged, he can be not engaged or disengaged (Chandani et al., 2016; Gallup, 2021). Engaged employees are those who work at their maximum potential to achieve the goals of the firm, whereas disengaged employees are likely to switch their jobs.

In the light of the research study conducted by Chandani et al. (2016), employee engagement depends upon the evaluation and perception of employees regarding their experience of work which includes the work environment, job, leaders of the organisation and their employer. Managers should pay attention to the talent, knowledge, and skills of their staff in order to enhance the engagement level of an employee. According to the study conducted by Schaufeli and Bakker (2010), employees that are aware of their talents and strengths tend to have a better level of engagement which ultimately leads to better performance in the organisation. The work engagement of an employee can be reflected through involvement, efficacy, behavioural satisfaction, and energy. The engagement of an employee results from work motivation and employee satisfaction. There are several definitions related to employee engagement that exist in the literature. It has been stated by Sarangi and Srivastava (2012) that employee engagement is the ability to capture the souls, hearts and heads of your employees to instil a passion for excellence and an intrinsic desire. The involvement and commitment of an employee towards the work aimed at improving the performance of an organisation are reflected by employee engagement.

2.4. Employee Productivity

It is the basic need of an organisation to improve the productivity of employees in order to ensure the achievement of organisational goals and objectives (Sivanandam, 2021). In the light of the research study conducted by Hanaysha (2016), the valuation of efficiency of a worker or group of workers is referred to as employee productivity. Productivity in actual terms is a component by which the profit of the company is directly affected. In a specific period of time, productivity may be evaluated in terms of the employee's output. Productivity can also be assessed in terms of the amount of units of a service or product which is handled by employees in a particular time frame (Sivanandam, 2021). According to the study conducted by Osborne and Hammoud (2017), the productivity of employees has become an important objective for businesses as the success of any organisation depends mainly on the productivity of employees working in it. However, there is a lack of standardisation and effective ways to assess the productivity of an employee.

In the light of the research study conducted by Sharma and Sharma (2014), besides the extent to which the employee is working efficiently or mentally present during the job, the productivity of an employee is based on the amount of time the employee is present physically at the job (Sivanandam, 2021). In order to ensure the higher productivity of employees, these types of issues must be addressed by companies. According to the study conducted by Abraham (2012), in order to produce the desired outcomes which are expected from the job description of an employee, the evaluation of productivity can be in terms of time that is spent by an employee who is actively executing the job for which they were hired. It has been stated by Sharma and Sharma (2014) that higher productivity results in social progress, higher profitability and economic growth. With increased productivity, employees can increase their employment opportunities to obtain better working conditions and salaries or wages (Sivanandam, 2021).

For the success of the organisation, the key contributor is the alignment of the strategic vision with employee productivity. This alignment inspires and motivates employees to become creative and to improve the effectiveness of their performance to accomplish the objectives and goals of the organisation (Banya, 2019). Through the improvement in quality and reduction in the cost of output, higher productivity tends to increase the competitive advantage of the organisation. According to the study conducted by Simha and Vardan (2015), the productivity of an employee has a significant impact on the profitability of the organisation. If the productivity of an employee decreases there is an overall decrease in the productivity of an organisation which results in low profitability while increasing the cost of production (Banya, 2019). In the light of the research study conducted by Kompas and Sridevi (2010), low productivity of an employee results in increasing the cost for an organisation because fewer units are produced with the same production cost due to low productivity. As per the annual report from 2019-2020, Hero MotoCorp spent around US\$ 2.6 million on learning and development for its employees and US\$ 13.7 million on employee engagement initiatives (Hero MotoCorp, 2020). These implicitly indicate that Hero MotoCorp believes in employee engagement and is plans to spend a substantial amount on employee engagement and development.

2.5. Changing Workplace Conditions

Working conditions can be defined as the working environment that affects an employee working in a particular environment. Specifically, in a broader context, the working environment of a business may involve different elements such as job hours, physical aspects, legal rights, training, workload, and culture (McCauley & Peterman, 2020). It is important to highlight that working conditions are referred to as the interaction with employees within their organisational climate which integrates the psychological as well as the physical working conditions (McCauley & Peterman, 2020; Polek, 2013). The definition of working conditions can be defined as the integration of the working environment along with aspects of the employee's terms and conditions which an employer sets for an employee.

It is evident that workplace conditions have been changing rapidly because of significant factors that are directly associated with it; for instance, technological factors, the changing environment, and social values and other factors have significantly influenced the business environment of the business sector (Morgan, 2021). It is a noticeable fact that these changing trends in the workplace environment arise because of the continuous changing internal and external business environment that has forced businesses to comply with their business strategies with the changing environment (Morgan, 2021). Considering the study conducted by Meyer (2012), the changing workplace conditions have demanded employees and businesses act more proactively because of the rapid changes which are influencing the business sector. It is important to highlight the focal point presented by Meyer (2012) that the changing workplace conditions force employees to show more commitment to their job and responsibilities. Moreover, it is also highlighted in the existing literature that though the changing workplace conditions make employees dissatisfied and less engaged with their job, still the findings of research have suggested that employee commitment and increased employee engagement are some significant factors that play an instrumental role in effectively managing change because of the changing workplace conditions (Morgan, 2021; McCauley & Peterman, 2020; Polek, 2013).

Furthermore, several studies have also been conducted in which researchers have made efforts to analyse the consequences of a changing workplace environment in relation to employees and businesses themselves (Banya, 2019; McCauley & Peterman, 2020; Polek, 2013; Sivanandam,

2021). According to Nielsen (2012), it becomes important for businesses to identify and assess those factors that can hinder the effectiveness of the change process. According to him, the effectiveness of the change is dependent on how different stakeholders respond to the change and the changing workplace environment (Morgan, 2021; McCauley & Peterman, 2020; Schram et al., 2019). The study of Nielsen concludes as it is acceptable that the effectiveness of the change process is dependent on the achievement of all the desired objectives of managing the change. Nevertheless, the study has concluded that it becomes difficult for businesses to achieve all the desired objectives of the change process. In this regard, it is mandatory for the business to predict and examine all the possibilities and consequences of the change process in order make its workforce familiar with the changing business environment.

Furthermore, several studies have been conducted showing significant literature that assesses the environmental factors that affect the workplace conditions (Satyendra, 2021). Moreover, some studies have also been conducted to examine the factors that affect the sustainability of business organisations (Schram et al., 2020; Shahin et al., 2020). It has been highlighted in the research work conducted by Satyendra (2021) and Unsworth (2012), that pro-environmental behaviours also have a significant impact on the business environment. It has been discussed in the research that different environmental factors cause change in the workplace environment. In this study, it has been suggested that different environmental problems in the form of a shortage of resources and other environmental concerns force employees to implement change which results in a changing workplace environment. In this regard, it also becomes important for businesses to consider these changing environmental problems while accessing changing workplace conditions.

Changing work conditions are a reality and each company needs to best adjust to suit its employees. At a time when the employee attrition rate is quite high, building employee loyalty is one the many ways to shrink the attrition rate to lower the impact on a company's profitability (Schram et al., 2020; Schram et al., 2019). Hero MotoCorp just executed a remuneration method to increase the loyalty component among its employees. With the ongoing pandemic situation due to Covid-19, Hero MotoCorp was at the forefront in assisting their employees in times of uncertainty, Hero MotoCorp released advance monthly payments for contractual employees (*Economic Times*, 2020).

2.6. Factors in Employee Engagement

Employee engagement is the passion or eagerness of an employee towards their work which is achieved through involvement and satisfaction. Employee engagement is characterised by three major categories: vigour, dedication and absorption (Schram et al., 2020; Schram et al., 2019; Schaufeli and Bakker, 2010). Although this was initially suggested by Schaufeli, Salanova, González-Romá and Bakker (Schaufeli and Bakker, 2010), it has been discussed and identified by several authors in their research studies, for instance by Sarangi and Srivastava (2012), Zarban (2018), Drake (2018) and many more. Due to the importance of these factors of employee engagement, a comprehensive discussion will be conducted on these in the following section.

Hero MotoCorp is the largest manufacturer of two-wheelers in the world. To attain and sustain this position, the company needs to focus on multiple employee productivity factors. Employee productivity depends on the degree to which workers feel passionate about their work, and the extent to which they are committed to the company. Schaufeli and Bakker's (2010) and Valamis's (2021) framework listed below, shows different factors playing an important role in employee productivity.

Figure 2: Source: Schaufeli and Bakker (2010) and Valamis (2021)

2.6.1. Vigour

The literal meaning of the word vigour is physical strength or energy and enthusiasm. It is an important factor in employee engagement (Gera et al., 2019). Employees that are enthusiastic about their work tend to be engaged and are resourceful for the organisation. Sarangi and Srivastava (2012) conducted a study to identify the impact of organisational culture and communication on employee engagement. Amongst the various employee engagement factors or components, vigour was utilised by the authors. Data were collected from 247 executives in the banking sector and the findings of the study reveal that culture and the level of communication within the organisation has a positive impact on the vigorousness of employees. Firstly, this illustrates that vigour or enthusiasm is an important part of employee engagement and second, it is influenced by the culture and communication of the firm (Andrianto & Alsada, 2019). A firm's management that is cooperative and provides an effective working environment for the employees tends to create passion and enthusiasm within the employees (Gera et al., 2019).

Vigour is the level of energy that an employee inputs while working; it is the inclination to devote determination and mental pliability within work. Rothmann and Rothmann Jr. (2010) carried out a study to identify the factors associated with employee engagement within a corporation. The determinants of employee engagement as identified by Rothmann and Rothmann Jr. (2010) were vigour, dedication and absorption. According to the authors, vigour is amongst the most important factors of employee engagement. Using the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES) scale consisting of 17 items to measure workers involvement, the findings of the study indicated that vigour or passion of the employees is substantially related to the support that they receive from the organisation. Vigour, which is a major component of engagement, was influenced by growth opportunities, support of the firm, support from the social circle and progress (Andrianto & Alsada, 2019; Gera et al., 2019). Thus, as proposed by Schaufeli and Bakker (2010) and further researched by Rothmann and Rothmann Jr. (2010) and Sarangi and Srivastava (2012), vigour is a crucial component of employee engagement. Speaking at "Conclave 2019", Samarjit Banerjee, head hr of Hero MotoCorp emphasised the need for "Vigour", to drive productivity (People Matters, 2020).

Samarjit Banerjee specifically spoke about the need to engage blue-collar employees, a working-class employee performing manual tasks. Vigour is especially important in the case of Hero MotoCorp because it churns out more two-wheelers than any other factory in the world; as per the estimate, Hero MotoCorp manufactures a two-wheeler every 18 seconds (People Matters, 2020).

2.6.2. Dedication

Dedication is the devotion and commitment of the employees towards their work and their organisation (Sittar, 2020). A dedicated employee will be satisfied and engaged with the organisation, and this will be revealed in the performance of the employee. Replicating ideas, processes and products is something that can be achieved easily; however, what an organisation cannot replicate is the dedication of the workers within the firm (Sittar, 2020). As per Kuntsi (2014), dedication is an effective way through which organisations can foster and enhance the engagement level of the employees. Illustrating that dedication will lead to employee engagement. There are numerous ways to enhance the dedication level of employees; providing them with challenging but attainable tasks, improved working conditions (Kuranchie-Mensah and Amponsah-Tawiah, 2016), bonus and incentives, promotions and effective communication between the employers and the employees are some techniques through which the devotion level of the employees can be enhanced which ultimately leads to a high level of involvement and improved performance (Hanaysha, 2016).

Zarban (2018), in his study, has indicated that dedication is one of the three elements of employee engagement. The aim of the paper was to identify the effect of leadership styles on the job engagement level of hotel employees. Various leadership styles were tested in the study such as transformational and transactional styles and while identifying the employee engagement factors, the author considered dedication as one of the factors of employee engagement. The findings of the study indicate that the styles of leadership influence employee engagement and the dedication level of the employees is highly dependent on the style of the leaders. The secondary findings of the study indicate that hotel employees in the United States, particularly male employees, are not dedicated to their work. And as discussed above by Rothmann and Rothmann Jr. (2010), organisational support and progress opportunities influence the level of dedication of the workers; therefore, the hotel management should provide support and opportunities for

development to the employees to enhance their levels of dedication. Hero MotoCorp has taken several initiatives to nurture “Dedication and Commitment”; for instance, Hero MotoCorp launched “Project Tejaswani” to increase the number of female employees and empower them, with required skill sets to contribute towards self-development, thereby nudging the increase of “Dedication and Commitment”, towards Hero MotoCorp (Outlook, 2019).

2.6.3. Absorption

Absorption is the involvement of the employees within the organisation’s decision-making processes (Gera et al., 2019). It has been observed that the level of motivation of the employees is highly attributed to the level of absorption within the organisation and as discussed by Schaufeli and Bakker (2010), it is a major component of employee engagement. The authors, in their study, have mentioned that absorption is the complete feeling that employees experience when they act in a totally involved manner. It is a prevalent and tenacious state of attentiveness and effort. Sarangi and Srivastava (2012) have also argued that absorption is the internal motivation and encouragement which is a sort of craving for participation in the activities that are challenging. Authors like Lee, Sheldon and Turban (2003) have stated that absorption and attention are two similar things and are associated with engagement with the process of self-regulation which is a process that describes the conversion of motivation into the performance of the worker. Thus, it can be stated that absorption is a major element of employee engagement as a motivated employee is inclined to work productively and in an engaging manner (Baran & Sypniewska, 2020).

Absorption is the opposite of inefficiency which means that there is an association between absorption and efficiency (Gera et al., 2019). Drake (2018) defined absorption as having a greater level of motivation on the job. The motivation that Drake (2018) implies here is the internal motivation that leads to a high level of engagement among the employees. Absorption is considered a crucial determinant of employee engagement. The factors that influence absorption are support of the top management and the opportunities to grow and progress professionally as identified by Rothmann and Rothmann Jr. (2010) in their study. Thus, the findings of the following section of the literature conclude that vigour, dedication and absorption are three important elements of employee management as proposed by Schaufeli and Bakker (2010) and the major factors that influence these elements are firm support and the chances to progress. Hence the

organisation must ensure that these two factors are catered to effectively to ensure a high level of job engagement. The reason behind the phenomenal growth of Hero MotoCorp and its manufacturing capacity to become the largest manufacturer of two-wheelers in the world is the factor of “Absorption”, where Hero MotoCorp employees treat every task as a mission; for instance, the research and development wing, and manufacturing unit worked together to become the first company in the world to manufacture the 100 millionth two-wheeler (*Times Now*, 2021). Hero MotoCorp was at the forefront in serving the people when the Covid-19 pandemic hit the world; the company soon switched gears and started manufacturing sanitisers to fight Corona virus. This was only possible because of a dedicated set of employees of Hero MotoCorp, where stakeholders are involved in the decision-making process to best achieve the company’s objectives (Shah, 2020).

2.7 Factors Associated with Working Conditions Driving Employee Productivity

According to Bakker (2014), working conditions are referred to as the working environment and other physical aspects that are provided to an employee and which have an impact on its productivity. There are several factors that are associated with working conditions and eventually drive the productivity of an employee. The following factors are discussed below:

2.7.1 Working Hours

It is evident that working hours have a positive impact on employee productivity. The reason for this can be that working hours involving either shift rotation or night shifts may not suit most employees (Okazaki et al., 2019). Though there are some people that would like to perform their duties on night shift, the majority of the population prefer offices with conventional job timings (Ali, 2013). It is important to highlight that some people would also not mind doing night shifts occasionally; however, a series of night shifts may raise considerable challenges. One of the prominent challenges is fatigue, sleeplessness, absenteeism that eventually results in decreased individual performance (Okazaki et al., 2019). Moreover, the productivity of an employee can also be greatly damaged once an employee becomes emotionally exhausted.

Furthermore, the argument presented by Pencavel (2014) is also convincing enough that when an employee is asked to sit for long working hours that may be because of training, the load season

or others, then employees naturally feel dissatisfied with work and the specific working conditions. This indicates that for employees, long working hours for the purpose of increased productivity actually results in decreased productivity and quality of work (Okazaki et al., 2019). Therefore, it can be stated that working hours represent an important constituent of working conditions and have a significant impact on employee productivity.

In the case of Hero MotoCorp, it follows a six-day working pattern, where employees are given required gaps to rejuvenate themselves and maintain efficiency. In the case of pregnant employee, the company has special extended maternity leave of 210 days and a 2 days of work from home policy with a 1.5-hour nursing break with the availability of childcare facilities on campus (Outlook, 2020).

2.7.2 Workload

Considering the study conducted by Tan (2014), workload can be defined as the extent of processing capacity which becomes a crucial factor during the performance of a task and indicates the relationship between resource and task. Therefore, it can be stated that the workload signifies the interaction between demand and resources (Davidescu et al., 2020). An employee, while fulfilling a task over its set capacity, requires extra effort, skill, and actions to perform the task within the specified allotted time. This extra workload does give financial benefits to employees in the form of bonuses and others; however, to a greater extent, the continuous high workload does leave a negative impact on employees' physical and mental health (Davidescu et al., 2020).

As managing high workload requires extra skills and efforts along with late sitting, therefore this makes an employee dissatisfied. The consequences of the workload results in increased absenteeism, lateness, and reduces the focus on the given task which is directly associated with the quality and productivity that an employee produces (Ali, 2013). Therefore, on the basis of the above arguments, it can be stated that employee productivity is being influenced by one of the important factors of working conditions that is workload.

In the case of Hero MotoCorp, the company has devised an innovative framework which works on managing remuneration along with the given workload by the company. It works on a simplistic parameter with a focus on finance and skill development, where employees who put in extra hours

and effort are paid additionally. Employees who intend to progress are given special training and support through different development programmes and a buddy system. Hero MotoCorp often announces special bonuses for its employees on achieving a new milestone; for example, rolling out the 100 millionth two-wheeler from its manufacturing unit was celebrated as a carnival in the company with the participation of employees (Hero MotoCorp, 2021).

2.7.3 Technology and Facilities

In the light of the research study conducted by Acemoglu (2012), the technological advancements at the work environment play a significant role in increasing the productivity of employees. Technology used throughout the processes of an organisation minimises the wastage from production. The technology helps the employees to reduce the time which is taken throughout the process which allows them to capitalise on this opportunity by increasing their productivity (Duran & Sanchez, 2021). On the other hand, technology also reduces the numbers in the workforce from the organisation which demotivates other employees of the organisation. According to the research study conducted by AIDamoe, Yazam and Ahmid (2012), technology is one of the factors which reduces the number of employees in an organisation which results in the increased turnover rate of the organisation. This affects the productivity of other employees in the organisation as they feel insecure about their jobs.

In the light of the research study conducted by Spencer, Buhalis and Moital (2012), the employees of an organisation which is technologically advanced are more productive as compared to the organisation which is yet to adopt technology in the process. This is because technology helps employees to economise on time which is beneficial for doing other tasks in the meantime (Duran & Sanchez, 2021). However, technology can also negatively affect the productivity of the employee if the employee is not aware of that technology or does not have skills or knowledge. In this sense, technology can affect the productivity of the employees in an organisation. According to the research study conducted by Sageer, Rafat and Agarwal (2012), there is a significant role of technology in the productivity of employees in an organisation which directly affects the profitability of the organisation. This relationship shows that technology plays a vital role in increasing employee productivity in an organisation (Duran & Sanchez, 2021).

Hero MotoCorp is at the forefront of using technology; to enhance its capabilities, Hero Moto Corp has developed Integrated Learning Management System (ILMS). The aim behind utilising ILMS is to enhance the learning management process of employees at different touch points. This encompasses a host of learning management processes starting from recruiting, training and development, and deployment till separation. This process of ILMS also assists the channel partners of Hero MotoCorp since the attrition rate is very high and since the induction of ILMS in the system there is a marked improvement in the overall process. Hero MotoCorp was the first company in India to experiment with “Digital Twins” in 2017 (Business Today, 2018). A digital twin is the creation or gathering of digital data constituting a physical object. The concept of a digital twin has its source in engineering and developing engineering graphics. Hero MotoCorp’s research and development wing is working on emerging technologies. Recently, Hero MotoCorp has deployed a Remote Support Solution using smart glasses & AR technology in critical manufacturing units, resulting in improved efficiency of diagnostics and significant reductions in downtime for maintenance of equipment and facilities (Hero MotoCorp, 2019). Hero MotoCorp is investing heavily in artificial intelligence and the internet of things to stay ahead of the curve in mobility.

2.8 Review of Articles

Past literature about employee engagement, changing workplaces, and their relationship and impact on employee productivity are listed below by segmentation into year of publication, aim of research, methodology of the research and implications of the research. Apart from the findings and conclusion, this table also throws light on how research has evolved over the past couple of decades in relation to employee engagement, changing workplace, and employee productivity.

S.No.	Author	Year of Publication	Aim of Research	Research Methodology	Research Findings and Conclusion
1	Chandani, Mehta, Mall and Khokhar	2016	Identifying the factors affecting employee engagement.	Secondary data collected from thirty academic and popular research papers.	A sense of involvement, opportunity thinking, enhancing employee decision-making and commitment lead to engagement which in

					turn results in decline in employee turnover intentions and increase in innovative work-related behaviour.
2	Dalal, Baysinger, Brummel and LeBreton	2012	To discuss the relative importance of employee engagement, other job attitudes, and trait affect as predictors of job performance	Used univariate and multivariate relative weight analysis to assess the relative importance of the variables and data were collected from 191 participants.	The results indicate that the best predictors of overall employee performance were trait negative affect, employee engagement, and job satisfaction. Moreover, the results were unaffected by the removal of a few behavioural items (akin to OCB) from measures of employee engagement. Implications and suggestions for future research are discussed.
3	Sarangi and Srivastava	2012	To identify the impact of Organisational Culture and Communication on Employee Engagement.	The sample consists of 247 executives drawn from the banking sector.	The study found out that organisational culture and organisational support in the form of communication have a major impact on the engagement level of the employees.
4	Zarban	2018	To identify the impact of leadership styles on the engagement level of the employees in hotel management.	This study used a quantitative method, specifically survey, that was distributed to the United States hotel employees through	This study found that 'fairness' was evaluated as the most valuable driver to make employees feel engaged at work. The findings of this study showed that there is a significant relationship between

				Amazon M-Turk. The survey measures employee level of engagement using UWES and leadership styles using MLQ in addition to 18 drivers of engagement and 10 demographic questions.	transformational and transactional leadership behaviour and employee engagement whilst significant negative correlation was found between the perceived passive/avoidant leadership and employee engagement.
5	Drake	2018	Assessing Employee Engagement and presenting a comparison between the Job Engagement Scale (JES) and The Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES).	Data were collected from 470 working adults. The measures were compared by examining their convergent and discriminant construct validity, examining the factor structure of each measure, and examining the criterion-related validity of each through dominance analysis.	Significant differences between the UWES and JES in terms of construct and criterion-related validity evidence. UWES has less psychometric strength than the JES; however, it is more strongly related to stress-related criteria than the JES.
6	Rothmann and Rothmann	2010	To identify the factors associated with employee	Survey designs were used with two samples taken from	The results of the study showed that two psychological conditions, namely

			engagement in South Africa.	various South African organisations ($n = 467$ and $n = 3775$). The Work Engagement Scale, the Psychological Conditions Scale and the Antecedents Scale were administered for the purposes of the study. The Utrecht Work Engagement Scale and the Job Demands-Resources Scale were also administered.	psychological meaningfulness and psychological availability, were positively associated with employee engagement. Work role fit was the best predictor of psychological meaningfulness and employee engagement. The findings indicate that job resources were positively associated with employee engagement. Organisational support and growth opportunities were the best predictors of vigour, dedication and absorption.
7	Kuntsi	2014	The first objective was to determine what the prerequisites of work engagement are among the case company's consultants and the second objective was to determine how the supervisors of these consultants foster work engagement through their actions.	The research data were collected through semi-structured interviews with five consultants and five supervisors working in the case company's office in Tampere. The case company's job satisfaction inquiry from the year 2012	The findings of the study indicate that the case company's consultants are dedicated and thus engaged in their work. The dedication enhancing themes among the consultants are appreciation, supervisor's work support, social relationships and cooperation, supervisor's genuine interest and caring, innovative activities and thoughts, success, trust, content and

				was also utilised as an additional source of information. The research data were analysed via content analysis and approached from a factual point of view.	quantity of tasks, consultant's personal characteristics, supervisor's own example, significance of tasks, challenging work, and employer.
8	Kuranchie-Mensah and Amponsah-Tawiah	2016	The paper empirically compares employee motivation and its impact on performance in Ghanaian Mining Companies, where, in measuring performance, the job satisfaction model is used.	The study employed an exploratory research design in gathering data from four large-scale gold mining companies in Ghana with regard to their policies and structures in the effectiveness of motivational tools and strategies used by these companies.	The study observed that, due to the risk factors associated with the mining industry, management has to ensure that employees are well motivated to curb the rate at which employees embark on industrial unrest which affects performance, and employees are to comply with health and safety rules because the industry contributes hugely to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the country.
9	Hanaysha	2016	This study examines the effect of work engagement on employee productivity in the higher education sector.	Primary data using survey instrument were collected from a sample of 242 employees at public universities in	The results indicated that work engagement had a significant positive effect on employee productivity. Moreover, this study provides evidence that all the dimensions of work engagement,

				northern Malaysia using an online survey method. The collected data were analysed using SPSS and Structural equation modelling on AMOS.	namely vigour, dedication, and absorption, have significant positive effects on employee productivity.
10	Lee, Sheldon and Turban	2003	The purpose of this study is to examine the mechanisms by which personality traits influence performance and satisfaction. Specifically, the authors examined how three personality characteristics derived from self-determination theory (autonomy, control, and a motivated orientations) influence performance and enjoyment through achievement goal patterns, goal level, and mental focus.	Data were collected from 284 undergraduate students enrolled in a required introductory management course at a large university in the Midwest.	Mental focus emerged as an important aspect of the self-regulation process. The results suggest that global personality traits can help researchers to understand and predict the motivational strategies that people use while working toward goals in achievement settings.
11	Ajala, E.M.	2012	The influence of workplace environment on workers' welfare, performance and productivity.	Descriptive research survey	A poor and unsafe workplace environment results in significant losses for workers, their families, and the national economy.

12	Ali, A.Y.S., Ali, A.A. and Adan, A.A.	2013	Working conditions and employees' productivity in manufacturing companies in sub-Saharan African context: case of Somalia	Correlation research design	Working conditions are found to have an impact on employee productivity.
13	Anitha, J.	2014	Determinants of employee engagement and their impact on employee performance.	Casual study	It was found that all the identified factors were predictors of employee engagement.
14	Iqbal, A., Ijaz, M., Latif, F. and Mushtaq, H.	2015	Factors affecting the employee's performance: a case study of the banking sector in Pakistan.	Regression analysis using SPSS software	There is a positive relationship between financial rewards and employees' performance in the banking sector of Pakistan.
15	Chandrasekar , K.	2011	Workplace environment and its impact on organisational performance in public sector organisations.	Descriptive research	Workplace environment plays a vital role in motivating employees to perform their assigned work.
16	Jain, R. and Kaur, S.	2014	Impact of work environment on job satisfaction.	Quantitative research	The results show that a strong relationship exists between job security and job satisfaction.
17	Kelchtermans , G.	2006	Teacher collaboration and collegiality as workplace conditions.	Descriptive research	Forms of collaboration and collegiality can take place that really contribute to pupils' learning, teacher development and

					quality of school improvement.
18	Khan, U.R. and Salahuddin, W.	2018	Impact of Workplace Environment on Employees' Performance.	Convenient & Random Sampling Technique	The result of the study indicates that workload, stress, overtime, fatigue, boredom are some factors which increase job dissatisfaction.
19	Gitahi	2014	Effect of workplace environment on the performance of commercial banks and employees in Nakuru town	Descriptive statistics and multiple regression models were used.	physical aspects did not have a significant effect on employee performance while the psychosocial and work life balance factors were significant.
10	Mariscal, López-Perea, García-Herrero, López-García and Herrera	2018	Data on the working population in Spain related to training, workplace conditions and accident rates.	Quantitative research	The majority of these data collected after the accident occurs, do not consider the employee's working conditions.
20	Parding and Berg-Jansson	2018	Conditions for workplace learning in professional work: discrepancies between occupational and organisational values.	Thematic analysis	This paper shows how teachers at upper secondary level identify their subjects as the most important to learn more within.
21	Pedersen, Minnotte, K.L., Kiger and Mannon	2009	Workplace policy and environment, family role quality, and positive family-to-work spill over.	Descriptive analysis	Women's owns workplace conditions.

22	Hetzner, Heid and Gruber	2015	Using workplace changes as learning opportunities: antecedents to reflection in professional work.	Correlation analyses and hierarchical regression analyses	The results revealed that both individuals' personal initiative and self-efficacy significantly positively affect reflection at work.
23	Shantz, Alfes, Truss and Soane	2013	To identify the role of employee engagement in the relationship between job design and task performance, citizenship and deviant behaviours.	Quantitative study with survey conducted with 283 respondents who were employees in the construction and consultancy industry of the UK.	Employees that are conscious of their capacities and strengths are inclined to have an improved level of engagement which eventually leads to better productivity in the organisation.
24	Osborne and Hammoud	2017	The aim of this case study was to discover strategies that certain communication corporate leaders use to engage their personnel.	Semi-structured interviews conducted and analysed by thematic analysis	The longevity of the firm is also affected by employee engagement but in contrast to this, improved employee productivity can lead to higher organisational financial performance.
25	Sharma and Sharma	2014	The aim is to focus on employee engagement as the antecedent of job involvement and making employees engaged to improve employee productivity.	The research was based on a qualitative secondary method.	Employee engagement can be regarded as the major element for the organisation to achieve its mission and generate desirable business results along with executing business strategy.

26	Abraham	2012	To identify how job satisfaction can be considered an antecedent to employee engagement.	A quantitative descriptive study was conducted where a survey questionnaire was conducted amongst 50 employees working in an insurance company.	There is a significant effect of employee engagement on employee productivity. It has been further identified in the research that engaged employees are often inclined towards exhibiting and showing emotional job attachment on a higher level that led towards higher productivity.
27	Simha and Vardan	2015	The main aim is to focus on how employee engagement is leading towards employees' performance and productivity.	Secondary qualitative study	Employee engagement is regarded as interwoven in the significant business outcomes and due to this, it has essentially impacted the performance of the firms. In the light of this research, it has also been identified that there are certain outcomes that can be achieved through higher employee engagement such as employee retention, customer loyalty safety and employee productivity and organisational profitability.
29	Kompaso and Sridev	2010	The main aim is to discuss employee engagement as the key to improving employee performance.	Secondary qualitative	Employers are largely engaged in realising the importance of focusing on employee engagement and for this purpose, they have

					also been inclined towards creating a more effective and productive workforce.
30	Robertson, Jansen Birch and Cooper	2012	The main aim is to test the hypothesis stating that levels of employee productivity will be predicted by an amalgamation of employee engagement as well as psychological well-being.	Multiple regression analyses conducted after conducting a survey questionnaire from 9000 employees from 12 organisations	Senior managers are highly attracted towards the view of employee engagement because of its linkage with performance and productivity of the employees working in the organisation.
31	Vance	2006	The aim is to discuss employee engagement and commitment: a guide to understanding, measuring and increasing engagement in your organisation	Secondary qualitative	Employees who are highly engaged in their jobs and are committed to their firms give a crucial competitive advantage to the companies in terms of lower employee turnover and higher productivity.
32	Andrew and Sofian	2012	The main aim is to analyse the uncertainty about the effect of individual factors of employee engagement on work outcomes.	Quantitative survey questionnaire from 104 HR officers	Higher employee engagement could be regarded as the major factor that can lead to higher organisational success and performance because it has a sufficient potential to affect loyalty, retention and productivity of the employees, organisational reputation, customer

					satisfaction and stakeholder value.
33	Moreland	2013	The main aim is to discuss how improving job fit can improve employee engagement and productivity.	Secondary qualitative	Workers and employees who are disengaged tend to show lower productivity as compared to those who are engaged within the organisation.
34	Shuck, Reio and Rocco	2011	The main aim was to discover likely associations between promising antecedents of engagement and organisational outcome.	Quantitative study conducted with survey questionnaire conducted with 283 respondents	Employee engagement shares a significant relationship with the outcome variables of the organisation such as employee behaviour, job performance and employee productivity.
35	Hechanova, R. M., & Cementina-Olpoc, R.	2012	To study Transformational Leadership, Change Management, and Commitment to Change for the comparison of Academic and Business Organisations.	The survey research strategy was conducted by the researcher in order to acquire the views of 305 employees and 267 employees from higher education academic institutions and employees from the business organisation.	In the study, it was found that employees of academic institutions rated their leaders more in challenging the status quo in comparison with the leaders that were leading the business. The respective study concludes that there is a difference in the nature of the two different types of leaders and leadership.
36	Parker, D., Charlton, J., Ribeiro, A.,	2013	To assess and examine the effectiveness of integrated project management and	Different project management tools and techniques	The findings of this study suggested that change management enhances field activities, especially

	& D. Pathak, R.		change management.	along with the secondary findings were used to assess the research phenomenon.	activities in managing projects and how the intervention of technology has resulted in improved productivity and performance for businesses.
37	MacKay, R. B., & Chia, R.	2013	To assess and examine various choices, changes and consequences while implementing change.	The findings of this study have been based on the case of NorthCo Automotive.	The findings of this study have suggested that for the implementation of an effective change process, it becomes essential to consider various other factors to achieve the purposeful objectives of delivering change.
38	Meyer, J. P., Stanley, L. J., & Parfyonova, N. M.	2012	To assess the employee commitment within the context of a changing workplace environment.	The quantitative research was conducted through a survey involving 403 employees.	The findings of this research have suggested that employees' commitment and engagement in the workplaces help businesses in implementing the change and ensuring its effectiveness.
39	Nielsen, K., & Randall, R.	2012	To assess the importance of employee participation in managing change and the perception of changes in team working interventions.	Quantitative research conducted through the survey involving 583 employees.	The study concludes as it is acceptable that the effectiveness of the change process is dependent on the achievement of all the desired objectives of managing the change. Nevertheless, the study has concluded that it becomes difficult for

					businesses to achieve all the desired objectives of the change process.
40	Unsworth	2012	Assessing the importance of increasing workplace interventions in creating pro-environmental behaviour of change.	The secondary research strategy followed by qualitative research design helped the researcher to study the respective phenomenon from different aspects.	It has been suggested that different environmental problems in the form of a shortage of resources and other environmental concerns force employees to implement change which results in a changing workplace environment.
41	Polek	2013	To assess the level of working conditions in relation to employee productivity specific to the case of sawmills in pole region.	Survey strategy means the quantitative research design was preferred by the researcher to conduct the respective study.	The findings of the study suggest that not only employee productivity is dependent on the individual talent, but also productivity is dependent on the internal and external factors that influence employee productivity.
42	Ali	2013	To assess the relationship between employee productivity and employee productivity and working conditions in manufacturing companies.	The survey questionnaire was provided to 150 respondents and the quantitative research design helped the researcher to conduct the respective study.	The researcher found that when employees are exposed to hectic, unsafe and stressful working conditions, then employee productivity is affected. Similarly, it has also been discussed in the literature that when employees are provided with good and healthy working conditions,

					then the productivity of employees is positively influenced.
43	Davies & Crane	2010	To create employee engagement in a strong triple bottom-line philosophy.	The secondary research strategy followed by qualitative design helped to conduct the research.	The organisations must expend more effort on formalising their social programmes to ensure the engagement of employees.
44	Rich, Lepine and Crawford	2010	To develop theory that positions engagement explaining the relationship between organisational factors and individual characteristics.	The survey questionnaire was provided to 150 participants and the quantitative research design helped to conduct the study.	Employee engagement has an impact on the characteristics of individuals and factors of the organisation.

Main Findings:

Employee engagement is a broad concept that is linked to nearly every aspect of human resource management that we are familiar with. Employees refuse to completely involve themselves in their jobs in reaction to such mismanagement if all aspects of human resources are not handled appropriately. Employee engagement is based on previous principles such as work satisfaction, employee loyalty, and organisational citizenship behaviour. Employee involvement is a wider term that is connected to and incorporates these definitions. Employee engagement is a major validator of positive organisational output visibility showing the ‘to and fro’ relationship between company and employee compared to the three earlier constructs: work satisfaction, employee loyalty, and organisational citizenship behaviour. Engaged employees are emotionally connected to their company and are immensely involved in their job, working with great enthusiasm for the prosperity of their employer, performing extra mile duties beyond the company’s contractual

agreement. Companies should step outside their primitive roles and comfort zones to explore new ways of working. They must create a congenial environment where employees relish what they do, giving them a sense that they have a purpose, giving them pride in what they do, and allowing them to progress up the hierarchy by utilising their potential. Employee performance is the amalgamation of hard work, capability, and the perception of task. Employee performance is the cornerstone of a company's profitability and success. Many facets influence employee performance; and workplace environment factors stands out as the key motivator of performance.

2.9. The Relationship Between Employee Engagement and Employee Productivity

The research conducted by Shantz et al. (2013) has revealed that employees who are highly engaged in the organisation due to higher levels of task variety, autonomy, feedback, and significance tend to show higher performance and productivity. It has been further identified in the study that an engaged workforce can lead towards higher productivity ratings from the supervisors whereas organisation citizenship behaviour tends to engage more employees with deviant behaviour. However, the research has not directly analysed the relationship between employee productivity and employee engagement but rather demonstrated productivity as the goal that can be achieved through differing factors of employee engagement such as task variety, autonomy, feedback, and significance (Satata, 2021). Nevertheless, this research has filled this gap by identifying the relationship between the two. The study considered Hero MotoCorp to analyse the above gap because it gives an immense opportunity to explore this facet since Hero MotoCorp has been through an overhaul process since its separation with Honda Motors.

According to the research undertaken by Hanaysha (2016), workplace engagement is directly associated with employee productivity where the former has a significant as well as a positive impact on employee productivity. The research has also focused on numerous dimensions related to workplace engagement such as absorption, dedication and vigour that have a direct impact on employee productivity. Similarly, this research has also adopted these three factors to indicate the relationship between employee engagement and employee productivity and identified the impact of engagement on productivity. In addition to this, the research of Osborne and Hammoud (2017) has also supported the notion of strategic behaviour of employee engagement and indicated that it has a direct impact on employee productivity. However, the research of Osborne and Hammoud

(2017) has also proposed the notion that the longevity of a firm is also affected by employee engagement but in contrast to this, improved employee productivity can lead to higher organisational financial performance. Nevertheless, the research did not identify how employee engagement can be combined with workplace conditions and how it impacts employee productivity within firms and this gap has been filled by this study (Satata, 2021). Hence, the interviews that were conducted with Hero MotoCorp employees had questions pertaining to “employee engagement”, “workplace conditions” and “productivity”. The research carried out by Sharma and Sharma (2014) indicated that employee engagement can be regarded as the major element for the organisation to achieve its mission and generate desirable business results along with executing business strategy. According to Drake (2018), the well-being of employees from their job is determined through the environment and conditions of the workplace which have been identified as essential factors in measuring and raising employee productivity. All these elements identified in the research have been considered as the productivity of employees can be measured by observing a variety of different ways of stimulating engagement amongst employees. As per the annual report published by Hero MotoCorp (2020), the company is spending a substantial amount on employee engagement, hence there is a strong basis for analysing the steps taken by the company and how it is perceived by the Hero MotoCorp employees.

The lack of existing studies is still evident as the study of Sharma and Sharma (2014) has not demonstrated any direct relationship between employee engagement and employee productivity nor has it found an impact of the former on the latter. Nevertheless, the research of Abraham (2012) suggested that there is a significant effect of employee engagement on employee productivity. It has been further identified in the research that engaged employees are often inclined towards exhibiting and showing emotional job attachment on a higher level that leads to higher productivity. The research of Abraham (2012) has demonstrated the direct impact of employee engagement on employee productivity; however, the gap has been identified in terms of pertinent factors of employee engagement used in this research. For instance, the research considered job attachment as the way to lead to higher employee productivity but did not consider absorption, dedication and vigour as determinants of employee engagement leading to higher employee productivity. Moreover, the study was not able to find any study in the Indian context to undertaken study which further satisfied the need to conduct the research and in addition, utilising the two-

wheeler segment and focusing on the world's largest manufacturer of two-wheelers has given a novel touch to the study.

As per the findings of the study of Simha and Vardan (2015), employee engagement is regarded as interwoven in significant business outcomes and due to this, it essentially affects the performance of firms. In the light of this research, it has also been identified that there are certain outcomes that can be achieved through higher employee engagement such as employee retention, customer loyalty, safety and employee productivity and organisational profitability. It has further been indicated that more engaged employees can be beneficial for obtaining higher organisational growth as they tend to be more productive within firms (Simha and Vardan, 2015). However, the research has not been conducted on an empirical basis and there is a lack of information on the relationship between employee engagement and employee productivity on an empirical level. Nevertheless, this gap has also been filled by this study as it has identified the direct relationship between the two by considering empirical information, through interviews.

According to the research carried out by Kompas and Sridevi (2010) employers are largely engaged realising the importance of focusing on employee engagement and for this purpose, they have also been inclined towards creating a more effective and productive workforce. It has been further identified in the research that organisational behaviour is highly responsible for engaging employees on a higher level that can lead towards higher productivity and efficiency of the employees, further motivating them to be more committed towards the organisation. However, a lack of research has been found on how employers can ensure that organisational behaviour is based on the changing working conditions and how it can lead to higher employee productivity. Nevertheless, this gap has been filled by this research where the factor of changing workplace conditions has been combined with employee engagement to identify their impact on and relationship with employee productivity.

The research undertaken by Dalal et al. (2012) had the main purpose of investigating the degree to which the psychological wellbeing of employees is being distinguished from positive work and job attitudes such as engagement and to what degree this can lead towards variance in employee productivity. The research has identified that there is a strong association between employee productivity and employee engagement as well as a strong association between positive work and

job attitudes and employee productivity. The study of Robertson, Jansen Birch and Cooper (2012) has also supported the direct relationship between employee engagement and employee productivity by conducting regression analysis and its empirical findings have also suggested that senior managers are highly attracted towards the view of employee engagement because of its linkage with performance and the productivity of the employees working in the organisation.

In the light of the study conducted by Vance (2006), employees who are highly engaged in their jobs and are committed to their firms offer a crucial competitive advantage to companies in terms of lower employee turnover and higher productivity. The research further explained that organisations of all types and sizes have been largely investing in the practices and policies that can foster commitment and engagement in their workforces. However, Zarban (2018) has stated that for the engagement and commitment to be translated into better business results, it is highly important to achieve higher productivity of employees through better workplace conditions. Nevertheless, Andrew and Sofian (2012) have professed in their study that higher employee engagement could be regarded as the major factor that can lead towards higher organisational success and performance because it has a sufficient potential to affect the loyalty, retention and productivity of the employees, organisational reputation, customer satisfaction and stakeholder value. However, the study still lacks empirical evidence indicating a direct relationship between employee engagement and employee productivity.

As per the findings of the study conducted by Moreland (2013), workers and employees who are disengaged tend to show lower productivity as compared to those who are engaged within the organisation. The study has also opined that employees who are not engaged with their work or jobs can also undermine the productivity and success of their co-workers and also decrease both productivity and morale across an entire firm. However, Chandani et al. (2016) have argued that although hiring the right people is important from the beginning, an engaged and productive workforce is equally important for the organisation and for this, employers are responsible for keeping the employees engaged and reaping maximum productivity out of them. Nevertheless, a gap has been identified in terms of how employee engagement can be combined with a positive workplace environment to achieve the benefits of higher employee productivity.

According to Shuck, Reio Jr and Rocco (2011), employee engagement shares a significant relationship with the outcome variables of the organisation such as employee behaviour, job performance and employee productivity. The research has further identified that employee productivity is the major outcome of employee engagement and it can further allow employees to be highly committed towards organisational goals and objectives. Lee, Sheldon and Turban (2003) have stated that organisations are prone to incorporating strategies that are associated with engagement and the process of self-regulation that can further lead towards the conversion of motivation into the performance of the worker. Thus, it can be stated that employee engagement is a major element of motivated employees that can lead to them working productively and in an engaging manner.

As per the study of Chandani et al. (2016), the pressure upon the management to execute the policies of the company along with keeping the workforce engaged is gaining momentum and due to this, the engagement and retention of employees are becoming difficult tasks. However, Dalal et al. (2012) have argued that the productivity of an engaged worker is achieved through motivation for work and eventually leads to the success of the organisation. According to the study conducted by Shantz, Alfes, Truss and Soane (2013), employees that are conscious of their capacities and strengths are inclined to have an improved level of engagement which eventually leads to better productivity in the organisation. The work engagement of an employee can be reflected through involvement, efficacy, behavioural satisfaction and energy. This indicates a strong association between employee productivity and employee engagement as demonstrated by past studies (Hanaysha, 2016; Shantz et al., 2013; Osborne and Hammoud, 2017). However, the lack of empirical evidence has been found in this relationship and this gap has been filled by this research.

2.10. The Relationship Between Changing Workplace Conditions and Employee Productivity

Considering the study conducted by Ali (2013), a positive work environment is essential for employees' psychological and as well as physical welfare. However, it is important to highlight that employee working conditions are not shaped or developed by mistake as it is the strategy and policy of an organisation that how it deals with its employees and develop the desired conditions for the employees. It is notable that good quality and healthy workplace conditions mainly develop

because of the ethics that a business considers while creating its workplace culture and environment for its employees. It is notable that good and suitable working conditions are those conditions in which employees are free to communicate and can discuss their queries openly.

Furthermore, the positivity and healthiness of working conditions can also be predicted by analysing the extent to which employees are given comfort and relaxation at work. Furthermore, it is also important to highlight that good working conditions are those in which managers expect the best from their workforce, give appreciation for their work and strive to develop a working environment where employees can demonstrate and foster their skills more conveniently and openly. Furthermore, managers and employees together develop a working environment where respect and good communication are adopted. It is evident that managers and employees are responsible for building the respective environment as both of them have a shared responsibility. The employees and managers are responsible for building well balanced and respectful workplaces as businesses also wish to build an industrious workforce that can manage performance and achieve the best results and business objectives.

It was found that employee productivity is a phenomenon which has been under discussion among researchers for years. In the field of academia, the examination of employee productivity has been a debated topic among researchers and also in the business sector. There are several types of research conducted in this domain to understand and assess what factors influence employee productivity. The prior researchers have placed significant importance on assessing employee productivity in various aspects. One of the aspects of studying employee productivity is by establishing its relationship with changing workplace conditions.

It has been discussed in several prior studies that the role of the workplace environment is vitally important in employee productivity. Considering the study conducted by Ali (2013), the relationship between employee productivity and workplace conditions can be established in such a manner that when employees are given a flexible and friendly workplace environment, then they are likely to possess innovative thinking and approaches. It is a noticeable fact that when an employee focuses on an innovative approach and develops the innovative approach, then the development of new systems and business approaches take place. The importance of innovative approaches and thinking can also be justified as they help the employees to increase their

productivity and become more efficient in comparison with employees that do not focus on innovative design approaches. In this regard, it can be stated that when an organisation focuses on the development of a healthy and friendly work environment in which employees have a chance to better foster their talent and skill, then the employee productivity significantly increases as the employee develops innovative business ideas and processes that allow them to increase their efficiency and productivity. The relationship between employee productivity and working conditions can also be established in such a manner that when employees are given a protected and fair workplace, then the employee's level of satisfaction increases which eventually makes an employee more engaged towards his/her job responsibilities resulting in the increased performance and productivity of an employee. Furthermore, it is also important to highlight that when employees are provided with training and development sessions, then employees' satisfaction levels are thus also increased. This is because, when an organisation focuses on providing employee training and development, then employees perceive they are being valued by the organisation. Training and development is one major aspect of enhancing employee productivity and efficiency. This is because training and development not only enhance employee satisfaction level but training and development is also responsible for educating employees in efficient and improved business operations and activities that enhance employee productivity and performance.

The study conducted by Polek (2013) is significant in understanding the concept closely as the researcher has made an effort to assess the level of working conditions on employee productivity. The main focus of the study under consideration was to examine working conditions and how they are associated with the efficiency of employees. It has been discussed in the study that working conditions have been referred to as the one important issue for an organisation irrespective of the size, nature, and location of a business. It has been identified in the study that employee satisfaction and dissatisfaction are dependent on the workplace environment which is given to employees. It has also been discussed in several prior studies that it is important to examine workplace conditions as it drives the level of satisfaction and dissatisfaction in an employee. Therefore, it becomes important for businesses to develop a workplace environment that can satisfy employees in different ways and encourage them to better demonstrate their skills. The study of Polek (2013) is comprehensive enough as the researcher has investigated different aspects in terms of how employee productivity is influenced. Various factors have been identified and discussed that are

responsible for affecting working conditions and making conditions unfavourable and disturbed for employees. It was suggested, based on the existing studies, that employees find excessive noise, poor lighting, and mismanagement issues to be some of the most generally observed causes that make the working environment for employees' unavoidable. These are the generalised small issues that significantly affect employee productivity and performance. Furthermore, some other factors are also identified that are responsible for making workplace conditions unfavourable for highly productive employees. Furthermore, there are also some factors that not only harm the productivity of employees but these factors also affect an employee in different ways, for example, in terms of their physical and mental health. The factors such as stress, overburden, workplace accidents and other occupational diseases are some of the most common aspects that also affect an employee.

Considering the study conducted by Ali (2013), the nature of physical conditions in which employees perform their jobs is important for individual performance and overall output and the productivity of a business. It becomes necessary for the management to consider how to develop a suitable workplace environment for its employees. For instance, in most of the manufacturing and production units, the safety of an employee becomes a major issue. It is evident that employee's safety comes first while discussing working conditions within the context of the working environment of this production and manufacturing unit. It is notable that employees working in these hectic working conditions usually get injured or even the lives of an employee may be in danger when a production and manufacturing unit does not fulfil all the health and safety standards for the particular working condition. It has been observed and discussed by the researcher that when employees are exposed to hectic, unsafe and stressful working conditions, then employee productivity is affected. Similarly, it has also been discussed in the literature that when employees are provided with good and healthy working conditions, then the productivity of employees is positively influenced as those particular conditions not only assist employees to work productively and efficiently, but these working conditions are also responsible for engaging employees by improving their satisfaction levels. In this regard, it can be stated that there is an association between working conditions and employee productivity as several pieces of evidence that validate how there the relationship exists between the two variables have been identified and discussed.

2.11. Impact of Changing Workplace Conditions on Employee Productivity

An individual is influenced by some activities in their work environment and their habitat. A workplace condition can be recognised as the place in which an individual works, which refers to the environment around a person (Kelchtermans, 2006; Russell et al., 2020). The professional and social conditions under which a human is supposed to communicate with other members of the organisation is based on their interaction and behaviour (Russell et al., 2020). Similarly, the workplace environment consists of a well-designed, friendly, safe physical space, effective communication and great equipment that will enhance productivity (Chandrasekar, 2011; Russell et al., 2020). According to Parding & Berg-Jansson (2018), it has been observed that well organised and designed workplaces and office areas have a significant impact on the perspective of a person about their workplace conditions. On the basis of the existing studies that are conducted in this domain, it was determined that continuous changes in the workplace environment can lead towards either enhanced productivity or a confused mind-set among employees.

It has also been seen that a hardworking, satisfied and happy employee is considered as an essential asset of a firm. Therefore, an effective workplace condition promotes employees who are much happier and satisfied with their workplace which ultimately has an impact on the growth and development of a firm and also on economic development and growth (Khan and Salahuddin, 2018; Obeng et al., 2021). Moreover, the researcher also discovered that the factors of workplace conditions are considered to be significant factors for job satisfaction. Similarly, the level of promotion, salary, association with colleagues and climate management are significant factors which have an impact on the employee's productivity (Obeng et al., 2021). Therefore, developing greater and better workplace conditions needs awareness about the impact of the workplace on behaviour and also about how this behaviour drives employee productivity (Obeng et al., 2021).

Correspondingly, it has been identified that the new challenge of management is to develop a workplace condition which would retain, motivate and attract its employee's performance (Mariscal et al., 2018). Furthermore, the workplace condition currently is changing and diversified in terms due to changing technology and rapid globalisation. Therefore, the combination of different factors has built workplace conditions under which businesses are more in need of their workforce in contrast to the workforce need for business.

Similarly, it is assumed that it is the quality of workplace conditions which highly affects the employees' performance and their motivation level (Lai et al., 2020; Pedersen et al., 2009). In the present time, when workplace conditions are becoming more competitive, firms are no longer able to afford the loss of their potential employees. Due to this reason, several firms are taking all possible measures to create safer workplace conditions and comfort for workers. In addition, it has also been seen that workplace conditions affect the employees' engagement, morale and productivity in both a negative and positive manner (Lai et al., 2020). Flexible workplace conditions motivate employees and also enhance employees' productivity to a huge extent. According to Ajala (2012), working conditions have been seen as a significant problem in all firms irrespective of their location, size or features. Correspondingly, working conditions offer employees a feeling of satisfaction or can be the reason for fatigue, and in several conditions even result in discouragement. Meanwhile, poor workplace conditions such as poor work, loud noises and poor lighting have an adverse impact on employee performance. The productivity of employees is an essential factor for an organisation. This is because employees are considered to be one of the most essential measures in determining economic growth level and competitiveness (Hetzner, Heid and Gruber, 2015; Lai et al., 2020).

Additionally, it has also been observed that the quality of the work place condition under which the employee is operating affects the motivational level of employees and later on their productivity (Lai et al., 2020). Workplace conditions also affect the employee's emotions and desire for work, and hence they affect their productivity. Anitha (2014) also stated that appropriate workplace conditions assist in minimising the amount of turnover and employee departures which results in raising productivity in the current dynamic and competitive business environment. Moreover, the changes in workplace conditions have an effect on employee engagement, morale and productivity, in both a negative and positive manner (Sahni, 2021). Furthermore, it has also been observed that the aspects of workplace conditions play a significant role in workforce performance. According to Iqbal et al. (2015) employees will be satisfied when they sense that their workplace environment is in relation to their responsibilities.

It has also been observed that the workplace conditions under which employees are operating determines if the organisation will flourish or not (Ali, Ali, and Adan, 2013). Similarly, the workplace conditions include physical aspects which include the design and layout of offices as

well as other aspects (Sahni, 2021). Furthermore, other factors of workplace conditions are the rules which includes conditions for employees in the workplace environment. Hence it has been seen that prosperous and better workplace conditions increase the performance of employees which results in organisational growth. However, it has also been recognised that due to the rapid changes in workplace conditions, employees in a lot of firms are facing issues in their working styles (Anitha, 2014; Sahni, 2021). Similarly, disengagement of employees increases because of which it has become necessary to create workplace conditions which will positively influence the workforce. Moreover, the comfort of an employee in terms of their job is determined through the environment and conditions of the workplace which have been identified as essential factors in measuring and raising an employee's productivity.

Furthermore, the impact of these changes in workplace conditions generates ambivalent and complex results. For instance, changes in workplace conditions might lead toward enhancement in both employees' productivity as well as the quality of the product but they can also minimise the commitment and morale between the members of the workforce. Correspondingly, there is also a chance that the evaluation of the effect of workplace conditions might be wrong or incomplete if the impact is measured immediately after the changes have been made (Jain and Kaur, 2014). Therefore, scholars have suggested that, to increase the productivity of employees, it is essential to identify which changes in workplace conditions would have a positive impact on the workforce.

2.12. Impact of Employee Engagement on Employee Productivity

Instead of focusing on the level of employee engagement, most organisations focus on getting their work done in a prescribed time (Russell et al., 2020). Most organisations tend to forget that it is essential for employees to be enthusiastic about what they are doing (Obeng et al., 2021). In the light of the research study conducted by Shantz et al. (2013), one engaged employee tends to contribute more to the productivity of the organisation compared to ten disengaged employees. Employees put extra effort into what they are doing when they are satisfied with the responsibilities of their job and are expected to improve their overall performance. According to the research study conducted by Hanaysha (2016), continuous emphasis on employee engagement helps organisations to fill the gap between how employees are treated by the organisation and how

customers are expected to be treated by employees. Engaged employees provide a better experience to the customers and tend to be happier (Lai et al., 2020).

It has been found in many studies that there is a positive relationship between employee engagement and employee productivity. In the light of the research study conducted by Osborne and Hammoud (2017), the productivity of employees who are satisfied with their work is exceptional as compared to the productivity of employees who are not satisfied with their job responsibilities. If employees are motivated, they will work with more honesty and dedication which will improve their productivity. According to the study conducted by Davies and Crane (2010), engagement of employees motivates teams in order to make improvements and substantial progress while having a huge impact on the bottom line for the business. Engaged employees motivate other employees in the team through their motivation and dedication which collectively improves the performance of the team. The increased performance or productivity of the team tends to increase the overall productivity or performance of the organisation and results in higher profits for the organisation.

Organisations need to focus on the engagement level of the employee in order to improve the productivity of the employee. According to the study conducted by Simha and Vardan (2015), repetition in tasks may lead to a loss of interest and disengagement of employees. Focusing on employee engagement and designing a more challenging workflow for the employee results in a change in the approach of an employee in order to achieve workplace goals. In the light of the study conducted by Kompaso and Sridevi (2010), more innovative approaches are used by employees in order to achieve their goals. Employees using creative approaches tend to have improved productivity as compared to employees with ordinary approaches. According to the study conducted by Dalal et al. (2012), innovative approaches are used or adopted by employees who are engaged with their job responsibilities and roles. These approaches are important for the productivity of the organisation which can result in the profitability of the company.

For any business in the world, the productivity of an employee is an essential element. In the light of the research study conducted by Robertson, Jansen Birch and Cooper (2012), the business will be more successful if the employees working in it are more productive. Teams that are highly engaged tend to be more productive and have less internal theft as compared to those teams that

are now engaged. Employees that are engaged have ideas and are innovative about what they can do in a better manner. The quality of engaged employees in terms of them being more enthusiastic and collaborative about their work allows them to complete their goals in the workplace more effectively which eventually leads to increased productivity at the workplace. According to the study conducted by Rich, Lepine and Crawford (2010), employees that are engaged tend to be more collaborative and innovative as compared to employees that are less engaged with their work.

It has been indicated by most of the researchers that employee engagement is positively related to customer satisfaction. Employees that are engaged with their job responsibilities have a positive attitude towards customers and deal with customers in a manner that they must feel their importance (Sahni, 2021). Satisfied customers are more likely to increase the profit of the organisation by increasing sales. In the light of the study conducted by Parding & Berg-Jansson (2018), one of the major causes of customer satisfaction is the engagement of employees with the job or organisation. Engaged employees provide better quality services and after services to customers which creates a positive image of the organisation in the minds of the consumers. Employee engagement involves improving the environment of the workplace where all the parties from managers to employees are encouraged and allowed in order to increase their productivity every day (Sahni, 2021). More opportunities to thrive over time and to grow are provided to the companies if they have a high level of employee engagement.

In the light of the research study conducted by Polek (2013), numerous reductions in turnover are reported by organisations that have a high level of employee engagement. These reductions are the result of the increased productivity of the employees due to the increased employee engagement. Employee engagement increases the interest of the employees in the responsibilities of the job and employees try to perform the job well. The increased performance results in the increased productivity of the employees. According to the research study conducted by Ali (2013), the productivity of employees plays a significant role in the profitability of the organisation and it is increased due to several factors among which employee engagement is the crucial one. Disengaged employees are demotivated and do not add value to the organisation with respect to productivity. Greater profitability is experienced by companies that have higher employee engagement. This is because increased productivity increases the productivity of the organisation which collectively

reduces the cost of the organisation. The reduced cost of production increases the profitability of the organisation.

The extent to which employees are engaged in the organisation is decided by the organisational systems, structures, procedures and policies. The structure of the organisation is designed in a way that it helps to retain employee engagement with the job or task provided. In the light of the research study conducted by Polek (2013), a change in employee engagement results in changes in the productivity of the employee whether it be positive or negative. The increase in the engagement of employees has a positive impact on the productivity of employees. There is positive behaviour among employees on the job if they are engaged with the job which leads them to increase their productivity. However, the negative behaviour of employees with regard to the job leads to disengagement which reduces the productivity of the organisation.

Several organisations have increased their emphasis on the engagement of employees by adopting different approaches. Most of the organisations believe in rewarding employees on a continuous basis in order to enhance their engagement with the responsibilities of the job. This engagement is profitable for the organisation in terms of productivity. According to the study conducted by Meyer (2012), the productivity of each organisation is dependent on the productivity of each employee working in that particular organisation. With respect to the automobile industry, the productivity of each employee is dependent on the level of his or her engagement with the job. The productivity of each employee matters in the automobile industry and has a huge impact on the profitability of the organisation. Employees working on the same wage rate and spending the same amount of time on the job while using the same amount of resources can either increase the productivity which will be profitable for the organisation or decrease the productivity which can increase the cost of production.

Various studies have emphasised the need to increase employee engagement in order to increase the productivity of employees. In the light of the research conducted by Nielsen (2012), the attitude of the employee towards the job determines the engagement of the employee towards the job which, however, increases or decreases the productivity of the individual. Increased productivity due to a higher level of employee engagement reduces the rate of employee turnover. The company retains the employees that are more productive and can reduce the cost of hiring new employees.

The hiring of new employees requires necessary training for the job which requires money and time. Organisations should focus on increasing employee engagement with the job in order to reduce the costs involved in the production. The productivity of an employee is essential for any organisation because the performance of the organisation is dependent on each of its employees.

In the light of the research study conducted by Iqbal (2010), employees that are engaged more with the job tend to have better results as compared to employees that have a low level of engagement. Employees that are less engaged are a burden for an organisation and the organisation should focus on generating their interest in the job in order to improve the productivity of the organisation. According to the study conducted by Koskinen (2015), organisations must take measures to increase employee engagement in the organisation in order to improve the productivity of employees. This increased productivity of each employee will result in an overall increase in the productivity of the organisation.

2.13. Theoretical Framework

After an in-depth review of 44 published research works, on employee engagement, changing workplaces, and their relationship with and impact on employee productivity, this section focuses on the theoretical framework. A theoretical framework is an assembly of linked concepts, like a theory but may not be well planned. A theoretical framework guides the research, and direction by regulating what components the study will measure, and what relationships the study intends to focus on.

2.14.1 The Zinger Model of Engagement

Shalini and Nasima (2018), in their research “The Antecedents of Employee Engagement in an Automobile Industry”, have advocated the use of components put forth by David Zinger in analysing employee engagement in the automobile sector. The study has given several valuable inputs on increasing employee productivity, by analysing the selected variables. The literature review of 44 research articles and the study by Shalini and Nasima (2018) justify the assertion that the Zinger model of engagement is an appropriate theoretical model to analyse the impact of employee engagement on employee productivity in Hero MotoCorp, which is the world’s largest manufacturer of two-wheelers.

The Zinger model of engagement was proposed by David Zinger and is based on 10 drivers that management should follow to ensure that employees are engaged and performing productively to achieve the aims of the company (Chouddhury and Mohanty, 2018). Crafting a strategy of how the organisation will achieve its goals, the connection of the various processes is also important to ensure that the performance of the employees is excellent. The process starts with crafting a strategy to achieve the results. This will be beneficial for the personal growth of the employee besides being beneficial to the community. Hence, this model is an effective model to achieve employee engagement within the organisation.

The main purpose of the Zinger model of employee engagement is to achieve a higher level of employee engagement in an organisation. By well-crafted strategies, the managers need to work on employees and on themselves. In the light of the research study conducted by Chowdhury (2014), the Zinger model of employee engagement benefits the organisation with a system of rewarding and recognising employees, so they remain motivated to perform much better in an organisation. The focus of this model is on increasing employee productivity in an organisation through increasing the level of employee engagement (David Zinger, 2019).

1. Achieving Results

The signage utilised for achieving results aims to ensure where we are targeting our engagement intentions. Achieving results is critical for the company, team, administrator, and worker. Engagement must be in line with a specific end, or it will fall short of focus, effectiveness, and sustainability. Engagement will be anticipated that lacks in attributing to strategic objectives fades away because of a drop in effectiveness or energy. The meaning of a result is an aftereffect, or reaction to something. Something that is being considered in this framework is engagement in work that leads to results. Also, in the coordinated view, integrating engagement with a task, employees will add to the development of a goal and outcome for the company. To establish whether the company's results are clear to its workers, a company should ask employees to elaborate on the results the company is aiming to accomplish. From the response of the employee, a company can ascertain whether the set objective is clear or not and whether employees are able to state these results without doubt or confusion. If not, company should make sure it communicates results which are crystal clear. Peter Drucker, in his book, *Managing for Results*, is one of the most influential thinkers on management focused largely on results (Drucker, 2011). He

ascertains that results are the outcome of leveraging opportunities instead of focusing on obstacles. Resources must be directed towards opportunities and to achieve economic results, we must concentrate. The manager must make sure that the resources of engagement are aimed at results and not at futile activities. When it is pertinent that a company is working to achieve desired results, the company can work backwards from the results to establish the clear-cut tasks required to fully engage with accomplishing those results. The company should create an environment for employees to give inputs into the designing of results. Ideally, a company should work on the concept of whether employees can play a key role in influencing results through engagement.

For a company like Hero MotoCorp, results are the cornerstone, in order to maintain their position as largest manufacturer of two-wheelers in the world. With a changing landscape, the company needs to adopt itself and at the same time, achieve results. Hence the inclusion of this component becomes important in analysing the impact of employee engagement on employee productivity.

2. Maximising Performance

As per the report published by Aon Hewitt's, "Trends in Global Employee Engagement", the biggest reduction in engagement is employees' anticipation of how an organisation is regulating performance (Kincentric, 2020). Employees around the globe believe that their company has not given the desired direction or level of management that leads to growth in profitability, neither has the company linked individual employee's performance to the company's target. In the "Human Resource Management Review" Jamie Gruman and Alan Saks have published an astute article on performance management and employee engagement (Gruman & Saks, 2011). As per the article, less than a third of workers perceive that their organisational performance management process helps them in developing performance. The book *Magnetic Employee Engagement* by Kevin Sheridan concluded that only 5% of performance appraisals and performance management communication ever discuss engagement (Zinger, 2019).

Engaged performance management must establish and adapt to the malleable, vigorous, uncertain, dynamic, and stressful components of performance. Moreover, making the situation more complex is an increase in the number of mobile workers, now more than a billion globally. A company's objective should be improvising on employees' performance rather than leading them to an

unstructured path of performance appraisals that burns out the efficiency of employees and respective managers.

Hero MotoCorp pays special attention to maximising performance, by employing a unique appraisal system, aimed at enhancing productivity, attaining global standards, creating motivation, and career growth. These elements are aimed at maximising the performance of employees and in turn, maximising the performance of Hero MotoCorp.

3. Path Progress

If one were to analyse the path of progress from the view of the classic board game snakes and ladders, then a ladder can be considered as progress whereas impediments are the snakes. It is essential to consider that the effects of impediments on emotional status are heavy compared to the effects of progress. Minor setbacks can eradicate minor accomplishments and negative behaviour by a manager can impact on the positive attitude of employees. As a company ascends over the pyramid of engagement, a company must shield itself against impediments more than engaging with development. Path progress is in the second row of the framework to demonstrate the relevance of this building block for a company to improve employee engagement. It works in coordination to increase performance and improve results. The framework has discussed seven steps to assist path progress for fruitful employee engagement:

Emphasising the positive, repetitive work in the direction of minor accomplishments and breakthroughs; maintaining how employees are putting effort into sensible goals, linked with sufficient freedom to achieve success. Managers should provide resources, assistance, and time necessary to move towards the ladder of progress. Managers should also cherish and cultivate strong interpersonal links focusing on progress. Disposing the negative. Negative actions have an excessive impact on engagement. Because negative actions have a more forceful impact than positive actions, hence it is paramount to avert obstacles before they take place or reduce the impact of an obstacle. A company should build a robust system where the manager works on a construct to mitigate problems, in a scenario where a setback is about to take place and if it occurs, establishes how to respond to the situation to minimise the impact on the path to progress. It has been observed that employees often hack their work to trump barriers and obstacles in progress, hence a company should not ignore these methods and work towards improvising the system where

an employee is not forced to hack their work to achieve progress. Hacking work and workarounds are two potent methods to accomplish progress and reduce setbacks. Bill Jensen and Josh Klein in their book *Hacking Work* speak about how employees often hack work and utilise methods of workarounds to accomplish progress (Jensen & Klein, 2014). Hacking work is the phenomenon where an employee exploits the loopholes in the system to get the job done and workarounds lead to effortless work to perform better. It has been observed that not only the managers but also employees at times can exercise control of outperform, leading to the creation of forceful benevolent workarounds or hacks to complete the job at hand and increase their own engagement. The question is, are employees committed, willing and ready to engage? Trying to engage employees without enabling them is a recipe for frustration. As per the research, around 20% of employees in a company may be frustrated due to lack of complete engagement. In the book *The Enemy of Engagement* by Mark Royal and Tom Agnew, the authors offer a conceptual framework to mitigate frustration among employees (Agnew & Royal, 2011). The authors discovered that 30% of employees lack clarity pertaining to goals set by company and feel an absence of authority in terms of performing their duty and around 50% of employees are perturbed with staffing related issues and do not intend to undergo training. They assume that training does not add to their quality of work and feel it is low-quality training and a waste of time and think there are structural issues with the company. The authors laid down several ways to reduce frustration among employees by enabling methods such as setting training as a preference, linking and common sharing of a platform for resources, and not allowing an employee to fall into the trap of routine. A company often implements principles and practices from games to transmit practices of gaming for daily tasks. Games, by nature, have an appeal factor due to sense of engaging that is often developed to give a sense of achievement as we progress with the game. Virtual games are designed to make sure that a new player starts engaging by experiencing progress right from the start. Hence, a company should focus on the factor of how much a new employee is experiencing progress. Is he getting confused with the systemic procedures and losing intent to progress? Here games can play a major role in nudging the employee towards progress; this can be done by instilling a sense of progress in the mind of the employee. Gaming is also a medium to instil a strong sense of teamwork and collaborative working; these are executed by multiple player gaming where players work in coordination to win over other teams. The aim of management is to transfer this collaboration into the work portfolio to work towards the path of progress.

It has been observed that the majority of the workforce shy away from taking on new tasks or feel repulsive by the load of work because at times, employees tend to fear the consequence of falling behind on deadlines. Hence, in today's scenario, in workplace small has gained a lot of significance. Today, management is looking to achieve more with less by ensuring proper procedures. Management should ensure that these small actions are task oriented and specific in nature, thereby maximising results, leading along the path to progress. Every step of progress should be dealt with a celebration, the way a gamer gets gratification for achieving a target; management should ensure a system of celebration to keep its employees enthusiastic on the journey of progress. There are different ways to celebrate an achievement; examples are: recognition, appraisal, promotion or even liberty to choose shifts and locations. The aim of the efforts discussed is to pave the way for progression.

It would be worth analysing the factor of "hacking", in Hero MotoCorp, through primary data, since there is no evidence available to suggest that employees at Hero MotoCorp utilise hacking to enhance their performance. Hero MotoCorp is the world's largest manufacturer of two-wheelers, hence analysing the factor of clarity among its employees will throw light on how clarity is perceived in Hero MotoCorp which is an important factor on the path to progress.

4. Building Relationships

As observed in the path to progress, gaming was utilised to collaborate and work in a team. Similarly, relationships are paramount for employee engagement and often referred to as the foundation of employee engagement. "Building Effective One-on-One Relationships" is an article published by Linda Hill in *Harvard Review* which quotes research by John Kotter that implicates the strong connection of relationships distinguishing general managers from effective managers with an outstanding performance record (Hill, 1996). These effective managers treat work as a relationship and understand the need to engage employees to achieve the desired outcome. Management should often take feedback from their employees to understand their state of mind and improvise on relationship building; for instance, managers can pose questions to their staff to answer themselves and nudge them towards relationship building. A self-evaluating feedback form may throw light on the status of practiced relationships in the company. Example questions could include: do I have a best friend at, when did I receive my last recognition, is my supervisor a cooperative, person who encourages me to develop and are managers pushing me to perform?

Management should not encircle employees with terms such as asset or liability because people are people. Though on a company's record you can describe people as an asset or human capital, in engagement and relationships, they crave proximity. After all, employees are nothing but humans and companies tend to dehumanise them referring to them as assets or liabilities, and a manager who is also an employee should be the first to understand this concept. In management, one of the classic definitions states that the company should get work done through people whereas in engagement the company tends to get work done with people. It shows a clear difference in the perception of how management views employees. Also, another point to remember is the fact that a company will never have a relationship with an asset but will have relationships with humans. An employee view of engagement is from the point of the company's task whereas managers' view engagement from the point of working relationships with employees. A successful relationship depends on connection and coordination between two individuals and in any given relationship, there should be interdependence between two parties who thus influence each other. This interdependence tends to shape the relationship equation between the two parties, with them impacting and influencing one another at different levels of engagement. For example, a manager exercising strong backbone on his team will have an impact on all the employees. The concept of backbone consists of bids, authenticity, caring and knowledge (BACK). Engagement, a very human element of our natures is often overlooked due to a limited view of soft skills. Soft skills are usually interpreted as mushy and irrelevant in comparison to hard skills which are considered to be the foundation of management. The concept of backbone refers to it being the cornerstone and cohesion for the body and it is the main part of the network that connects the network. This concept gives building blocks to relationship formation between managers and employees.

B stands for Bids. In the book *The Relationship Cure*, author John Gottman states that a very strong practice to develop improved relationships in all aspects of our lives includes formal work (Gottman, & DeClaire, 2002). The author evaluated minor changes between employees that coordinated and communicated a desire for connection leading to one of three outcomes. A bid is a principal parameter of emotional communication. This can be in the form of a question, an action, a look, a style, or any expression that denotes that an employee has an intention to connect. The outcome of a bid can either be positive or negative for the other individuals' bids to establish emotional connection. A positive outcome can be interpreted as an acceptance of the bid to

establish emotional connection whereas a negative outcome can be interpreted as a rejection of the bid to establish emotional connection. Mastering the process of bids assists in relationship building through this mechanism. Managers can establish relationships with their employees and improvise performance to achieve a management target.

A stands for authenticity. The term authenticity is the quality of being real or genuine, an act that is true to someone's self. Authenticity is the cornerstone of trust, faith, hope, respect, dignity, and a genuine relationship. a manager practising authenticity at a workplace displays integrity and honesty, with a profound sense of determination and intention to work due to their core principles. *True North: Discover Your Authentic Leadership* is a book authored by Bill George, which states that authentic managers have a genuine interest in serving the company and their employees through management principles (Bill, 2007). These managers are interested in decentralising and empowering the employees they manage to make a distinction, more than they are interested in recognition, money, power, or reputation for themselves. They navigate according to their heart, soul, and mind, exercising heart-based navigation impeded in passion, affection and compassion, as well as courteous management. Employees, in turn, tend to follow an authentic manager because they have the quality of being consistent, dependable, courteous, decisive, reliable, and capable of executing responsibilities for the company. It has been observed that authentic managers tend to differ from other managers; for example, in a scenario where authentic managers are pushed beyond their value system, they tend to resist and remain uncompromised. If the company wants to foster engagement, a company should create a system for nurturing authentic managers.

C stands for Caring. Everything becomes trivial and insignificant, if the quality of caring is missing from the horizon, hence a company dealing with humans should keep "Caring" at the centre of its management practice. In caring, you tend to value employees who report to you and to look after their needs and wants over your own. Caring is not a frivolous emotion but rather a powerful attitude and practiced behaviour displayed by managers. Caring also comprises "care-frontation", where others are held liable for their conduct and are not afraid to communicate in relation to inappropriate behaviour or deviation in performance.

K stands for knowledge. Interpersonal knowledge is very important in maintaining and building relationships. a company should create a system of knowledge generation; this can be done

through effective training of employees and managers. A learning environment is a building block towards knowledge generation; this parameter also assists in improvising on performance by bringing on board new knowledge. Knowledge is essential to develop relationships via creating connections and coordination among employees and building cordial manager-employee relationships. Knowledge assists in communication and creating conversations in a workplace; it assists in engaging with another party. Such conversation often leads to knowing each other and strong relationships are based on the principle of knowing each other. Engagement at work can be developed by dwelling on the principle of knowledge where each employee is unique and has its own knowledge pool; communicating with others creates a bridge towards enhanced relationships and improvising on engagement in the workplace.

Hero MotoCorp is an Indian company; it will be interesting to fathom how the concept of relationship building is dealt with by the company. Also, how well does the concept of bids, authenticity, caring and knowledge (BACK) fit into the scheme of things at Hero MotoCorp? The theory discussed above on relationship building will act as a guiding tool in analysing the results.

5. Fostering Recognition

Recognition means acknowledging, accepting and validating something; if the word recognition was split into two parts as re-cognition it means to think again. Hence, a company need to dwell on what recognition stands for in the workplace. Recognition can be built into a strategic pillar to assist in accomplishing results and developing the company. Recognition can be given a personal touch that is to recognise an employee who is struggling to complete the task and having difficulty in following procedures. In the current scenario, recognition can be a social media tool by recognising employees on social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn. The authors of *Missing Pieces*, Brun and Cooper have acknowledged that the main challenge for current organisations is to boost the time spent by managers on their team members, which is far less, since managers are involved in their workplace duties (Brun & Cooper, 2009). Hence, the need for recognition is important not only on certain occasions but also daily.

The Corporate Leadership Council published a study by Gallup, emphasising that recognition relates to increased employee engagement (Weintraub, 2009). Another, done by AON Hewitt research, indicated that the current position of employee engagement across the globe is around

56%, which suggests a disparity in workforce to company's success or failure (Kincentric, 2020). The greatest drop is observed in the way employees discern performance management by a company. Employees are demanding recognition for the work executed and want improved communication about their company's vision and better coordination in terms of how individuals can add to the success of the organisation. A company should focus on both intent and the influence of recognition. Several gifts such as gift cards and home appliances can be useful when the intention is to express care made visible, not as a mandatory task of a manager. It is necessary to analyse the impact of recognition, for instance how is the given recognition perceived by the employees, has it made any difference to the work, or is it perceived as managerial lip service? Hence, recognition needs to be genuine and fair and should be perceived a real by employees otherwise the entire purpose is defeated. Gary Chapman and Paul White have published numerous articles on appreciation in the workplace and have focused on the five-pillar approach: physical touch, acts of service, quality time, words of affirmation and tangible gifts (Chapman & White, 2012). Roy Saunderson has strongly defended the argument for "real recognition"; he has served in the Recognition Management Institute (Saunderson, 1997). A workplace without recognition has a vacuum in terms of the human element because we are humans and not machines who only work. If a company recognises and appreciates the efforts of employees, it is very important that the company should communicate this to their employees. There is a major difference between tokenism in recognition and authentic recognition and employees are often smart enough to notice this sooner or later and it has a negative impact on employees once they figure out that given recognition was tokenism. Hence, recognition is more than an annual celebration or accidental gift cards for good performance. Recognition is a strategic tool that is very powerful due to its psychological impact on employees due to the influence on social life. Recognition is a process of re-evaluation of engagement in our daily work life and it is a powerful force multiplier giving impetus to motivation and engagement among workers. A company should conduct routine feedback sessions with its employees and should ideally provide an environment where employees are willing to discuss issues without any fear. A company can introduce several methods whereby the identity of the employee is not known; for example, this is important in cases of adverse feedback to protect the respective employee from being targeted. A company should recognise that disengagement is not an offence, but rather matter of choice to start a conversation. The most

successful companies understand the art of recognition and discern that more gratitude leads to better engagement and improved performance.

Employee recognition is often referred to as social recognition. It is an act of acknowledgment on a public platform about who your employees are and what they stand for. The concept of employee recognition assists employees in identifying and recognising each other, resulting in a more inclusive environment at the workplace. Employee recognition is one of the most important pillars in driving engagement at the workplace, in terms of performance, and employee retention. The symbol utilised for depicting “Fostering recognition” in the employee engagement pyramid relates to the Eye of Horus, resembling the Egyptian symbol connected with strength, better health, and force. Recognition can foster a company and contribute to the betterment of the employees. Hence a company must use recognition as a tool for engagement and fully utilise its potential. A company should come out of management silos and accept, appreciate, and recognise the employees that work for them. Recognition stands at the core of the pyramid of employee engagement; it is at the heart of engagement at work. A company should assist employees in recognising: a) what employees need to engage with to accomplish essential outcomes; b) clear communication on progression and deficiency and gaps where they are falling short; c) methods through which employees can minimise failure and move towards improvement; d) making employees realise that the company cares for them and values their relationship with them.

Hero MotoCorp follows a format of reward directly linked to employees’ efforts, performance, dedication, and achievement of the company’s target (Hero MotoCorp, 2020). Hero MotoCorp, on its company profile, has specified that the company recognises the effort and commitment of its employees and this recognition is often given in the form of higher remuneration, promotion, bonuses, and career progression programmes. The study in hand will give deep insights into recognition parameters for Hero MotoCorp, how employees perceive them, and whether they are looking for any improvement in the existing system.

6. Mastering Moments

Engagement rests in the moment. Employees must learn the art of mastering moments from quality networks to forceful touch points. It is all about balance, when challenges and skills are balanced, it leads to a zone that flows and dwells in the moment. Moreover, focusing on a task within the

moment mitigates work stress. There are primarily six methods to engage the moment: 1. Accessing opportunities for engagement; 2. Working on details, and try to be a micro-manager; 3. Reaching out to people; 4. Transforming your interaction into high quality interaction to power up the company; 5. Nesting in the moment to mitigate stress; 6. Converging into the challenge and skill to trace flow, as the Nobel laureate author of *Thinking Fast and Slow*, states that we experience around 20K individual moments in a single day (Kahneman & Egan, 2011). These moments exist for a few seconds and each moment gives an opportunity to engage. Within a moment, an employee can blend with the work involved in and full engagement. Approximately at 1% completion, one can experience 200 forceful engagement moments daily; hence, it is advisable to follow a path that converts opportunities into moments. Mostly, micromanagers are not perceived to be praiseworthy managers by their employees, and there are several reasons which make an employee uncomfortable working with micromanagers. Micromanagers often tend to display excessive supervision over their employees. These managers keep an eye on each task very closely, irritating employees because it gives them a sense of policing. In contrast, imagine if employee regulated their moments and paid attention to moments of interaction; they could improve substantially because micro moments have a capacity to make a huge difference. To make engagement an effective tool, one needs to focus on the term ‘engage’ and try to be committed to engaging in the moment, thereby giving exceptional results. Instead of engaging in the energy draining process of micromanagement based on regulation and dominance of frivolous details, managers should focus on micro moments by appreciating connections, feedback, co-creation, authenticity, and interaction. To better understand, management of interruption in the moments, one can take cue from former CEO Douglas Conant of “Campbell chicken soup”. Douglas Conant utilised the concept of “Touch points” to bring improve the dismal score on engagement by Gallup, a firm that assists companies and CEOs in ironing out most their pressing management problems (Horovitz, 2009). Douglas Conant perceived that to work on the moment of interruption is the actual work of management. Every day when we make different connections due to interactions, we have the potential to reach a high and low point in another person’s life. The primary reason behind getting in touch is that every touch point has the liberty to gain high performance intention, to imbibe the purpose with high clarity and enhance energy, and to leave an imprint on the course of events. As per Gallup, “Touch points” can take place at a given time interval between two or more parties or individuals, when they intend to get together to debate an issue and get it sorted.

Hence interruption interactions are not interferences but, on the contrary, the actual work of management. In the case of moment of engagement, any action rests in the interaction. Jane E. Dutton, Professor of Business Administration and Psychology and cofounder of the Center for Positive Organisations at the University of Michigan's Ross School of Business, suggests that there is immense strength in connections and interaction, and one must be cautious against connection working on the principle of corrosion that damages motivation, promise, loyalty and engagement. On the contrary, one must augment superior-quality connections asserted by collective trust, positive regard, and proactive engagement on either side (Dutton et al., 2014). The main pillar of superior-quality connections is “respect”, in an engagement characterised by affirming to others and communicating in a way that demonstrates regard and values another person’s worth. It has been observed that even a minor act of respectful engagement animates energy in each relationship. A continuous flow of superior-quality interaction by employees within a company may be the single most forceful way to reenergise and add to a company’s efficiency to achieve results. It takes a certain amount of energy to commence a superior-quality interaction; however, it can be fathomed that there is an exchange of energy throughout the process of interaction.

Alan Watts, a British author, and orator known for elucidating and publicising different religions in Western society, stated if one think where he is going is important than when on arrival to that place it makes one feel worthless. Stephan Rechtschaffen, M.D. is the president and co-founder of the Omega Institute in Rhinebeck in New York, and he said in his book *Time Shifting* that there is no stress in the present moment, and it is important we start living in the present moment (Rechtschaffen, 2002). He says that we think we do not have enough time to perform because we spend our time either thinking forwards or backwards, without focusing on living in the present moment. The paradigm of “Time Shifting” works on the logic that every moment is imbued with rhythm and every individual has a capability to bolster or shrink an individual moment. The way Stephan Rechtschaffen looks at time is, if one intends to change what is happening in his world is not trying to put efforts to do more rather emerging deeper into the moment. “Time Shifting” is nothing but one’s capability to switch gears, to shift the rhythm as discussed earlier to cut across that moment and be present in the moment.

As per Stephan Rechtschaffen, we tend to waste a great portion of time by thinking about the task we just completed and the task we will be undertaking, instead of concentrating on the task we are

involved in, hence much of our stress comes from regret and phobia. Stephan Rechtschaffen has suggested numerous tips to enhance moments at work: 1) one must arrive early at the meeting to settle down with the feeling of nervousness and feel composed; 2) if your phone rings, make it a point to allow it to ring again, to attain the state of getting centred that is a zone of emotional balance; 3) attain a state of mindfulness by performing one task at a time and immersing yourself into that task and not thinking about any other task; 4) take a break after the completion of each task; 5) when you are standing for an elevator, think about the task you are involved in rather than coming under stress from past and future tasks. Work in the moment by performing on work that stabilises challenge. Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi a Hungarian-American psychologist noted for his work in the study of happiness and creativity. In his book *Flow*, he offers a timeless landscape and suggestions on how we can access a state of combining fully with work (Csikszentmihalyi, 2008). Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi suggests that we sense more “Flow” at work than our recreation time and advises that we generally discount the importance of the experience that engagement gives us at work. This principle of “Flow” is studied very thoughtfully by game developers to make sure that players playing the game are experiencing the flow. We need to immerse ourselves in the same way at work. Some of the main components that enhance flow at work are: 1) clear goals: there should be clarity in expectation and rules are understandable and goals are realistic and align with an employee’s skill set and capability to achieve; 2) concentration: one should practise an immense degree of concentration on a defined field of attention; 3) lack of self-consciousness: we should intend to move towards merging action and awareness; 4) timelessness: subjective experience must change in character or composition; 5) clear feedback: it is necessary to provide clear and concise feedback, to improvise on one’s performance; 5) balance of ability and challenge: any given task is neither too easy nor too demanding; 6) personal control: it is necessary to exercise a sense of personal control over the situation; 7) intrinsic rewards: to create a sense of intrinsic reward to feel the effortlessness of the action taken to complete the task; 8) absorption: one must practise the art of absorption to the fullest in any given activity through focus and awareness.

It will be valuable to analyse what employees of Hero MotoCorp think about “Mastering Moments” and whether time shifts impact their working. Inputs from this parameter will give deep insights and add to the understanding to help develop a holistic programme for employee engagement to enhance productivity.

7. Leveraging Strengths

Engagement is a powerful element. A person knowing his or her strength should practice those areas of strength and leverage those strengths in the utility of others; this will culminate in enhanced engagement, wellbeing, and happiness. If you intend to discover and bring those strengths to the surface for others, you should first analyse and understand your areas of strength. Analytical and smart managers can discover these areas of strength among their employees and add fuel to these areas by added training and feedback. Peter Ferdinand Drucker, an Austrian management consultant and author of numerous books on management, has contributed immensely to the philosophical and practical basis of modern management, and has given five paths to strengthen engagement at work. Peter Ferdinand Drucker, in 1991, in an article on managing careers stated that, we need to put ourselves where one can make the highest possible contribution to the community and company (Drucker, 2001). Hence one should stay alert in one's work life, which suggests a need to understand how and when to transform the work we perform, portraying the importance of staying in tune with mental alertness, at work. It has generally been observed that people achieve exceptional results in performing task which they are good at when working in a format which best suits their capability. However, Peter Ferdinand Drucker believes that on the ground, there is a very small portion of the population that is aware of their fundamental strengths and weaknesses (Drucker & Maciariello 2009). Peter Ferdinand Drucker states that one must hold conversations with others at work to discover their areas of strengths. One needs to ask: 1) What are my areas of strengths? 2) How am I performing in the workplace? 3) Where do I belong? 4) What is the expected contribution from me? 5) What are my values? One of most valuable tips that Peter Ferdinand Drucker gives is to accept yourself the way you are, not to try to change yourself. One must focus on improvising and developing skills which one possesses and undertaking tasks that are tailored to the individual's way of acting and performing. If this philosophy is followed at work, one can transform from an ordinary employee into an extraordinary employee in the workplace, hence successful careers are not planned but executed. Successful careers take-off when people intend to formulate to gain an opportunity because these people have asked relevant questions of themselves which are listed above and have evaluated their unique capability and characteristics. One must follow Martin Seligman's powerful path in line with happiness and well-being. Martin Elias Pete Seligman is a psychologist and is a strong advocate within the scientific fraternity of his theories of positive psychology. Martin Elias Pete

Seligman has been an active contributor to bringing psychology in line with a balance of the positive and the negative. *Learned Optimism* a book by Martin Elias Pete Seligman explains how to overcome an “I give up” attitude, establish an enhanced constructive explanatory style for understanding behaviour, and feel the advantageous of an improvised positive interior dialogue (Seligman, 2002). Martin Elias Pete Seligman has developed the VIA (Value In Action) Strength Survey of parameters of Strengths – calculating 24 parameters of strengths. This survey has a global viewpoint, it can be utilised both internally and externally at the workplace and it is available at no charge. Research has shown that individuals know their top five strengths because they utilise them on a daily basis and leverage them to serve others that, in turn, results in an enhanced level of happiness and well-being. Gallup, American analytics, and an advisory company have been spearheading helping people and companies deliver strengths at work. One of the questions in Gallup’s well-known survey of employee engagement focuses on the opportunity to do what one can do best in each day. This question aims at enhancing strength and Gallup discovered that if a manager overlooks an employee’s performance than it results in a 44% chance that the employee will be disengaged. In contrast, if the manager only focuses and communicates about gaps, this can result in a 22% chance of an employee being disengaged (Kincentric, 2020). However, if a manager focuses on performance and communicates about strengths based perceptive, there is only a 1% chance of the employee being disengaged.

Marcus Wilfrid Buckingham, an English author, motivational speaker and business consultant, and Tom Rath, an American consultant on employee engagement, strengths, and wellbeing, have published several books and material based on strength at the workplace (Clifton & Buckingham, 2001). Their main strength-based evaluation is called as StrengthsFinder 2.0. Anyone can take this assessment after buying one of the author’s book linked with strength at the workplace and by punching in the StrengthFinder password for the website. Gallup has also done exceptional work in creating useful instructions and resources to master more about someone’s strength and how to utilise these strengths at work. StrengthsFinder 2.0 is just one of the tools of many tools available to trace strength at work, offered by both the authors and Gallup. Marcus Wilfrid Buckingham has consulted Gallup and is currently practising as an independent strength-based coach, presenter, and writer. Buckingham has recently presented another strength-based tool, developed to assist an individual to give an edge and accomplish goals at work. His assessment is considered quite useful;

however, his actual contribution is listed in his book *Go Put Your Strengths to Work*. Buckingham has worked on a video series *Trombone Player Wanted* on strengths, where the first series works on “So, What's Stopping You?”. Buckingham is one of those who has advocated for tracing strengths not in a judgement or assessment but by paying close attention to what one is expected to work on in an upcoming task, what will be engaging in the upcoming task and what will give the greatest sense of satisfaction.

Especially, we have glanced at what engaged us to decide our strengths and then we increase these activities and aspects to intensify our engagement, and it can be ascertain that there is no need to test. Buckingham’s video series *Trombone Player Wanted* is rather a source of inspiration, assisting in building strengths in the team by analysing the video together with the team. *Trombone Player Wanted* focuses on enhancement of personality; as we grow our personality transforms, and one tends to transform especially in the area of weakness, and a smart team member will also be available to assist his team.

Positive Organisational Scholarship (a sub field of Management and Organisations), a world-class centre at Ross School of Business in the University of Michigan, has put forth the “Reflected Best Self Exercise” to utilise stories gathered from individuals in all walks of life to assist us to fathom and self-reflect about our strengths and weaknesses, where we stand and how we can best contribute. These stories gathered from individuals who know us can assist in strengthening and connecting with others, assist us in experiencing with clarity about who an individual is when he is at his best, and improve personal development targets so that we can be at our peak more often. A major strength of this path is the societal component and in contrast to the anonymous feedback of a comprehensive evaluation it paves the way for more discussion and explanation from individuals who can tell us what one is when he is at his best. The majority of us have grey areas or blind spots about our strengths and the Reflected Best Self Exercise can assist us in replenishing those gaps. Below are listed the six approaches for becoming strong at work: 1) make sure one goes above taking a test and quoting you have done the strength test; 2) do not curtail the essence of strengths to a tally of five attributes; 3) be aware of what really engages you and feasible to work reverse from engagement to strengths; 4) pay attention to the strengths of other people and give them strength-based feedback; 5) establish a regular routine or reminders so that an individual

does not lose strength in the bombardment of demands and tasks; 6) practise discipline about your strengths and convert strength aligned work into your foundation base at the workplace.

This parameter is focused on self-reflection and evaluation. Analysing this parameter will assist in understanding whether the largest manufacturer of two-wheelers, Hero MotoCorp, provides the desired system for employees to self-reflect so they can leverage on their strengths. If there are any systems in place, do they assist employees, and do employees perceive these systems as an asset or liability?

8. Making Meaning

For work to augment and enrich individuals, it must be sensible and meaningful. Individuals those who ask question “why”, to work tend to infuse sense of powerful intrinsic motivation. Progress, when it is sensible, worthy and meaningful, can be one of the excellent episodes of the day. Paul Fairlie, founder and CEO of Heliosophy, a management consultancy working towards positive work science, recently published a column on meaningful work, under the “Positive Work Inventory” and engagement in advances under the “Positive Person Inventory” (Galli, 2019). The column listed general aspects of meaning: having a reason or target, existing as per one’s values, principles and goals, competency, autonomy, challenge, commitment, engagement, growth, control, fulfilment, and achievement. Paul Fairlie undertook an exploration of meaningful work with around 574 respondents (Fairlie, 2011). He drew several conclusions from his research for human resource development practices: inner discussion and social interaction, unstable mindsets, and an education management based on a framework of human meaning. He implicated that meaningful work was an exclusive predictor of engagement, “elements of meaningful work are neglected area of individual motivation and engagement in a given company”. Below is the list of eight approaches to build meaningful work: 1) defeat how with why; 2) develop ample leadership whys; 3) bridge meaning, squeeze money; 4) imbibe with purpose, desire, mastery, aspiration, autonomy; 5) master your charm; 6) rework your principles and values as affirmations; 7) lead on reason; 8) double your “Work as Meaning Inventory” (WAMI) at work. Viktor Frankl, an Austrian neurologist, psychiatrist, and Holocaust survivor implicated that the meaning of life is discovered in each moment of life and that life never terminates to have a meaning. To apply his concept to the workplace, if one has a “why” to work, the individual can endure almost any “how”. Not each one of us is engaged in a meaningful activity, however each one can, if intend to do so. A company,

managers, and workers must master how to co-develop meaningful workplaces. Section of accomplishing this happen is assisting employees to discern and experience the superlative purpose in the workplace. In the workplace, meaning is co-developed between company and employee.

It is not a gift or a prize that is given to a person, rather meaning it something that needs to be developed through authentic interaction about the why of work. David Olson Ulrich, a university professor, author, and management consultant, Marshall Goldsmith an executive leadership coach, and Wendy Ulrich, a psychologist and founder of the Sixteen Stones Center for Growth in Alpine, co-authored *The Why of Work: How Great Leaders Build Abundant Organisations That Win*. The authors manoeuvre the book around down-to-earth, sensible, rational, and meaningful questions on character, identity, reason, motivation, work culture, purpose, contribution, teams, resilience, growth, happiness, and courtesy (Younger, Ulrich, & Brockbank 2012). The author nudges the reader to ask; 1) What am I as a person known for? 2) Where am I heading? 3) Whom should I take my journey with? 4) How should I develop a positive work atmosphere? 5) What are the challenges that interest me? 6) How do I respond to change? 7) What gratifies me? The “why” of work is a pragmatic handbook for managers who are intending to infuse meaning. As the authors elaborate in their preface: managers and leaders are meaning builders: they show direction to their employees that others thrive to; they assist others to engage in doing good work; they publish the ideas and put effort into practices that carve how an employee thinks, acts and feels. As company increasing becomes an identity and purpose for individual’s sense, managers optimise in assisting employees carve the meaning of their lives. Money does matter and also meaning does, to instil motivation, competition and caring at work. Dan Ariely, an Israeli-American professor in Duke university of psychology and behavioural economics, put forth insightful video content on work and meaning on a website called bigthink.com (Ariely, & Jones, 2008). He elaborates how motivation and engagement are developed through meaning.

Michael Steger, Professor of Psychology at Colorado State University and founder and Director of the Center for Meaning and Purpose, encourages us to detect our work and meaning inventory (WAMI) at work. Employees in any company work for many reasons – some are very evident (to get a salary), some are not that evident (my friends work at the same place) (Steger et al., 2006). Research literature, data analysis and case-studies argue for the fact that understanding how

employees approach work and what they get from their workplace is important to understand how to accomplish excellent possible results for employees and the company. Meaning is a great predictor of desired work perspectives like work satisfaction. Also, meaningful work is a good predictor of employees being absent from work. The Work and Meaning Inventory (WAMI) gauges three main elements of meaningful work: the extent to which individuals detect their job to have importance and purpose, the contribution a job makes to detecting extended meaning in life, and the desire and process for an individual's work to make a positive addition to the greater good. Below five meaningful components to be considered are listed: 1) develop meaning rather than tracing them, developing meaning is an innovative and co-innovative process; 2) working with a meaning to accomplish meaningful outcomes; 3) passionately engaging with some of the routes listed to improvise your own meaning and assist others to develop their meaning; 4) having a broader vision about your work so that you can visualise and experience the larger ambition in what you do; 5) making yourself remember that meaning is a process rather than an incident; meaning is not discovered overnight, it requires engagement to find meaningful work on a daily basis.

Making a meaning is one of those components that is not conveyed explicitly, hence the study will evaluate the primary data to implicitly extract the understanding of "Making a meaning" in the case of Hero MotoCorp employees. This also offers a novel approach to the research since this component has not been explored before in relation to employee engagement and its influence on employee productivity.

9. Enhancing Well-being

We should develop internal wellbeing in the workplace. There are several steps which we can take external to our workplace to advocate wellbeing but how we cultivate and increase wellbeing within the workplace is becoming important. We must dispose of a lethal workplace environment, lacking respect and mutuality. We must develop intense wellbeing where individuals enrich the workplace rather than depleting the workplace environment. Below five instructions for wellbeing at the workplace are listed: 1) make cheerful the five elements of wellbeing; 2) developing stable wellbeing; 3) minding your work; 4) developing and cultivating psychological social safety; 5) bringing alive a wellbeing manifesto. Jim Harter, Chief Scientist of Workplace and Well-Being at Gallup, and Tom Rath, American consultant on employee engagement, strengths, and wellbeing,

published a book *Wellbeing: The Five Essential Elements*, stating that wellbeing is an amalgamation of love for what we execute daily, the authenticity of relationships, the safety of financial components, the energy of our physical health, and the pleasure we take in contributing towards our society (Rath & Harter, 2010). Most relevant is the convergence of these five elements for wellbeing. As per the results published by the authors, 66% of individuals are quiet well with at least one of the above five elements of wellbeing; however, only 7% of individuals are flourishing in all five areas. This leaves a definite vacuum to improvise on wellbeing at work in terms of the career parameter, financial parameter, social parameter, physical parameter, and community parameter. Martin Elias Peter Seligman, an American psychologist, advocates for wellbeing with the prudence of a scientist and the expectation of an individual who invented the method of learned optimism (Seligman, 2002). Not limiting to happiness work, Martin Elias Peter Seligman, explores flourishing and gives constructive inputs on how to imbibe wellbeing. Seligman's aspect of wellbeing also has a basis in 5 elements, dissimilar to Gallup, and formed around the abbreviation PERMA. The full form of PERMA is Positive, Emotions, Engagement, Relationship, Meaning and Achievement. Can an individual work towards sustainable wellbeing? Positive emotions and cheerful life activities add to our wellbeing and happiness. Engagement develops wellbeing with forceful interactions in terms of work, affinity and serving. Relationships are among the 10 pieces of the pyramid of engagement, in the literature after study has that that relationships are one of the most important addition to wellbeing. Meaning is a recent addition to the block studied in the series of the pyramid of engagement, which is important for health. Accomplishment is a new addition in Martin Elias Peter Seligman's method for authentic happiness and wellbeing. Seligman studies his love for bridge and concluded how much accomplishment plays a role in wellbeing. Accomplishment / achievement sinks well with the above three blocks of engagement pyramid: achieve results, maximise performance and path progress. Mindfulness can be a forceful yet elusive avenue to wellbeing. Jon Kabat-Zinn, an American professor emeritus of medicine and the developer of the Stress Reduction Clinic and the Center for Mindfulness in Medicine, illustrated mindfulness as focusing impartially in a distinct way, on desire in the present moment (Kabat-Zinn, 2005). How effectively are we showing up to the moment? One can mitigate soaring levels of stress connected to the past and the future by being where we are.

Stephan Rechtschaffen, president, and co-founder of the Omega Institute in Rhinebeck, specialising in holistic studies, stated in his book *Time Shifting* that there is no stress in the present moment (Rechtschaffen, 2002). Polly LaBarre, Leadership Expert & Founding Writer of the Fast Company published an article in Harvard Business review quoting Pamela Weiss a Buddhist teacher authorised in two traditions - Zen and Theraveda - that if one wants to change a company it is not about altering systems and methods so much as its about transforming people's minds and hearts (LaBarre, & Taylor 2014). Mindfulness is one of the most intense methods for helping to mitigate suffering of individuals by bringing out outstanding potential as human beings. Mindfulness seems so exquisite, almost lacking wellbeing, but for a planet which has gone insane it can keep us well, aware, centred, present and connected. We generally seem to be tracing for dramatic data-driven technique when this exquisite and forceful technique is permanently available to us, installed in us, and just a moment away. We have concentrated and advanced physical safety at work. We should provide safety to every employee. Moreover, we should make sure that our workplaces are imbued with psychological and social safety. Safety is developed through reciprocal purpose and reciprocal respect. It defines that there is a reciprocal characteristic of carrying between each other, especially carrying for things which we are mutual interested in. This characteristic must be authentic, and it is more than a vague warm feeling. Our ability to deliver results gets subverted, if people start doubting over safety parameter, develop relationships and be well at work. Absence of safety erodes wellbeing at work and develops futile clashes and confrontations. It seems to be that safety is a bigger topic than the engagement topic at work. It is perceived as unsafe for most employees to be honest, reliable, direct and appreciate engagement. An inadvertent aftermath of the anonymous survey in engagement is that we are informing workers that we do not intend to know who they are, thereby concealing the employees, hence powerful engagement needs a name and a face. Management tends to give its own argument, justifying anonymous surveys because organisations think employees may lie unless they are anonymous. Companies need to stop perceiving that disengagement is an offence and rather utilise it as a prompt for meaningful conversations about work. David Zinger, based on 15 years of work experience as an assistance counsellor and 25 years of teaching psychology at the University of Manitoba. Zinger (2019) has listed 33 suggestions to guide us towards better wellbeing at work: 1) we should try to find internal wellbeing at work and not rely on the external environment, unless we are out of our workplace or in the phase of retirement; 2) hope is a foolish future prospect

which tends to sway us from reality because we can make a difference, right now-right here; 3) in the present moment there is no stress, so one should aim to be where you are; 4) esteem is an evaluative ambush that watches you like cheese watches a mouse to be snapped in the ambush. Hence it is necessary to accept yourself rather than evaluating yourself; 5) life is primary, and work is secondary. Moreover, work and life balance are not stagnant, rather it is a changing balance; 6) wellbeing is just a theory unless someone engages in doing well; 7) ignorance becomes primary, and knowledge becomes secondary in the case of fostering and increasing wellbeing because not knowing is the beginning; 8) individuals tend to repel their interpersonal feedback until and unless these are a component of personal safety because they help in overcoming psychological problems; 9) authentic caring wins over official competency in almost every relationship; 10) accomplishing happiness is a trivial and irrelevant approach to living; 11) structure wins over self-discipline and willpower in advocating and increasing wellbeing; 12) useful and powerful put forth in front of us are essential WD40 (WD40-repeat 47, a microtubule-associated protein, is essential for brain development and autophagy) for the brain; 13) wellbeing is a powerful substance. We must understand how to live and leverage our power in the service of others; 14) energy must be in line with wellbeing to receive energy and when it gets drained, it becomes a major hurdle to experiencing wellbeing; 15) relaxation is a drug for stress management; however, it can lead to stress; 16) what might mitigate stress today may primarily be a reason for fostering stress tomorrow; 17) There are no arithmetical possibilities of wellbeing but only heuristic expectations of success; 18) we are humans, life is a journey, one suffers stumbles, failure, and falls. It does not matter how many times you fall but what matters is how many times you stand again by picking yourself up. In transactional analysis, it is often said, I am not okay, you are not okay and that is okay; 19) a placebo is anything that seems to be a "real" are best examples of caring transforming into tangible; 20) employee wellbeing cannot be termed as a soft skill, just as accounting cannot be termed as a hard skill. Wellbeing becomes flowing in nature when the fixed components of life are in a desperate state of repair and maintenance; 21) reality is exaggerated, living through positive deception, not delusion, is practical and forceful; 22) wellbeing is more than an intimate enterprise; it is a societal phenomenon; 23) only an individual is answerable for its own wellbeing, however others are obligated for your wellbeing; 24) no one has the capacity to upset someone, once those 90 seconds have gone; 25) compliance is a secondary product of power; 26) logically one does not repel change but rather repel persuasion and the gravity of the recognisable is what

holds us where we are placed; 27) when life throws a lemon at you, think, and decide where it has arrived from, think what one can do out of it and then only think of making lemonade. It is a proverbial phrase utilised to enforce optimism in the face of misfortune. Lemons are the sourness or hindrances in life whereas lemonade is turning that situation into a positive one; 28) positive thinking must be transformed into a more genuine productive thinking. Everyone goes through a rough phase; positive thinking can act as a gloss to reduce the ruggedness; 29) bad is twice as important as good in most circumstance, so one must make the critical difference for good; 30) life is an iceberg, most of it we know, we don't know; 31) conflicting views are only dangerous, if we lock ourselves into fixated thinking and mindset; 32) wellbeing suggestions that are discussed without personal analysis and experimentation can develop a confused circle to suggestions leading to the generation of more stress. One must practice Buddha's wisdom, "be a light unto yourself", in terms of the path of enlightenment; 33) as famously quoted by the great comedian Charlie Chaplin, take a long shot, life is a calamity in closeup and a comedy in long shot. How much time do you need to take a long shot on yourself, others, and circumstances?

In the case of Hero MotoCorp, the company has taken several steps for employees, as per the wellbeing report published by the company. Hero MotoCorp has also received a "Healthy Workplace Award", at the 7th Global Healthy Workplace Awards, held in collaboration with Monash Wellbeing. The study will analyse the steps undertaken by Hero MotoCorp, for improving wellbeing of the employees and evaluate the perceived value of these steps and the impact they have on employee productivity.

10. Enlivening Energy

The basic resource of engagement is energy. Input of energy is required for engagement and genuine engagement adds to our energy. Energy comes in different forms: organisational, mental, physical, spiritual, and emotional. We must work towards proficiency of all our energies. Below are five methods to imbibe energy for employee engagement: 1) infuse power in the engagement via energy; 2) intensify through superior-quality network; 3) energy should be mobile in nature without any hindrance; 4) go for a brisk walk of at least 10 minutes; 5) form the habit of asking energy questions of yourself and others. In the past decade, the spotlight on energy relating to mental, spiritual, emotional, and physical have grown stronger. However, these four forms of energies are new for the workplace and have a strong basis in historical medicine utilised by "First

Nations” people from a very long time ago. Jim Loehr, co-author of *The Power of Full Engagement* and Tony Schwartz an American journalist and business book author known for his contribution to *Trump: The Art of the Deal* book, published a book *The Power of Full Engagement in 2003* on the above discussed four energies (Loehr, 2005). *The Power of Full Engagement in 2003* was known as one of finest books on engagement. Both the authors made a powerful energy declaration that “not time” but energy is the main component of superior performance. Happiness, performance, and health are grounded in the adroit management of energy. Jim Loehr a world-renowned performance psychologist and C-Suite Leadership Coach and Tony Schwartz an American journalist stated that to be completely engaged one should be physically energised, interconnected emotionally, psychologically centred and spiritually regulated with a reason beyond our urgent self-interest. They argued that physical scope is the amount of energy, emotional capability is the trait of energy, mental capability is the focal point of energy, and spiritual capability is the strength of energy. We require a great amount of energy to give us a focal point and strength to accomplish outcomes. With a list of instructions, research, and constructive practices, this book can help to alter and leverage strength for complete engagement. Jane E. Dutton, cofounder of the Center for Positive Organisations at the University of Michigan's Ross School of Business, has completed a great amount of research and contributed to literature on energy in companies. Energy is the feeling of “being craving to move and competent of action” (Worline, Dutton and Sisodia, 2017). Jane E. Dutton gives a pathway based on evidence to cultivate and increase a company’s energy through the force of superior-quality interconnection at work. Energy is finite but sustainable resources and managers can add exclusively to energy formation. Super-quality interconnections not only energise others but also ourselves, they have a compelling influence on wellbeing and mitigate or eradicate corrosive connections. Frequent intercommunication develops upon respectful engagement, assignment enabling, and faith can bring changing vitality to engagement and a company’s outcome. Heike Bruch, professor and director of the institute for leadership and human resources management of the university of St. Gallen, and Bernd Vogel, professor in leadership and director of the Henley centre for leadership, defined how managers can foster their company’s energy and flareup strong performance (Bruch and Vogel, 2011). Organisational energy is the that trails team works or organisation. A company must marshal its behavioural, cognitive, and emotional potential. There are four forms of energy depending on strength and quality: productive energy, corrosive energy, comfortable energy, and

resigned energy. In the case of productive energy, high intensity of dedication, mental agility, and effort are coordinated with organisational objectives. Energy states play an anticipatory role in various benefits in performance, customer loyalty, productivity, customer satisfaction, and effectivity. To increase organisational energy, an organisation must shield against three energy exhausting pitfalls: excess complacency, destroying corrosion, and endless acceleration.

Robert E. Thayer, professor of psychology at California State University, an influential researcher in biopsychology, published an astute and well-investigated book on energy and mood, *Calm Energy: How People Regulate Mood with Food and Exercise* (Thayer, 1997). Thayer conducted an in-depth investigation on how one can control mood and how this controlling mechanism is linked to food. Thayer suggested in numerous experiments that the most powerful approach to curb mood and energy was by a brief duration of brisk walking; just a brisk walk of 10 minutes elevates energy which is prominent for an hour. We must restore our energy during the day by a brief walk or a brief sleep, it gives instinct dose of rejuvenation to work related activities. Donald Hiller Graves, an American author specialising in the field of writing education, devoted a year to examining the relationship between energy and teaching (Graves, 2006). He published an explanatory book on the energy to teach. In a true sense, he travelled across the United States asking one simple question, “What provides you energy, what takes it away, and how do you define a waste of time?”. This a key question we must ask ourselves and self-reflect, by analysing our responses, to give an opened ended-route to an energising communication.

Enlivening energy is a powerful implicit component of employee engagement influencing employee productivity. Interviews were conducted to generate valuable data to dwell on this parameter and explore the perceptions of the employees of Hero MotoCorp, in relation to productivity.

2.12.2 ADKAR model

Change is an inevitable part of the world and is the only constant thing that exists around us. However, the process of change might not be as easy as it seems and is often disliked by employees within an organisation initially, until they start to realise the importance of change. It is the responsibility of the organisation to ensure that the change is rolled out across the entire organisation smoothly. One model or framework which can be helpful in this context is the

ADKAR model proposed by Jeffrey Hiatt (AL-Qahtani, 2010). ADKAR stands for Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability and Reinforcement. It is an employee-focused method for managing change (Shepherd, 2014). This model is helpful in facilitating change on an individual level as, according to this model, change is more related to how people react to the change.

The first step of the ADKAR model is to create awareness amongst the employees regarding the need for change. During this step, the organisation must convey the positives related to the change and the negatives of the previous system, process or model. It is necessary to ensure that the employees participate in the process and support the process (Shepherd, 2014). This can be done through formal or casual meetings or presentations about the advantages of the change. The third step is conveying the process of change or how the organisation will go through with the change. This step must discuss the process of change in depth to clear away doubts and concerns about the process. The next step will be the implementation of the change (AL-Qahtani, 2010). This can be in the form of gradual changes from department to department or across the entire organisation in one flow. The last step is to make sure that the changes are maintained, and the old process or system has vanished so that the employees do not go back to the old system.

Hero MotoCorp has been going through a systemic change since its separation from Honda Motors, on December 16, 2010. The previous process and system of Hero MotoCorp were localised, catering to the Indian sub-continent due to the partnership agreement. Hero MotoCorp had global ambitions due to its production capacity and manufacturing competence. Hence it is necessary to consider changing workplace conditions while evaluating the influence of employee engagement on employee productivity in the case of Hero MotoCorp. The ADKAR model is practical in nature as it emphasises individual change for an employee or making sure that individual employees make a transition and transform. The ADKAR model best suits Hero MotoCorp, which is the largest manufacturer of two-wheelers in the world because it is not bound to tasks and a process of change management but rather focuses on a greater level of individual achievement.

2.14 Conceptual Framework

Figure 3 Conceptual Framework

Source: (Hiatt 2006; Zinger 2019)

A conceptual framework demonstrates the areas that research intends to explore. It identifies the relevant variables for the research and outlines how these variables might relate to each other. The conceptual framework is supposed to be constructed before the data collection stage. The above conceptual framework will assist in evaluating the impact of changing workplace conditions and employee engagement on employee productivity in the context of Hero MotoCorp India. The conceptual framework has utilised Zinger's (2019) model of employee engagement and Hiatt's (2006) ADKAR model of change management. A combination of both these models to analyse the productivity of employees offers a novel approach and will contribute to the existing pool of literature on employee engagement, change management and employee productivity.

For a company like Hero MotoCorp, results are the cornerstone, to maintain its position as the largest manufacturer of two-wheelers in the world. With changing consumer demand, the company needs to adopt itself and at the same time, achieve results. Hero MotoCorp pays special attention to maximising performance, by employing a unique appraisal system, aimed at enhancing productivity, attaining global standards, creating motivation, and career growth. This cannot be possible without analysing the factor of clarity among its employees, how clarity is perceived in Hero MotoCorp which is an important factor towards the path to progress. Hero MotoCorp is an Indian company; it will be interesting to evaluate how the concept of relationship building is dealt with by the company. Mastering moments and self-reflection are another factor in the conceptual framework that needs to be evaluated in the context of Hero MotoCorp and whether time shifts impact their working. Making meaning, enhancing well-being and enlivening energy are the other three core employee centric components that will be explored in the context of Hero MotoCorp.

2.15. Conclusion

The purpose of the preceding literature review has been to discuss how a change in the working conditions in Hero MotoCorp due first to the separation from Honda Motors and then due to the global outlook ambition of the company impacts the productivity of the employees within the organisation. The literature review conducted an in-depth discussion of factors of employee engagement and the concept of employee productivity and change management. It has been concluded that change is an essential part of the organisation; therefore, it is important that the organisation must undergo effective strategies to ensure that the change process is rolled out effectively. Specifically, in the case of Hero MotoCorp, it is pertinent to take steps, if it intends to expand globally and wants to maintain its position as the largest manufacturer of two-wheelers in the world.

Ten important factors of employee engagement extrapolated from Zinger's model and five factors of change from the ADKAR model are influenced by organisational support and the opportunities to grow that are provided to employees. The relationship between employee engagement and productivity are discussed and it was found that the performance and productivity of the employees are enhanced if the level of engagement within the organisation is high.

It was also found out that the workplace conditions and the leadership or the management of the firm have a substantial impact on the productivity of the employees. Firms that provide adequate working conditions for employees are successful as the performance of the employees is higher. The literature also concluded that change is a difficult process and if not managed properly, it might affect the productivity of employees in a negative manner. To support the literature, two theories are also discussed. The Zinger model of engagement and the ADKAR model of change are discussed in the theoretical framework of the literature. The last part of the literature has presented the conceptual framework based on the literature.

Since developing the conceptual framework, the next step is to develop the research methodology. The research methodology is the method or techniques employed to determine, select, process, and analyse data aimed at elucidating the research topic. The next chapter is on the research methodology justifying the procedures adopted to conduct the research.

Chapter Three: Research Methodology

3.1 Chapter Introduction

The research methodology provides directions to conduct a research study. Therefore, this chapter is essential in identifying the research philosophy, approaches, and research methods (Saunders, 2011). In addition to that, all these research tools and techniques contribute to attaining the research aims and objectives. For example, the study commenced with the research population identification, sampling techniques description, sample size selection and the research instrument preference for research interviews. Furthermore, the chapter includes methods of data collection that include primary and secondary sources of data.

Additionally, the chapter also encompasses data analysis and the presentation of the data. In the end, the chapter concludes with research limitations and ethical considerations of the research under review. Lastly, the conclusion of the chapter has included a summary of key findings on the research methodologies.

3.2 Research Onion

Figure 4 Research Onion. Source: Thornhill, Saunders and Lewis (2009)

The study utilises the research onion model published in *Research Methods for Business Students* by Thornhill, Saunders and Lewis (2009). This model aims to analyse the different research levels to assist researchers in developing an improvised organised methodology. The above research onion model characteristically epitomises various components analysed to create the final research design. The research onion comprises six main layers: 1) **philosophy**: attributing a set of rules about the worldview or viewpoint from which the research operates, studied under the terminology of ontology and epistemology. Ontology stands for the authenticity of the data and its interpretation. Ontology is defined as things existing in the social world, as well as preconceptions about the shape and character of that social reality. It asks whether social reality exists autonomously of human comprehension and perception; for example, is there a shared social reality or many context-specific realities? On the other hand, epistemology stands to validate data needed to conduct the research and collecting it. It is concerned with the nature of knowledge and how people learn and know about social reality. Philosophical positions are segmented into positivism and interpretivism. Positivism accepts that knowledge is not dependent on the subject under consideration. Interpretivism advocates that every observer has an inherent perception and evaluation of reality. Positivism is generally scientific in result testing, hence are qualitative, whereas interpretivism is generally qualitative. The study under consideration on change and engagement utilises **an interpretivist approach**. 2) **Approach**: this is necessary to pick up an appropriate methodology. The methodological approach includes the deductive approach and inductive approach. The deductive approach opens with a definitive hypothesis for testing, based on an in-depth literature review observed by researchers. Deductive reasoning, often known as deductive logic, is the process of arriving at a logical conclusion by reasoning from one or more propositions (premises). In contrast, the inductive approach commences with observations that researchers utilise to arrive at a conclusion or create a new theory. The inductive approach, generally referred to as inductive reasoning, begins with observations, and theories are generated from observations near the end of the research process. The study under consideration has taken an **inductive approach** in conducting the research, that is, a bottom-up approach, moving from a specific scenario of Hero MotorCorp to a general organisational phenomenon. 3) **Strategy**: this offers a path for relevant data collection for conducting the research. Strategies can include a case study or systematic review, action research, survey, interview, or experimental research. The study under consideration decided to utilise **interviews** to collect data, and employees of Hero

MotorCorp are respondents. 4) Choices of Methods: in the case of choice of methods, the research onion proposes mono, mixed and multi-methods as desirable choices for conducting research. The mono-method consists of only one type of method for conducting research. In contrast, the mixed method consists of two or more types of methods of research, usually defined as a qualitative and quantitative research methodology. The third one is multi-method which utilises a wider selection of methods. The study under consideration decided to employ a **mono-method** technique for the generation of data via interview. 5) Time horizons: this relates to the time construct of the research. The time horizon can include cross-sectional and longitudinal. Observations utilise cross-sectional data, which includes observations made at a single point in time, as in most surveys. On the other hand, longitudinal data suggests that observations are made from the point of view of a variable available for several quarters, years, or months. The study under consideration falls under **the cross-sectional** time zone. 6) Data collection and analysis: this is the last level of the research onion and includes techniques and measures utilised. It elaborates the ways and reasons behind conducting the research. The study under consideration utilises both primary data and secondary data for carrying out the research. In the case of primary data, the study has utilised **qualitative** data generated via interviews.

3.2 Research Philosophy (Interpretive Constructionism)

The research philosophy can be defined as a set of beliefs and agreements among scientists, which defines the standardised techniques and methods to understand and address research problems (Kaushik & Walsh, 2019). In other words, the research paradigm provides a standardised and time-tested model to assist the research process (Collis and Hussey, 2013).

Some of the most common philosophies include positivism and constructivism. The first one deals with a single reality and describes it to be known and measurable. Therefore, this paradigm encourages the researcher to use quantitative methods to assess and measure that reality (Collis and Hussey, 2013). Constructivists contradict the positivist approach and nullify any “single reality or single truth”. Constructivists believe in the possibility of more than one reality. Therefore, the practice encourages the researcher to use the qualitative method to unveil those multiple truths/realities (Greenfield, 2016). According to pragmatists, reality is continually debated, explained, and negotiated. Therefore, the solution to the research problem is the best and most preferable option (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

Qualitative research in social sciences has shown a higher tendency of researchers to adopt an interpretive approach. According to interpretivism, human behaviour is an unpredictable multi-layered structure, which cannot be studied using traditional and predefined probability models. Furthermore, they argue that human behaviour is influenced by environmental factors, whereas genes do not play any considerable role in the development of human behaviour. Therefore, interpretive studies consider human behaviour in the presence of natural variables and not in a controlled environment (Hair et al., 2015). In other words, positivism and interpretivism can be summarised as two parallel approaches. The positivists believe in the predictability, probability, measurability, and controllability of human behaviour. While on the other hand, interpretivism believes that human behaviour is unpredictable and should be studied in the natural environment. Although these paradigms contradict each other, both are necessary for the development and growth of knowledge (Bajpai, 2011).

As the research under consideration is majorly associated with determining the impact of employee engagement on overall change management, the interpretivism philosophy will work the best with this study. This is because the study under consideration aims to study different aspects of human behaviour (Cooper et al., 2013).

3.3 Research Methods (Qualitative Research Method)

Quantitative and qualitative methods are the most common research methods (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). And the choice of appropriate research method for a study is entirely dependent upon the nature of the research questions, personal preferences, and the researcher's familiarity with these methods (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

Quantitative Research

The quantitative research method utilises statistical and numerical data. Mathematical and statistical tools enable the researcher to derive his assessment in a short period. The research data for this method is also straightforward to identify; for example, if numerical figures and numbers are not involved in the research, it cannot undergo quantitative analysis. Therefore, quantitative research data are often classified into primary and secondary research data (Bryman and Bell, 2015). The quantitative research data can be obtained from various sources, such as online and personal surveys, interviews, and observation. Quantitative data can be analysed and illustrated in

multiple ways. For instance, graphs can be used to represent the correlation between derived values visually. Similarly, cluster analysis is preferred to identify and explain relationships between those groups that are not tested hypothetically (Zikmund et al., 2013).

Along with this, the quantitative research method commonly adopts experiments and surveys as critical data collection tools. Experiments are beneficial to provide research outcomes related to the cause-and-effect relationship between different research variables, including independent and dependent ones. However, the most adopted method of data collection is survey and questionnaire. In a survey, interviews can be conducted via telephone conversation, through online interviews, and other sources. After data collection, quantitative data are analysed using statistical tools. Many analytical tools such as regression analysis, t-tests, correlation, and many others derive authentic, reliable, and accurate research outcomes.

Qualitative Research

The qualitative research technique is different from the quantitative research method as it does not analyse numerical values. The qualitative research method utilises narration, words, pictures, and observations to collect data for analysis. The qualitative study provides a comprehensive understanding of the context. The data derived through qualitative analysis can identify attributes and characteristics of the research object. For instance, qualitative analysis can provide considerable information about personal traits and behavioural and emotional attributes if a human body is subjected to research. This quality offers it a distinctive edge over quantitative analyses.

Qualitative research data can be procured through interviews; these can be structured, unstructured or semi-structured. However, interviews are highly time-consuming for conducting research, though they are beneficial to achieve the desired results and responses from respondents related to the critical research topic. Another required data collection method is online or offline distributed questionnaires that encourage users to write their feedback in response to specific queries about the research topic. One of the key benefits of using a survey questionnaire is to get accurate answers. However, the reactions can create biases in the results.

Qualitative data can be analysed using various analysis tools, such as data structuring and coding. These days, the trend for computer-assisted qualitative analysis is also becoming popular.

However, the choice of tools is often influenced by academic colleagues and the researcher's supervisor (William, 2003). The key reason behind the deployment of a qualitative research methodology is that it enables the researcher to get detailed insight into the meanings of the responses that the research participants give. As a result, this allows the researchers to better understand the critical dynamics associated with the research topic. Apart from that, the deployment of such a methodology also allows the researcher to better learn from the respondents' experiences, hence developing a basis for the readers to draw meaning from the research and add their interpretations to the results, creating independent conclusions (Cooper et al., 2013).

3.4 Research Approach

Research is a comprehensive process, and it can be conducted in numerous ways. However, the five most common methods are described below. In addition, these research methods are often used in combination with other research methods (Bajpai, 2011).

Descriptive Approach EXPLORATORY METHOD

As the name suggests, the descriptive research explores the research topic and provides additional details to enhance the researcher's understanding. In other words, a descriptive study attempts to collect the maximum possible information about the research topic and paves the way for further research work. It also answers the fundamental questions about the nature of the research object; however, it does not provide sufficient details to predict the results (Hair et al., 2015). This approach is beneficial to developing an understanding of the "problem" that research attempts to address. However, a descriptive study is only helpful if the information is selected according to specific criteria. The descriptive method of study is preferred because it effectively collects details about minor problems (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016; Greener, 2008). It offers an observation of the research-object in the natural and variable-influences environment, which leads to honest and realistic assessment (Hair et al., 2015). Descriptive research can also incorporate qualitative and quantitative techniques during the data collection process (Bryman and Bell, 2015). A descriptive study is timesaving (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

On the other hand, descriptive research cannot provide statistical and numerical figures about the research topic. Therefore, the collected data may contain a data collector's bias to a certain level. Descriptive research is an observation-based technique; consequently, it is repeatable.

However, it just studies the research object and does not provide any details about the cause of that specific phenomenon (Greenfield, 2016). Many studies have already been conducted about the role of employee engagement in the facilitation of change within an organisation. Therefore, the descriptive research approach best suits this research, as it will allow the researcher to further describe this topic, specifically in the context of Hero MotoCorp India. In addition to that, the researcher has made use of a qualitative research methodology. This approach best suits the methods and will help the researcher ensure that practical conclusions are generated through the research, thereby adding to the overall scope of the study (Saunders, 2011).

3.5 Research Population

The research population signifies the number of respondents subjected to research questions or any scientific query (Greenfield, 2016). In other words, a research population is a specific number of individual respondents or objects with similar characteristics, which are utilised to collect data for that particular research. However, if the research population is large, it becomes problematic, expensive and time consuming for the researcher to reach each individual. Therefore, to counter these issues, researchers utilise sampling techniques (Saunders et al., 2012). For this research, the research population will include all the organisations that have the same employee base, scale of operations, and overall resource base and operate within the automotive sector of India. This is because the current study has been conducted about Hero MotoCorp, India. Hence, the results of this study can be effectively extended across organisations that operate in similar areas over the same scale and nature of operations without causing the issue of mass generalisation (William, 2003).

3.6 Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

The research under consideration has made use of the convenience sampling technique for the selection of the sample. This technique allows the researcher to select a model that is most conveniently available to the researcher. Because participants are chosen based on their availability and willingness to participate, convenience sampling is possibly the simplest sampling technique. The key reason behind the deployment of this technique is that it will enable the researcher to select a sample within the given time and monetary constraints. It is also relatively simple, allowing the researcher to choose a model without entering technical statistical calculations. This

sampling technique, however, is prone to the issue of biasness. To cater to this issue effectively, the researcher has selected a sample from different departments, hence reducing the probability of bias, thereby ensuring that the conclusions generated by the research are not clouded (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

3.7 Sample Size INTERVIEW SURVEY

The research under consideration is based on a sample size of 20 employees. The primary reason for selecting this sample size is that it will allow the researcher to ensure that holistic and exhaustive data are collected through in-depth interviews. On the other hand, bulk data collection or data mismanagement have been reduced to the minimum. Hence, it has allowed the research to manage and organise the data effectively. Finally, as the study under consideration has collected data through interviews, too large a sample size would have delayed the overall data collection process, hindering the comprehensive research (Hair et al., 2015).

Research Instrument

Research instruments are defined as “those specific tools which researchers design to assist their research process”. These tools help researchers to collect necessary data for analysis. Some of these tools include structured and unstructured questionnaires (William, 2003). Structured and unstructured interviews include inter-person communication using electronic mediums such as video chat or phone calls which are also considered interviews (Cooper, Schindler and Sun, 2013). Institutions also utilise the performance evaluation and achievements of individuals to assess the performance of those individuals (Greener, 2008). Other research instruments include rational rose, rating scale and checklist (Bajpai, 2011).

The research under consideration has adopted interviews as the critical research instruments to gather primary data from participants. The mechanism is explained below:

Interviews

Interviews are defined as a well-structured and systematic way of interacting with people. Interviews mainly aim to inquire into the thoughts and opinions of an individual or group through a formal or informal conversation. Researchers use open-ended questions during interviews to collect the maximum amount of data from respondents. However, when researchers hire a “third

party” interviewer, they should know that an interviewer’s views are not a part of their research. Instead, they should maintain their primary focus of respondents’ feedback and responses. Interviews provide an opportunity for respondents to freely express their views and opinion about a specific topic or object (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

Researchers can also utilise interviews as a platform to observe the reaction of respondents in response to certain simulated situations. The researcher should ensure the clarity and affectivity of research questions, and an appropriate method should be adopted to control the flow of ideas. Interviews serve an essential role during research, and many experts believe that interview is the most effective platform to know about someone’s honest opinion about any object or situation. Moreover, interviews can provide genuine and personalised data to the researcher that is very helpful for producing accurate results. Interviews also offer several opportunities to researchers, such as probing, chain questioning and the opportunity to observe the body language and physical responses of respondents (Saunders, 2011).

3.8 Methods of Data Collection

Data collection can be defined as a well-structured and pre-planned process to collect information from all relevant sources to address the research problem, as well as to test the precision of the hypothesis and to predict the outcome of the research (Greenfield, 2016). The data collection techniques can be categorised into two types that include primary data collection methods and secondary data collection methods (Collis and Hussey, 2013).

Primary Sources

The primary data collection techniques consist of quantitative and qualitative data collection methods. As described before, quantitative data collection methods deal with statistical figures and complicated mathematical calculations in multiple formats. However, the procedure for collecting quantitative data and analysis is relatively simple. The technique involves the formation of a questionnaire where closed-ended questions are arranged in an appropriate sequence. This questionnaire is then either published online or distributed among individuals to register their feedback. Finally, the collected data are analysed using concepts of regression and correlation, mean, median, mode and other statistical processing formats (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

Researchers often prefer quantitative methods because they are cheaper to apply and are time-saving. On the other hand, continuous advancements and standardisation of mathematical techniques, and results derived from quantitative analysis can be cross-matched/compared with other results to find the precision and accuracy of findings (Zikmund et al., 2013). On the other hand, qualitative research methods do not utilise numerical values for analysis. Instead, qualitative research methods are related to collecting narrative data such as sounds, language, words, sentences and emotions. In other words, every non-quantitative thing can be associated with qualitative data.

Moreover, qualitative data provide a deeper understanding of context, whereas the collection methods for qualitative data are also different. For instance, qualitative data collection questionnaires include open-ended questions for detailed and personalised feedback of the targeted audience. Other methods include focus groups, role-playing, observation and case studies (Saunders et al., 2012). As described before, the researcher's choice to utilise quantitative or qualitative data in his research is widely influenced by nature, area, and the objective of his study.

Interviews

As discussed above, the research under consideration has adopted interviews as the critical research instrument to gather primary data from participants. Interviews can be classified into different categories. These include structured interviews, semi-structured interviews and unstructured interviews (Greener, 2008). Structured interviews, as the name suggests, follow a pre-defined strategy to ask precise questions to collect accurate and comprehensive feedback from respondents. These interviews strictly follow their script and leave no room for follow-up sessions. Such interviews are easier to conduct and manage.

On the other hand, unstructured interviews are unorganised sessions that do not follow any structure. Such interviews often start with a generic opening question, and then respondents' responses lead the conversation. These interviews are not only time consuming but are also challenging to manage. The outcomes of unstructured interviews often lack the required depth about the context, and sometimes follow-up questions are needed to be asked of respondents for detailed understanding (Cooper et al., 2013).

Semi-structured interviews are a combination of structured and unstructured interviewing methodologies. Such interviews follow a pre-determined path; however, semi-structured interviews are not as rigid as structured interviews and allow the interviewer and respondent to lead and maintain the flow of their discussion. Such interviews are prevalent in the healthcare industry, where medical staff start by asking some pre-defined and generic questions, but conversations become personalised as they move forward. Semi-structured interviews are often preferred over structured interviews because this method allows the respondent to collect personalised information, which is necessary to produce accurate results out of research (Bajpai, 2011).

Hence, the research under consideration has made use of semi-structured interviews. These allow the researchers to ensure that a considerable and adequate amount of space is provided to the respondents. It ensures that the key findings associated with the respondents' experiences are extracted and identified effectively during the research. Such a data collection instrument also plays an essential role in ensuring that the researcher retains control over the direction of the conversation. As a result, the researcher is facilitated to make sure that the topic of the discussion does not move away from the topic of the research, hence allowing effective data collection (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

Focus Group

An interview is a person-to-person communication, whereas focus groups collect similar data from many respondents at once. A focus group is a research group that is organised to initiate discussion about the research topic. Focus groups are especially helpful in producing information about participants' collective views, which compares logical reasons regarding the research topic or some specific phenomenon. In addition to that, focus groups also serve as an effective platform for respondents to share their personal experiences and life events, which provides an opportunity for the moderator (researcher) to establish theories and predict outcomes based on the personal experiences of participants (Greenfield, 2016). However, focus groups have numerous drawbacks: 1) since they are a group task, not everyone is able to express their opinion; 2) dominant participants' views can overshadow the topic under discussion; 3) respondents may give a biased

view on a topic because of another respondent's opinion; 4) organising and executing a focus group is complex compared to interview.

Secondary Sources

Secondary data can be defined as “the information collected and published by another researcher”. The secondary sources are cost-efficient and timesaving. The secondary data sources are beneficial when primary data sources are unavailable or cannot be obtained. Additionally, secondary data also provide guidelines for the researcher to lead his research. They also help the researcher make his primary data collection more elaborative and specific according to the context.

Moreover, secondary data also identify the deficiencies and shortcomings related to the “research topic” and “research population”, which helps the researcher during his research period. In other words, it provides a considerable amount of data about the research topic and maps an outline for the researcher to build his research strategy (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Secondary data have been used in the review of academic literature related to the research topic. Along with this, there are several sources of secondary data collection. Some of them include journal articles, use of the online website, books, official reports, the company's website and many other sources (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

As described before, the secondary data set a reliable foundation for the researcher related to his research. Using this information, a researcher can develop his research methodology, as well as data collection strategy. In addition, data obtained from secondary sources contain information about authors and credible publishers, which is very helpful for the researcher before he initiates his research. Secondary data can also be used to compare research results, enabling the researcher to overcome his deficiencies. Moreover, data obtained through secondary sources highlight the research gap and challenges that help the researcher set his direction and produce precise results (Cooper, Schindler and Sun, 2013).

3.9 Data Analysis and Presentation

The research under consideration has made use of the content analysis technique to assess the collected data. Content analysis is a qualitative research method for analysing and identifying

patterns and themes in content. The content was generated by transcribing the data available through recording of the interviews. Under this technique, the data have been analysed through the deployment of a stepwise approach. These steps include a first step consisting of dividing the overall data into small segments based on four departments of respondents (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012) (Appendix 4). The researcher then assessed these segments, and a first set of findings were drawn (Cooper, Schindler and Sun, 2013) (Appendix 3). The next step was associated with developing broader categories based on objectives that were identified under the second step (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012) (Chapter 5). Finally, the last step was associated with amalgamating categories into broader themes based on the similarity between their findings (Cooper, Schindler and Sun, 2013). Manual transcription of data and analysis was executed, to avoid complexities involved while employing software such as NVivo. These complexities include interpretation of data and time consumed in channelling the data through the software (Zamawe, 2015).

The key reason behind the deployment of this data analysis approach is that it will allow the researcher to ensure that all the aspects of the data are effectively analysed, and holistic findings are drawn out of the data (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). For data presentation, the researcher has ensured the use of simple words, direct quotations, and a logical pattern. All of these elements will ensure that the data do not lose their true meaning and essence. At the same time, the readers are facilitated to develop links between different components of the data and can draw their conclusions by following through with the overall research (Cooper, Schindler and Sun, 2013).

3.10 Ethical Considerations

Ethical issues are the biggest concerns that emerge during the interview process. Hence, high ethical standards should be practised while interacting with respondents, and their privacy and confidentiality must be ensured. It is the moral responsibility of the researcher to make sure that his research does not cause any damage to respondents in any way. The interviews should not be utilised for commercial purposes or to gain monetary benefits. Interviews should be conducted on high moral grounds, and if a respondent seems upset, then the interview should be immediately postponed (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

Some ethical concerns and solutions include that the research under consideration has collected data from direct respondents; hence, anonymity was one of the ethical issues that we're the study under review confronts us. Therefore, the researcher ensured that no personal data, such as name and phone number, were collected during the research (Cooper, Schindler and Sun, 2013). Another critical issue confronted by the study under consideration is that of informed consent. To manage the consent issue effectively and appropriately, the researcher ensured that all the respondents were informed about the purpose of the research. Their free consent to participate in the study was taken before their interview (Saunders et al., 2012). Furthermore, the research also confronted plagiarism, which was managed effectively using proper referencing. The original author of the work was acknowledged when someone else's ideas or opinions were used in this research (Cooper, Schindler and Sun, 2013).

3.11 Chapter Conclusion

As is evident from the analysis mentioned above, the research under consideration has been conducted using a qualitative research method, where the researcher used an interpretivist paradigm. Further, a descriptive approach was followed, where the data were collected using interviews with the employees. The research population was all the organisations operating at the same scale as Hero MotoCorp, India. The sample was 20 employees of Hero MotoCorp, India, selected using the convenience sampling technique. Finally, the data were analysed through a content analysis technique and presented using quotations, simple words, and a logical flow.

CHAPTER FOUR: Analysis of Results

4.1: Introduction

Data analysis for this study has been conducted mostly in the form of qualitative research. As a part of qualitative research, 20 interviews were conducted amongst the employees of Hero MotoCorp India keeping in mind the employee engagement of the organisation which is the main essence of this research thesis. The interviews were conducted amongst multiple employees working in various departments in the company so that we have an overview of employees from different areas of work and understand the overall working culture.

The interview data (4.2) have been divided into four main sections (4.2.1, 4.2.2, 4.2.3 & 4.2.4) which include all the interviews undertaken for this research. Section 4.2.1 majorly contributes towards explaining the effects of employee engagement and 4.2.2 analyses the strategies uses by Hero MotoCorp India. The other two sections, mainly 4.2.3, contribute towards the effects of disengaged employees on personal performance, organisational performance and co-workers and finally, Section 4.2.4 talks about the roles of trust and leadership in employee engagement including behavioural and attitude changes.

The qualitative analysis is drawn based on the interviews conducted and the responses recorded from the employees working in the Hero MotoCorp India organisation. The responses of some of the informants have been stated below and the rest of the interview answers have been mentioned in the appendices.

4.1.1 List of Interview Questions

Effects of employee engagement in Hero MotoCorp India

1. Interview Question: How can you identify if an employee is engaged or not?

Strategies used by Hero MotoCorp India for employee engagement including both positive and negative effects.

2. Interview Question: What strategies do you use to keep employees motivated?

3. Interview Question: What strategies do you use to keep employees engaged in the organisation?
You can mention multiple strategies.

4. Interview Question: What strategies mentioned in the previous question didn't work or weren't very effective? Why?

5. Interview Question: Are there any strategies used by the organisation to increase employee engagement? Were there any challenges? If yes, how were the challenges overcome?

6. Interview Question: When do you feel disengaged at work?

7. Interview Question: Did your organisation use any strategy/motivation to engage you again?

8. Interview Question: What strategies do the organisations use to renew employee engagement?

Effects of disengaged employees on their personal performance, organisational performance, and co-workers in Hero MotoCorp India.

9. Interview Question: What is the effect of disengaged employees on organisational performance?

10. Interview Question: What is the effect of disengaged employees on personal performance?

11. Interview Question: What is the effect of disengaged employees on co-workers?

Role of trust and leadership in employee engagement including behavioural and attitude changes.

12. Interview Question: How does the attitude of an employee change when they are disengaged?

13. Interview Question: What role does trust play in influencing employee engagement? Why?

14. Interview Question: How does leadership influence employee engagement?

4.2: Interview and Responses

4.2.1 Effects of Employee Engagement in Hero MotoCorp India

Interview Question: How can you identify if an employee is engaged or not?

Respondents were selected from four specific departments: 1) maintenance and utilities; 2) manufacturing engineering; 3) quality assurance and quality systems; and 4) packaging and dispatch. These four departments were selected based on the relevance towards change in working conditions in the context of an automobile industry (Cody, 2015; Lewchuk et al., 2001; Miglani, 2019). To get easy access to employees from these departments, a chain-referral method was utilised; however, it was ensured that there was an equal distribution of respondents from each department. In the chain-referral method, existing respondents provide referrals to recruit new respondents. The interviews were conducted online through Zoom and Teams, depending on the flexibility of the respondent. The primary reason for conducting online interviews was due to distance constraints because the company under consideration is in India, whereas the researcher is based in the United Kingdom. Moreover, due to the pandemic most of the staff were operating from home. However, respondents were advised to make themselves available in a room free of disturbance and distraction.

The interviews taken and the responses generated were completely unanimous from all the informants and the respondents and were recorded with their complete consent. The response provided by all the candidates has been discussed in terms of how they identify if an employee or a colleague of theirs is engaged within the organisation or not. Though conducting a pilot study is helpful for any research design, no pilot study was conducted for the study under consideration, primarily due to time constraints and narrow access to target respondents. There was fear that if prospective respondents were utilised for the pilot study, the researcher may have difficulty recruiting new respondents for the main study, which would have consumed additional time.

Based on the above analysis, the employees are usually engaged if they are completely productive in the organisation and they are providing positive results. They are well engaged if they enjoy working in the organisation and they help other colleagues whenever there is any help required. Engaged employees work towards the goals of the organisation and focus on achieving the deadlines. This is visible from the response of one of the respondents from the manufacturing engineering department, designated a Group Supervisor “*An employee or colleague seems to be engaged if they have been completely productive in the organisation and their effort has provided positive results. Moreover, if an employee is focused in the job they do and if they are happy with*

what they are doing, then it can be said that the employee is completely engaged in the organisation.”

In one of the other responses from a respondent from the maintenance and utilities department, designated an Assistant Manager *“If an employee is not engaged, he/she starts misleading the projects and has a very less interest towards work as they lack intent. Moreover, the employee also starts showing lack of communication, i.e., they become withdrawn and stops sharing anything with colleagues and managers about the work they are doing. A non-engaged employee also regularly complains about work and other people in the organisation. They also deliver very low quality of work and lack ownership of whatever they do.”* It can be fathomed that disengaged employees do not work hard and take very few initiatives in the organisation. Disengaged employees start misleading the projects and have a lack of intent. They also keep on complaining about the organisation and about the team which lowers the reputation and goodwill. This ultimately affects the organisation’s productivity and may lead to financial losses.

4.2.2 Strategies Used by Hero MotoCorp India for Employee Engagement Including Both Positive and Negative Effects

Interview Question: What strategies do you use to keep employees motivated?

This interview question helps to identify the strategies used by the management of Hero MotoCorp to keep their employees motivated. This would play a key factor in the research to draw analysis on the motivation level of employees in this organisation.

Analysis based on the above interviews states that there are various strategies used by Hero MotoCorp to keep employees motivated; one of the important ones is communication. Other strategies include setting realistic targets, providing development opportunities, rewards, appreciation, recognition, and performance awards. Trust also plays an important factor, and the organisation focuses on creating a friendly environment for their employees. This analysis can be interpreted from the response of one of the respondents from the quality assurance and quality systems department, designated a QC Head *“There are various strategies which we follow in the team to engage the employees. One strategy is to be always friendly with the team. Another one is providing incentives to the employees to recognise the work they have done. We provide regular*

trainings for professional growth of the people and take regular feedbacks to improve and excel further. We organise regular meetings to discuss any concerns and issues if the team has. This helps in identifying the existing problems within the team and resolving them accordingly. This indeed helps in helping to each other whenever anyone needs any kind of help.”

Interview Question: What strategies do you use to keep employees engaged in the organisation? You can mention multiple strategies.

Based on the response of one of the respondents from the packaging and dispatch department, designated as Manager “*We get to know the employees and their working style and provide them with tools and knowledge to succeed in the organisation. We give them timely updates on the performance of the company and how the company is doing at regular times. We give room to each employee to grow for their professional benefit. We recognise the team’s hard work they have done and support them whenever they need any help and reward them for their hard work. We widely encourage teamwork within our team and give opportunities to everyone in the team to lead from the front so that they can improve their leadership qualities.*”

The above interviews clearly define that to keep the employees motivated, the organisation provides regular trainings and gives enough tasks to complete in a particular time frame so that the employees are not overburdened. The organisation provides room to grow and identifies the hard work everyone is putting in to support them at their professional front. They follow fair practices and policies in the workplace and take regular feedback to resolve any issues.

Interview Question: What strategies mentioned in the previous question did not work or were not very effective? Why?

There were various strategies which did not work such as managing the workload, providing incentives, communicating the tasks, promotions and over trusting the employees as sometimes it is difficult to maintain transparency among the employees. This analysis can be fathomed from two different responses: 1) “*Sometimes it is difficult to implement transparency at a wider scale as it can offend some underperforming employees*”; 2) “*The strategy which sometimes did not work is leading from the front whenever required. This is because some of the members of the team take*

disadvantage of the freedom and leadership when provided to them. They usually do not work with the team and make other team members follow them.”

Interview Question: Are there any strategies used by the organisation to increase employee engagement? Were there any challenges? If yes, how were the challenges overcome?

Based on the response of the respondent from the quality assurance and quality systems department, designated a QC Officer *“The company organises parties and social gatherings every quarter so that the teams and colleagues get along with each other and know each other well. In these gatherings the achievements of the organisation are also discussed. The management also shares about the progress and how well the organisation is performing as compared to its market competitors. With this strategy, employees usually attend social gatherings for free food and drinks, but they also get to know about the important information which is shared.”*

There were many strategies used by the organisation to increase employee engagement. They provide regular trainings to the employees and they have an appraisal system in place to reward deserving employees. Regular team meetings are organised to discuss any issues and listen to any concerns if employees have them. There were a few challenges sometimes as there were some guidelines set by the organisation which had to be followed by the employees, but they disapproved of them.

Interview Question: When do you feel disengaged at work?

There are various instances when disengagement is felt such as when there is an excessive workload, and it is accomplished on it but there is no appreciation of it. When there is a lot of mental pressure and stress, the mind feels disengaged. Moreover, when the employees do not get paid for the overtime they do and lastly when there is no appreciation when they work out of office hours. This interpretation is primarily based on the response of a respondent from the manufacturing engineering department, designated as Assistant Engineer *“There is various instance when disengagement is felt such as when there is excessive workload, and it is accomplished on it but there is no appreciation of it. When there is a lot of mental pressure and stress, the mind feels to be disengaged. Another one is when we are not getting paid for the overwork we do and lastly when there is no appreciation when we work out of the office hours.”*

Interview Question: Did your organisation use any strategy/motivation to engage you again?

The organisation used various strategies such as providing appraisals and vouchers. Rewarding the people, providing professional development, and volunteering opportunities, recreational activities, playing stress relief games, social gatherings and taking feedback and resolving any issues. The above interpretation can be fathomed from a response from a respondent from the manufacturing engineering department, designated as Intern “*Yes, the organisation started rewarding people who performed well, and this encouraged other colleagues to participate and make the projects more interesting with their new ideas.*”

Interview Question: What strategies do the organisations use to renew employee engagement?

One of the respondents from the packaging and dispatch department, designated as Officer said, “*The organisation communicates deliberately and regularly to employees to renew their engagement. They invite employees for feedback and act on it. The organisation defines its goals and purpose and share it with the employees. They empower the employees and recognise the good work they do.*” Based on the above analysis, the organisation used various strategies to renew employee engagement such as social gatherings, parties, recreational activities, promotions, trainings, professional development opportunities and feedback.

4.2.3 Effects of Disengaged Employees on Personal Performance, Organisational Performance, and Co-workers in Hero MotoCorp India.

Interview Question: What is the effect of disengaged employees on organisational performance?

One of the respondents from the manufacturing engineering department, designated as Assistant Engineer said, “*In terms of organisational performance there is very less overall productivity in the project, the office environment becomes very dull and boring as it leads to more pressure on the other employees to work harder. There is less motivation across because of which there is a negative flow of energy overall. All of this leads to stricter deadlines and rules across the organisation for other employees and the pressure rises from both the clients end and the senior management end.*”

According to above interview and other interviews that were analysed, it has been found that as far as organisational performance is concerned, there is very less overall productivity in the project,

the office environment becomes very dull and boring as it leads to more pressure on the other employees to work harder. There is less motivation because of which there is a negative flow of energy overall. All of this leads to stricter deadlines and rules across the organisation for other employees and the pressure rises from both the client end and the senior management end.

Interview Question: What is the effect of disengaged employees on personal performance?

As per the response of one of the respondents from the maintenance and utilities department, designated as Officer, *“The personal performance of the employee is affected if an employee is disengaged as the personal growth becomes very slow after such negativity at work. The person always feels unhealthy and unsatisfied towards work and is not much reliable or trustworthy. The employee is also in complaining mode most of the times towards the work he does or towards the project/team he is working with and ultimately becomes an unreliable team member. The person also shows lack of leadership is does not portray effective team member skills as they are mostly ready with excuses towards all the work which is assigned to them and thus becomes a bad listener or seeker and becomes a liability for the company.”*

According to above interview and other interviews that were analysed, it has been found that the personal performance of the employee is affected if an employee is disengaged as personal growth becomes very slow after such negativity at work. The person always feels unhealthy and unsatisfied towards work and is not very reliable or trustworthy. The employee is also in complaining mode most of the time towards the work he does or towards the project/team he is working with and ultimately becomes an unreliable team member. The person also shows a lack of leadership and does not portray effective team member skills as they are mostly ready with excuses for all the work which is assigned to them and thus become a bad listener or seeker and become a liability for the company.

Interview Question: What is the effect of disengaged employees on co-workers?

One of the respondents from the packaging and dispatch department, designated as Officer said, *“The co-workers feel really disturbed when they have disengaged co-workers working along with them as the disengaged colleagues disrupt the whole working environment and try to have negative*

influence on the people working with them. This disrupts the whole environment, and the co-workers feel frustrated which effects the productivity of the project and impacts the whole organisation.”

According to above interview and other interviews that were analysed, it has been found that disengaged employees create a negative environment in the workplace, always keep on complaining and put additional pressure and workload on the co-workers. The workplace environment becomes negative and affects the productivity and growth of the organisation. The workplace also becomes uncomfortable for some of the co-workers to work and this disrupts the whole team mindset.

4.2.4 Roles of Trust and Leadership in Employee Engagement Including Behavioural and Attitude Changes

Interview Question: How does the attitude of an employee change when they are disengaged?

One of the respondents from the maintenance and utilities department, designated as Manager said, *“The employees have various changes in their attitude such as they have a social withdrawal from the society and have very less participation in any activity. They usually take a lot of breaks at work and find ways to be off from work by taking longer duration breaks. Their quality decreases for the work they do which results in low productivity at work. They also do not value time as they usually arrive late at work and are the first to leave.”*

According to above interview and other interviews that were analysed, it has been found that attitude changes drastically as the employees become irritated at work and do not socialise or engage much with their co-workers. The employees have very little interaction within the team and absenteeism starts increasing as well. They are lost in everything they do and become very rude whenever there are told off for anything. They also carry a carefree attitude and become rebellious if someone tries to explain them anything.

Interview Question: What role does trust play in influencing employee engagement? Why?

One of the respondents from the quality assurance and quality systems department, designated as QC Head said, *“Trust is one of the key factors in influencing employee engagement as building trust is firstly a difficult process and if the management manages to do that then the employees can*

take the organisation to greater heights. If an employee has trust on the management, they work more harder with a vision to achieve a goal which ultimately leads to achieving the goals of the organisation.”

According to above interview and other interviews that were analysed, it has been found that trust plays an important role as the employees feel connected and motivated. They also feel a sense of belonging leading to increased productivity and output. Employees also feel empathetic towards the team and their co-workers. Trust is one of the key factors in influencing employee engagement as building trust is firstly a difficult process and if the management manages to do that then the employees can take the organisation to greater heights. If an employee has trust in the management, they work harder with a vision to achieve a goal which ultimately leads to achieving the goals of the organisation.

Interview Question: How does leadership influence employee engagement?

One of the respondents from the packaging and dispatch department, designated as Manager said, *“Employee engagement is created by the organisation’s Leadership Body but organisational culture, also created by leaders, plays an important role for workers. Leaders have different ways and strategies to engage their employees. Very important aspect of employee commitment: trusting the leader and fully cooperating with the person who creates a safe environment for everyone. Workers become productive, adaptable, and easily set over-achieving goals because they work in a safe environment and trust their leaders. When workers make a mistake, they receive, instead of public criticism, support, and coaching. Thus, they are encouraged to make better decisions.”*

According to above interview and other interviews that were analysed, it has been found that it can be rightly said that leadership plays a crucial role in influencing the team and employees. A true leader supports and shows the right direction to the team and helps the organisation succeed in their goals. These factors build trust among the employees and they feel more secure and motivated and work towards achieving the goals of the organisation.

4.3 Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis is a procedure for analysing qualitative data. It is generally employed on the content of texts, for instance interview transcripts (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The researcher closely analyses the data to identify common patterns – topics, and themes of meaning that occur repeatedly in the text during analysis (Nowell et al., 2010). In the current research, a set of 14 questions were asked to 20 employees of Hero MotoCorp. These questions were based on four broad criteria: 1) effects of employee engagement in Hero MotoCorp India; 2) strategies used by Hero MotoCorp India for employee engagement including both positive and negative effects; 3) effects of disengaged employees on their personal performance, organisational performance, and co-workers in Hero MotoCorp India; and 4) roles of trust and leadership in employee engagement including behavioural and attitude changes. The thematic analysis of the responses received from the respondents gave rise to ten prominent themes that are listed below. Each theme is coded with a specific code that helps in identifying the respective respondents.

- 1) Productivity
- 2) Task
- 3) Communication
- 4) Monitoring
- 5) Goal
- 6) Recognition
- 7) Feedback
- 8) Promotion
- 9) Training
- 10) Trust

Hero MotoCorp is the largest manufacturer of two-wheelers in the world and the emerging themes from thematic analysis clearly are in line with the company's vision to remain the largest manufacturer. The emerging themes from the thematic analysis of Hero MotoCorp point to the direction of productivity, where performance is the centre of employee engagement. The majority of themes are directly or indirectly linked to production. The Hero MotoCorp has just inaugurated its new production unit in Andhra Pradesh. With this new unit, the Hero MotoCorp has six production units located at Dharuhera, Gurgaon, Neemrana, Haridwar, and Halol with a total

annual manufacturing capacity of 11.6 million units (*Economic Times*, 2020). This is in line with the company's vision of retaining its position as the largest manufacturer of two-wheelers in the world. Another major theme is the task; it points to the direction that management is highly task oriented to achieve the desired targets, and without task orientation it will be impossible to maintain the position as the world's largest manufacturer of two-wheelers. Next in line is communication; this theme shows the how different departments within Hero MotoCorp are interlinked with each other to achieve a common goal. For smooth execution, there is monitoring which is the next theme emerging out of thematic analyses. Hero MotoCorp follows a format of reward directly linked to an employee's effort, performance, dedication, and achievement of the company's target (Hero MotoCorp, 2020). Hero MotoCorp, on its company's profile, has specified that the company recognises the effort and commitment of its employees and this recognition is often given in the form of higher remuneration, promotion, bonuses, and career progression programmes. However, as per the conceptual framework, themes such as making meaning, enhancing well-being and enlivening energy are missing, hence mental and physical health are omitted, the importance of which is discussed in the next chapter. The factors which stand as the pillar of employee engagement are perceived as discouraging by some employees. For instance, employees often feel overburdened because of the tasks. There is a detailed discussion on this issue in the next chapter in relation to the ADKAR model of change management.

Conclusion

As per the data analysed, and the results gathered using interviews as part of the qualitative analysis from all the interviewees from Hero MotoCorp India, everyone has their own point of view on employee engagement and the effect of organisational changes on it. The analysis was done based on various factors which included the effects of employee engagement on the workforce, and the strategies used by Hero MotoCorp in engaging their employees to the fullest. Also, the analysis was done based on the effects of disengaged employees on the organisational performance, their own personal performance, and the co-workers they are working with. Finally, the analysis was also done based on attitude changes, behavioural changes, trust in employees and the influence of leadership on employees.

Even though the organisation is doing everything and has their incentives, support, rewards, and other recognitions in place, there are instances and situations when the employees feel disengaged and are not satisfied in the organisation which leads to low morale, less productivity and a negative workplace environment. Such missing factors in the organisational culture may not have much effect in the short run but do affect the organisational goals and the deadlines which leads to financial losses as well. One of the findings also made it clear that there are various strategies in place to reward the employees for their hard work and capabilities, since employees tend to feel demotivated as sometimes, they feel that they are undervalued. For instance, the employees are more engaged if they have a feeling of trust for the organisation and they believe that the leadership is strong. In such cases, employees feel more secured and are much more productive in terms of achieving organisational goals. More emphasis is put on the analysis in the next chapter of this thesis, which focuses on the findings from the research and the literature review.

CHAPTER FIVE: Discussion and Interpretation of Findings

5.1 Introduction

This section aims to reflect on the data analysed in the earlier areas in parallel to discuss the literature review on the impact of employee engagement on employee productivity and how it affects the overall organisation and the people working in that organisation. The discussions in this chapter and the findings primarily focus on how employee engagement affects Hero MotoCorp India's overall productivity and how it affects the people working in it. This chapter will also critically evaluate the analysis on organisational change and identify the role of employee engagement in initiating change. The study has assessed the effects of employee engagement and the strategies used by Hero MotoCorp India to increase employee engagement. The research and the discussion will also shine light on the impacts of disengaged employees on their performance, organisational performance, and co-workers. Further, the debate will reflect on the findings of the role of trust and leadership in employee engagement, including behavioural and changing workplace conditions.

The discussion focuses on the research conducted based on the interviews and the response from the respondents. The data presented and the study have been analysed based on the following four objectives and 20 in-depth interviews. The reactions were confirmed by 20 respondents who provided their responses based on an interview that consisted of 14 questions. The data were then gathered through these in-depth interviews and discussed, keeping in mind the objectives set for this research. Finally, significant conclusions have been drawn based on these analyses. All the data have been presented in serial order, meaning that objective one has been discussed first, followed by the 2nd, 3rd and 4th objectives.

5.2 Analysed Data Based on Objective 1

Research Objective 1: To critically evaluate the literature on organisational change and identify the role of employee engagement in initiating change.

Why is it essential for managers and organisations to change? Simply put, companies that do not introduce sufficient reform on time are unlikely to succeed. One explanation for the rapid change is that information and technology feed on each other, continuously producing new ideas at

exponential rates. In most organisations, change is unavoidable—and it is an essential component of development. When companies experience change measures, leaders often concentrate on setting out the proper steps they must take. Still, they also overlook the human dimension of change: guiding their team toward the new vision, changing culture, promoting learning and development, and interacting. One of the most critical aspects of successful management is change. Individuals, communities, and organisations engage in the coping process of shifting from their current state to the desired shape to counter complex intrinsic and extrinsic conditions that change current realities. To thrive in the global economy, companies are continually looking for ways to boost their competitiveness. More recent approaches have emphasised the role of employees in generating competitive advantage. According to research, engaged employees make a significant contribution to the company's financial bottom line.

Employee engagement is not limited to activities, games, and events. Employee engagement drives performance guided by employee engagement. Engaged employees take a holistic view of the organisation and understand their position, where they fit in and contribute. As a result, managers will be able to make better decisions. Companies that have a highly motivated workforce outperform their competitors. They gain more per share (EPS) and bounce back faster from recessions and financial setbacks. When it comes to development and creativity, commitment is a crucial differentiator. An employee engagement survey is essential for better understanding the company's needs. A satisfaction survey is not the same as this. Employee engagement can play an active role in initiating change in an organisation. The primary step is to generate employee engagement feedback. This can be done via an employee engagement survey. Employee engagement surveys were created to assess participants' success, strategic alignment, competency, and satisfaction. If engagement surveys are to be effective, they must be statistically checked and benchmarked against other organisations. Once the data are generated, management can analyse the data and implement necessary organisational changes to enhance employee engagement.

5.3 Analysed Data Based on Objective 2

Research Objective 2: To evaluate and identify the effects of employee engagement in Hero MotoCorp India.

The objective seeks to analyse the effects of engaged and disengaged employees within the organisation and identify if an employee is engaged or not, which will help provide solutions and recommendations in the future. In analysing the engagement and disengagement components, a conceptual framework is utilised as a guiding tool to give a structured approach.

In interviews conducted with around 20 respondents, all views on employee engagement in Hero MotoCorp India. They were all from different departments, and each department had a different style of working and employee engagement. Engaging employees plays a vital role in talent retention and increasing the productivity of the company. According to the report published by Forbes (2020), engaged employees are more likely to be motivated and respect the commitment set by the organisation. In addition, engaged employees positively affect the team and the people, whereas disengaged employees disrupt the organisation's environment.

Based on the available data, different facets of employee engagement came to the fore in the form of an interview. There were direct and indirect questions about employee engagement that were asked of employees of Hero MotoCorp. Based on the interviews conducted, an employee seems to be engaged if they are productive. Their efforts have provided positive results and increased productivity for the company, which is confirmed in the literature (Hanaysha, 2016). It was also analysed that most of the engaged employees in Hero MotoCorp felt happy and motivated in their job and about the work they are doing. These views are in line with the existing literature (Dalal et al., 2016). However, Hero MotoCorp is highly concentrated on productivity, which often works against the law of engagement, and employees feel the relationship as merely transactional with Hero MotoCorp. It is visible from thematic analysis how productivity, performance and goal are more utilised in each conversation.

Engaged employees said that they tend to help each other whenever there is any help needed. When engaged employees said they were inclined to take more outstanding initiatives at work, they assume more responsibility for aligning their needs with the organisation's goals. As stated by one of the respondents, engaged employees in their team are much more dedicated and busier with the work they do, which ultimately generates good results for the organisation. These employees also have a positive attitude at work while working on their tasks at hand. Truly engaged employees usually look beyond tasks and work towards a larger goal of an organisation to achieve it. Also,

they focus on keeping the organisation on top priority and want the organisation to achieve and succeed.

A respondent also shared that in their department, they use an online ticketing process updated daily, which helps the management track the progress of an employee and check if an employee is engaged or not. Also, enthusiastic employees have enhanced performance, have a positive experience for others, have a collaborative outlook, and look for ways to improve. One of the respondents also stated that if an employee spends less time on their phone or social media, they are more likely to be engaged in the company. As per the analysis from another respondent, an employee is engaged if they have excellent and open communication and present a positive experience for others. These employees look at the bigger picture and have a collaborative outlook. They also look for and share ways to improve while exceeding the goals and expectations while focusing on personal and professional development.

On the other hand, after analysing the responses based on the interviews conducted, disengaged employees in Hero MotoCorp are not hard workers and neither do they take any initiative or take fewer initiatives. Non-engaged employees also get more stressed about their work and the shifts they work in, and they also reflect a sense of lack of motivation in their work. In line with the responses recorded, non-engaged employees usually mislead the projects they work on and have significantly less interest in their work as they lack intent. The employees also show a lack of communication, which means that they become withdrawn and stop sharing anything with colleagues and managers about their work. In addition, these employees regularly complain about work and other people as they deliver low-quality work and lack ownership in whatever they do.

As confirmed in the existing literature by Abraham (2012), some of the non-engaged employees reflect poor communication, and a lack of networking skills. As a result, they do not participate in the company's tasks and spend less time in the organisation, affecting productivity. Non-engaged employees also miss deadlines, lack apathy, lack communication skills, keep complaining regularly, and have a very low quality of work.

5.4 Analysed Data Based on Objective 3

Research Objective 3: To identify the strategies used by Hero MotoCorp India for employee engagement.

This objective seeks to analyse the strategies to engage all those employees who are not involved in the organisation. To understand the results, analysis was drawn from multiple respondents who belonged to various teams and departments in the organisation. Thus, we have an overview of different types of personnel across the organisation.

Also, this objective assists in understanding the strategies Hero MotoCorp use to keep their employees motivated in the organisation. Moreover, it will also draw conclusions on the engagement strategies, including which ones are effective and not. Finally, it will also give the author an understanding of the strategies used to increase employee engagement and, if the employees feel demotivated, consider how does organisation re-engages them.

According to the respondents who were interviewed from various departments, it has been found that Hero MotoCorp India employs multiple strategies in terms of employee engagement. From the responses recorded of the respondents, it has been found that the critical process is to communicate the goals clearly to all the employees working in Hero MotoCorp. It also includes setting up appropriate tasks with realistic targets within a specific timeframe for the employees. Providing development opportunities is also one of the key strategies to keep employees motivated as it helps in both the professional and personal development of an employee. Appreciating the performance and work done by an employee is another strategy to keep them engaged. Creating a collaborative culture in the office space is also an essential strategy that the organisation follows. Hero MotoCorp also lets the employees feel and understand that they trust their employees, giving them a sense of belonging and responsibility. Another strategy which the organisation uses is to set smaller weekly goals for the employees. The organisation also motivates the employees by giving them a purpose in whatever they do by being transparent, asking questions, and giving feedback. The company maintains a friendly working environment and maintains a close relationship with the employees. They also acknowledge the achievements made by the employees and reward them for their successes. The company defines a career path for all the employees, making them competitive and motivating them to go beyond the ordinary and achieve higher goals. The company also has a zero-discrimination policy and follows fair working policies. The teams also have regular fun events and parties for the employees to socialise within the group, creating healthy relationships.

Hero MotoCorp also provides regular training for professional growth and organises regular meetings to identify issues and resolve them. The organisation also conducts motivational talks to build confidence among employees and have employee of the month contests to have a competitive spirit. Hero MotoCorp also has various strategies to keep the employees engaged, such as organising regular training and taking employees' feedback. The organisation gets to know the employees and their working style and provides them with tools and knowledge to succeed. They also give them timely updates on the company's performance and how it is doing at regular times. They offer room for every employee to grow for their professional benefit. They recognise the team's hard work and support them whenever they need any help, and reward them for their hard work. The organisation widely encourages teamwork within the team and gives everyone in the group a chance to lead from the front to improve their leadership qualities. The management has made the workplace a pleasant and comfortable place to work. They widely encourage being respectful to others, being honest and supportive to everyone in the team. They also offer employee rewards whenever someone has gone beyond to achieve something. The organisation also provides coaching to the employees for success, providing the employees with the right tools they need to work, engaging the high potential employees into dedicated organisational tasks, and clearly defining their goals.

Though Hero MotoCorp uses various strategies for employee engagement, many methods did not work as well. Managing the workload of the employees was sometimes tricky due to untimely deadlines. Sometimes the training which is provided theoretically does not help much in the practical world. Also, leading from the front was too much success as some team members take advantage of the freedom and leadership when provided to them. They usually do not work with the team and make other team members follow them. Providing incentives sometimes does not work as some employees think the incentives are underrated but must follow the company guidelines. As a result, the morale is sometimes down for the employees. Also, promoting employees or providing a promotion is ineffective as the results are not seen immediately. Sometimes over trusting the employees is not very practical because you rely on them, which has led to projects' failure. According to one of the interviewees, designating with authority does not always work because many people do not work as a team. They point out flaws in other people due to their dislikes or personal issues.

Although the organisation incorporated various strategies, there were many instances when the employees felt disengaged at work. There were multiple instances of when disengagement has been handled, such as when there is an excessive workload, and it is accomplished on it, but there is no appreciation. When there is a lot of mental pressure and stress, the mind becomes disengaged. Also, when the employees are not getting paid for the overwork they do and lastly when there is no appreciation when the employees work out of the office hours. The employees do not feel engaged when there is poor communication between the people in the team and when there are regular breaks from the routine and complacency. Disengagement is also felt when the work and tasks are too easy to follow or when there are no challenges and no competition with other colleagues within the team. Another respondent stated that they feel disengaged when there is a lack of personal growth, training, and appreciation for their work. The employees are also disengaged when all the hard work and good work they do is not appreciated. Management behaviours towards subordinates make a difference. If managers do not show concern and care towards the employees, then the environment does not feel friendly, and thus the employees feel disengaged.

According to some of the employees, some of the departments used some strategies to re-engage the employees who felt disengaged. The organisation provided appraisals and vouchers as a gesture to boost motivation. They rewarded people who performed well and encouraged other colleagues to participate and make the project more enjoyable with their new ideas. Another interviewee mentioned that the managers organised and coordinated volunteering opportunities and prioritised mental and physical health. The management organised some stress relief games and motivational speech classes. They also started celebrating birthdays and organised team parties from time to time. The project managers also rotated working areas for employees and tried to give new tasks to everyone. The company provides:

- New e-learning platforms
- Training
- From time to time, health learning quiz competitions to motivate employees and offer rewards and incentives

Motivation is also provided by providing regular training and creating a friendly work environment for everyone. The organisation also tries to resolve all the issues that employees face by taking into account all their queries and providing frequent training to everyone. Furthermore, as per an interviewee, the organisation asks the employees about their hobbies and what they are good at, which lifts the employees' mood and they are asked to showcase their hobby in front of everyone.

In addition to re-engaging employees, there are many strategies used according to the interviewees to renew employee engagement. As per one of the interviewees, the organisation organises office parties, provides gift vouchers, and organises office outings regularly. They also effectively divide the workload, have created recreational environments, and manage training sessions for all the employees. The team asks for feedback, holds regular social gatherings, provides a friendly and transparent working environment, and clarifies targets and goals for everyone. The organisation identifies top performers and rewards the achievers. An interviewee also mentioned that the management has made changes in the employee policies and increased the annual increments in the salary for employees. There are outstation trips organised for all the employees in addition to appraisals. The organisation communicates deliberately and regularly to employees to renew their engagement. They invite employees for feedback and act on it. The organisation defines its goals and purpose and shares them with the employees. They empower the employees and recognise the excellent work they do. They try to make employees study past projects to get intel on the shortcomings or positive points on that project that can help in the future. They also started IMAD awards which means I make a Difference (Hero MotoCorp, 2020). They usually implement annual reward schemes and provide incentives to deserving employees. They typically organise seminars to motivate and renew employee engagement. They have a poll session and a suggestion box where the employees can drop in their suggestions. The company communicates deliberately and regularly, invests in wellbeing, invites feedback – and acts on it. It defines the organisation's purpose and shares it, and empowers the people to recognise good work.

5.5 Analysed Data Based on Objective 4

Research Objective 4: To examine the effects of disengaged employees on their performance, organisational performance, and co-workers in Hero MotoCorp India.

This is one of the most important objectives of this study. It helps us analyse and identify the effects of non-engaging and demotivated employees on performance, the overall performance of the organisation, and the effects on co-worker's performance in Hero MotoCorp India.

In terms of the effects of disengaged employees on organisational performance, all the interviewees had different opinions based on their experience and time. According to one of the interviewees, there is very little overall productivity in the project in terms of organisational performance. The office environment becomes dull as it leads to more pressure on the other employees to work harder. There is less motivation across because of which there is a negative flow of energy overall. All of this leads to stricter deadlines and rules across the organisation for other employees, and the pressure rises from both the client's end and the senior management end. It impacts the primary goal of the organisation or project on which the whole team is working. It affects the targets set by the organisation, which becomes difficult to meet. There is a lack of progress on the overall project, which ultimately leads to the team's poor performance. Disengaged employees are more likely to work hard or meet expectations for their role, decreasing overall productivity. Another interviewee stated that a disengaged workforce directly negatively impacts the customer experience. There is a decrease in morale and company culture because of a disengaged mindset. The disengaged people are less likely to work hard as they usually become demotivated and thus do not meet any targets or expectations of their roles. These kinds of employees cause more errors and defects in their work, impacting the whole project. Disengaged employees work slowly and slow down the organisation's progress as they do not work as per their full potential and thus impact customer service as well. Due to disengaged employees, the organisations usually suffer substantial financial losses as productivity goes down and there is not much motivation left. Actively disengaged employees cause disruption and dissatisfaction within the company, leading to less involvement in the projects and ultimately affecting the organisation's overall productivity. These types of employees leave a negative impact on the working environment and the whole team working in that environment which impacts the performance of the employees. The organisation's reputation is affected due to disengaged employees as the organisation struggles to achieve their goals leading to dissatisfied customers and clients. There are project delays, and the organisation cannot meet the expected deadlines due to the degradation of the qualitative work that employees do. According to another interviewee, disengaged

employees create a hostile working environment in the team which affects the people working in the team as the morale goes down and there is a lack of motivation. It also leads to clashes within the workspace and causes delivery delays in projects. The Service Level Agreement with the client can be affected, leading to monetary or goodwill loss for the organisation. The disengaged employees' lower organisational efficiency and demoralise the team. They have poor productivity and have more rejections towards their work, and usually do not achieve targets on time. Disengaged employees cause attrition which means that the strength and effectiveness of the organisation are reduced by sustained pressure. Disengaged employees are less likely to work hard, feel motivated, or meet expectations for their role, and they cause more errors and defects in work performance. Disengagement costs money.

As per the analysis drawn from the interviewees, the author did not reflect on the effects of non-engaged employees on personal performance. According to an interviewee, the employee's performance is affected if disengaged as personal growth becomes very slow after such negativity at work. The person always feels unhealthy and unsatisfied about work and is not very reliable or trustworthy. Most of the time, the employee is also in complaining mode about the work he does or towards the project/team he is working with and ultimately becomes an unreliable team member. The person also shows a lack of leadership and does not portray practical team member skills. They are primarily ready with excuses towards all the work assigned to them and thus become a lousy listener or seeker and become a liability for the company. Another interviewee stated that the stress levels of the employee increase, which leads to low productivity and output for the organisation. It ultimately impacts the overall development of the employee in terms of their personal development and growth. The employee tends to not get involved in team-building activities. They become very slow and lazy at work which increases the errors in everything they do and affects their overall performance in the team. The employee keeps on complaining about everything in the group, whether it is about the work they do or about the organisation. They become very disturbing for the whole team and lower their growth and self-development. Disengaged employees start making errors in the work they do and get stressed about everything. These employees cannot provide adequate customer service and client services and are not enthusiastic or happy about their work, which brings down their personal growth and goodwill.

The employees disrupt the workspace environment, which ultimately lowers the productivity of the project and downgrades team-mates' performance.

Another respondent stated that personal performance is affected if employees are disengaged and create a lack of enthusiasm among employees, which lowers the energy levels. If the employees are disengaged, their accuracy at work and the sharpness in evaluating tasks start decreasing, and the performance is affected, which is not good in the long run. Moreover, they mentioned that disengaged employees are less likely to work hard as they are usually demotivated to do anything. Furthermore, the employees' morale is also impacted and decreased, and their confidence level goes down as well. The employee's performance is impacted if an employee is disengaged as the energy levels are firstly down. It, in turn, starts affecting the project, and the employee has very little input, which directly affects their personal growth and development, and their productivity sees a drastic downfall. It affects team leaders and bosses badly, and when assessed, it affects their incentives and other benefits. They are less likely to work hard, focus on looking for a new job, and are a financial loss to the organisation. Disengaged employees are looking for new jobs or opportunities, feel less motivated and rarely expect other expectations. They have a lack of interest at work which leads to decreased efficiency and productivity.

In terms of the effects of disengaged employees on their co-workers, various analyses are drawn based on the interviews conducted, and the interviewees had different opinions on this. According to one of them, when the colleagues start feeling disengaged, there is a direct effect on the co-workers as this puts a lot of additional pressure on them. Moreover, the office environment becomes very dull as there is a negative influence, which creates additional workload for the co-workers. Also, there are conflicts within the team as the disengagement creates problems between the co-workers. Finally, disengaged employees make 100 times more errors than their engaged colleagues, which means a lot of productivity is lost.

Furthermore, disengaged employees generally spend less time working as they are involved in conversations and chats, take more breaks, procrastinate, spend time on social media, etc. So, this all affects the performance of the co-workers as well. Disengaged employees are usually known for their bad behaviour. They disrupt and destroy the environment and atmosphere of a good workplace for the co-workers working alongside. Disengaged employees disturb the whole

working environment and make co-workers uncomfortable, which impacts the overall team and project. As per another interviewee, the co-workers feel demotivated if they have disengaged colleagues in the team because they think that they do not have enough support from their colleagues. Disengaged employees make the co-workers feel uncomfortable and less motivated to engage and work. Co-workers are directly affected by disengaged employees. Their mindset makes them lose track of projects and impact the healthy habits at work due to the disengaged workforce. Also, while disengaged employees tend to look out for jobs outside the organisation, they influence other team members and co-workers who accompany them and sometimes leave the organisation, which decreases the organisation's productivity. Disengaged employees are less likely to work hard, which reduces the morale of the whole team and thus, there is underperformance noticed by everyone. The co-workers feel discomfort working with the disengaged employees as their discomfort increases and the co-workers start pointing out personally to their colleagues. Disengaged employees can negatively impact the workplace as the co-workers are less likely to work hard and ultimately feel demotivated. The co-workers feel disturbed when they have disengaged co-workers working along with them as the disengaged colleagues disrupt the whole working environment and try to have a negative influence on the people working with them. It disrupts the entire environment, and the co-workers feel frustrated, which affects the project's productivity and impacts the whole organisation. The morale of the team decreases, and they get burdened because of the extra work. The co-workers feel demotivated and usually have heated arguments with their colleagues. Sometimes disengaged employees engage in groupism with their co-workers and spread negativity across the whole organisation. It has adverse effects on collaboration, workplace ethics, and group work efficiency, which negatively affects the co-workers and their productivity.

5.6 Analysed Data Based on Objective 5.

Research Objective 5: To develop a conceptual framework on employee engagement based on employee engagement elements and changing workplace conditions at Hero MotoCorp.

This objective seeks to analyse the conceptual framework on employee engagement which focuses on significant factors such as trust, leadership, and the impact of changing workplace conditions on the employees and how these affect the productivity and growth of the organisation, including the productivity of the people working at Hero MotoCorp India. With the assistance of the above-

analysed objectives and Objective no 5, below is the conceptual framework of the impact of changing workplace conditions and employee engagement on employee productivity in the context of Hero MotoCorp India.

Figure 5 Practised engagement and changing workplace components in Hero MotoCorp

Source: (Hiatt 2006; Zinger 2019)

In the case of Hero MotoCorp, when it comes to changes in workplace conditions, employees look up to trust and leadership to overcome the effects of change. Concerning the workplace changes among the employees when they feel disengaged, all the interviewees had opinions about their experience working within different teams at Hero MotoCorp India. One interviewee stated that change in workplace conditions impacts the employees and often leads to irritation at work. Employees tend not to socialise or engage much with their co-workers. It affects their behaviour, and they are lost in change, and they tend to become very rude whenever there are told off for anything. They also carry a carefree attitude and become rebellious if someone tries to explain anything. Another interviewee mentioned that disengaged employees do not see any growth opportunities due to sudden changes in changing workplace conditions. Due to drastic change,

there is a lack of curiosity to learn new things, making them think that there is less growth as a better professional. The employees have various changes in their attitude, such as they have social withdrawal from society and have significantly less participation in any activity. They usually take many breaks at work and find ways to be off work by taking breaks of a longer duration. Their quality decreases for the work they do, which results in low productivity at work. They also do not value time as they usually arrive late at work and are the first to leave. These types of employees generally talk very little and have very little interaction with anyone. Whenever they talk, they either speak negatively or talk about some problem and find ways not to work. They also complain most of the time about the company policies and the senior staff or co-workers. They have a moody attitude and are not easy to go to people with unstable behaviour at work. Actively disengaged employees make themselves known through their bad moods. They stop caring about their place and position in the company. They watch out for employees undermining others, are constantly criticising more than contributing, and consistently participate in toxic workplace gossip. Disengaged employees feel lonely most of the time and have a very negative effect on the workplace. These types of employees have increased absenteeism and ignore standard working timings of the company. Their productivity and quality of work take a downturn most of the time, and they lack the enthusiasm to meet targets and tasks. Disengaged employees usually start interfering in the creation of others and start wasting time as well. They tend to disturb and distract others from the work they do. The changes in attitude are primarily visible in how they socialise with people as they are more about complaining than being productive at work. They are usually a negative influence on everyone in the organisation and always try to ruin the organisation's reputation. The employee becomes disinterested and starts blaming others for their mistakes. They do not act responsibly or appropriately; they sometimes show a bad attitude, they feel left out in the company and try to act out. Lack of interest leads to less innovation and no new ideas, which decreases productivity.

The interviewees focused on the trust factor and mentioned that it is one of the most critical aspects of working within a team. According to one of the interviewees, employees who trust their organisations tend to share information and work well in groups. These employees also have higher levels of job satisfaction, are more likely to recommend their employer to others and are less likely to leave the organisation. The employees feel connected and motivated and have a sense of

belonging, leading to increased productivity and output. Employees also feel empathetic towards the team and their co-workers. Putting trust in employees gives them confidence, and they put extra effort into their work. Another respondent mentioned that trust plays a crucial role in influencing employee engagement as it makes them work hard, and they rely on the management and trust whatever they say or do. Employees who feel trusted are empowered to get work done to the best of their ability leading to increased productivity and growth. If the management shows trust in employees and makes them understand that they depend on them, they would fill the shoes and work much harder than anyone can imagine. A vote of confidence goes a long way. One of the interviewees quoted, "Let them know you trust them to do the best job possible and they will disappoint the company". Trust plays a huge role as it is a significant factor in engagement because it makes employees comfortable with working conditions and working collaboratively. Trust plays a vital role in influencing employee engagement by bringing change and new ways to motivate them by providing career growth opportunities and training. It gives them the confidence to keep things in between the concerned persons and assurance that they can perform and meet the targets. When employees trust their employers or management, they are much more likely to work together towards achieving the same ultimate business goals and deadlines. Trust is one of the critical factors in influencing employee engagement, as building trust is a complex process. If the management manages to do that, then the employees can take the organisation to greater heights. If an employee trusts the administration, they work harder with a vision to achieve a goal, which ultimately leads to achieving the organisation's goals. It is the leading role as, if an employee can trust the organisation and their team, then they will communicate correctly, getting them engaged and caught up with the team. If a workplace can foster a strong sense of trust within their organisation, they can see several benefits, including increased staff productivity, improved morale amongst employees and staff, the ability to work more effectively as a team rather than as individuals. Employees who feel trusted are empowered to get work done to their best ability. They know they will be supported in learning what they do not know and optimising what they know best. Employees who feel trusted are empowered to get work done to their best ability. Trust plays a very important role as it is the foundation of any relationship, which greatly impacts employee-to-employee relationships.

Most of the interviewees conducted on leadership had strong opinions about the importance of leadership in the success of both the organisation and the employees working in the organisation. A critical look at the findings from the interviews states that leadership plays a vital role as employees feel motivated, leading to high satisfaction levels and increased productivity. Employees genuinely feel connected and satisfied when the leadership in the organisation is effective. A respondent stated that visionary leaders who create a culture of engagement maintain employee trust, drive optimal productivity levels, increase overall satisfaction and retention, and position the company for success. It is in these times that employees look to organisational leaders for guidance. Leadership is the most crucial key through which there can be increased employee engagement. A leader listens to the thoughts and opinions of all employees and acts on them. The organisation's leadership body creates employee engagement, but leaders also create an organisational culture that plays a vital role for workers. Leaders have different ways and strategies to engage their employees. A very important aspect of employee commitment is trusting the leader and fully cooperating with the person who creates a safe environment for everyone. Workers become productive, adaptable, and quickly set over-achieving goals because they work in a safe environment and trust their leaders. If workers make a mistake, they receive, instead of public criticism, support, and coaching. Thus, they are encouraged to make better decisions. Another respondent stated that leadership provides a job to inspire and motivate others to work to the very best of their abilities. Being an effective leader demands several qualities and characteristics that encourage those around them to succeed. With good leadership, the leaders act as role models for the employees and employees can look up to the leaders who lead by example. An excellent, engaging leader has more productive and interested employees. Good leadership influences the employees to work effectively as the proper guidance is given to them, making them feel secure. Leadership has a positive influence on the employees; it is like an army fighting for the king. Even if the king is not there, the military will fight for him.

Similarly, with excellent leadership, the employees produce much productivity even if the leaders are away for some time. A leader always engages all the employees and keeps the team together as they understand the team's potential and motivate them to work beyond their potential. Leadership influences effective communication among the employees, and efficient managerial styles always build trust and respect, which is essential for a positive approach. Effective

leadership plays a vital role in influencing employee engagement as a good leader would always bind the team and support them in everything they do. A good leader would always motivate the employees to work harder and always take responsibility for failures. It creates a positive environment in the team, and the employees' morale is boosted to work together and take the organisation to greater heights. It influences them significantly as proper leadership will keep the team morale high and motivate them to work correctly. One of the interviewees stated a vital point: leadership can sometimes play a negative role as the employee could feel dominated by the leader in the team. Leadership in an organisation needs to maintain employee trust, drive optimal productivity levels, increase overall satisfaction and retention, and position the company for success. Workers become productive, adaptable, and quickly set over-achieving goals because they work in a safe environment and trust their leaders.

5.7 Analysed Data Based on Objective 6

Research Objective 6: To recommend a solution based on the findings for developing employee engagement programmes to enhance the process of organisational change.

Objective 6 is focused on the conclusion and recommendations of the thesis on the impact of changing workplace conditions and employee engagement on employee productivity in the context of Hero MotoCorp India

5.7.1 Conclusion

Hero MotoCorp is ranked the single largest manufacturer of two-wheeler motorcycles in the world. Hero MotoCorp started as Hero cycles in 1956, and by 1975, it had become the largest manufacturer of bicycles in India (NDTV, 2021). In 1984, it decided to take a joint venture route, entered a contract with the Honda Motor Company of Japan, and formed Hero Honda Motor Limited. Finally, on December 16, 2010, the Hero Group and Honda Motor Co. decided to dissolve their partnership, bringing to a close one of the most successful joint ventures in the world of the automobile industry (DNA, 2010). Hero Group's strategy is for market development, as the single largest manufacturer of two-wheeler motorcycle companies in the world could not export its products to international markets. It was one of the contentious issues which led the company to end the relationship with Honda Motors. As per the joint venture terms, Hero Group could only sell its two-wheelers to Sri Lanka and Nepal. It can be implicated that the Hero Group had peaked

in the Indian market, and further market penetration was becoming cumbersome. Hence, the Hero Group wanted to go for market development, but the agreement with Honda Motors was a significant obstacle.

Moreover, there was excessive reliance on Honda Motors technology, and Hero MotoCorp wanted to move away from this dependence. Additionally, several aberrations started emerging in the joint venture. For instance, Honda's reluctance to freely share technology and high royalties charged by Honda Motors hurt the Hero Group's vision.

It is a dual transition for Hero MotoCorp, where the organisation is going solo and intends to expand internationally, where the company is entering into new agreements and partnerships. Hero MotoCorp has already bought a 49.2% stake in US-based performance (race) motorcycle maker Erik Buell Racing (EBR) for \$25 million (nearly Rs 150 crore) (LiveMint, 2013). Hero MotoCorp has also sent feelers to Harley Davidson for a partnership and has entered a strategic partnership with the Italian brand Ducati. These changes have given a unique opportunity to analyse the impact of changing workplace conditions and employee engagement on employee productivity. After the breakup with Honda Motors, Hero MotoCorp, implemented numerous changes in the work setting because previously parameters of workplace conditions were dominated by Honda Motors. The study utilised the Zinger employee engagement model to analyse employee engagement, which has its own set of advantages compared to another engagement model. For instance, the Boston model of employee engagement is culture focused. In contrast, the Zinger employee engagement model works on ten major drivers that management should follow, which gives greater scope for evaluating employee engagement and its impact on employee productivity. To evaluate change in Hero MotoCorp, the study has utilised the ADKAR change management model, which focuses on factors driving personal change.

The study decided to take an interpretive approach to the impact of changing workplace conditions and employee engagement on employee productivity in Hero MotoCorp India. The interpretive approach has the unique advantage of exploring hidden reasons behind complex constructs like engagement. To generate the data, 20 employees of Hero MotoCorp were interviewed with a set of 14 questions. These questions were later analysed based on a set of six objectives of the study. The thematic analyses of the generated interview content revealed that employee engagement in

Hero MotoCorp is concentrated on productivity. In the case of changing workplace conditions, employees look towards leadership and trust to manage change. The study has come up with an integrated framework based on the findings and theoretical underpinning of the Zinger model of engagement and ADKAR model of change to analyse the impact of changing workplace conditions

and employee engagement on employee productivity in the context of Hero MotoCorp India.

Figure 6 Integrated conceptual framework.

Source: (Hiatt 2006; Zinger 2019)

Based on the analyses of the Hero MotoCorp's employee data, the study has come up with its own set of recommendations that are discussed below.

5.7.2 Recommendations

The study has analysed the impact of changing workplace conditions and employee engagement on employee productivity in the context of Hero MotoCorp India. The analyses of the generated data and conceptual framework acted as a guiding tool throughout the research. The study has developed an improvised version of the conceptual model for Hero MotoCorp employee productivity, focusing on changing workplace conditions and employee engagement. Post analyses of the generated data and juxtaposing them with the conceptual framework, it was observed that there were facets that were missing in employee engagement components in Hero MotoCorp. Employee engagement is concentrated on productivity and growth. Hence, components that enliven energy, enhance well-being, and make meaning are completely absent. Hero MotoCorp should focus on these factors. 1) Enlivening energy: Hero MotoCorp should create a department within human resources that focuses on employee energy generation because the primary resource of engagement is energy. The input of energy is required to drive engagement, and genuine engagement adds to energy. Energy comes in different forms: organisational, mental, physical, spiritual, and emotional. Hero MotoCorp can launch specific programmes that cater to each form of energy; for instance, it could introduce a programme related to yoga intended to improve mental, physical, spiritual, and emotional energies. Hero MotoCorp could introduce small functional tasks such as introducing more networking platforms within Hero MotoCorp, allowing employees to go for 10-minute brisk walks and encouraging employees to ask others questions. Enlivening energy is a powerful implicit component of employee engagement influencing employee productivity. 2) Enhancing well-being: well-being is the state of being comfortable, healthy, or happy. Well-being is an essential co-efficient of the long sustainable growth of a company. Hence Hero MotoCorp should focus on the well-being of its employees, which is an intrinsic quality. Hero MotoCorp should put systems in place to eradicate lethal workplace environments and enrich respect and mutuality. Taking a cue from Tom Rath's book, *Well-being: The Five Essential Elements*, Hero MotoCorp can implement the recommendation to enhance the well-being of their employees. Hero MotoCorp can tailor-make initiatives based on the five essential elements: authenticity of relationship, safety of financial component, energy of physical health, and the pleasure taken in

contributing towards society. Hero, MotoCorp can devise a method to regularly check employees' emotional and physical status and take appropriate steps where required. 3) Making meaning: this is an essential component in the engagement of employees. For work to augment and enrich individuals, it must be sensible and meaningful. Employees who ask the question "why" about work tend to infuse a sense of powerful intrinsic motivation. Hero MotoCorp can create an employee development programme to enhance engagement based on the list of eight approaches to build meaningful work: 1) defeat how with why; 2) develop ample leadership whys; 3) bridge meaning, squeeze money; 4) imbibe with purpose, desire, mastery, aspiration, autonomy; 5) master your charm; 6) rework your principles and values as affirmations; 7) lead on reason; 8) double your "Work as Meaning Inventory" (WAMI). Hero MotoCorp should seek out feedback based on "Work as Meaning Inventory", a 10-item scale Likert scale, a very well-validated scale, investigating meaning developing at work and how the work contributes to the greater good.

In the case of changing workplace conditions on employee productivity in Hero MotoCorp, employees are dependent on two major factors: leadership and trust. Therefore, the theoretical model utilised to analyse changing workplace components is the ADKAR model of change.

5.7.3 Research Limitations

One of the critical limitations of the research under consideration is the deployment of only a qualitative methodology. Even though this methodology adds depth to the research conclusions, it limits the accuracy and authenticity of the data because of the lack of empirical and statistical backup. Coupled with this, the research sample size under consideration is also tiny, meaning that it is not possible to generalise the conclusions. The data collected from a limited number of respondents is extended over a large population. Moreover, the data were collected through online interviews, where nonverbal communication is hard to pick up on. In face-to-face communication, verbal content makes up 7%, paralanguage (tone, volume) makes up 38%, and body language makes up 55% (Hess, 2016). Hence, the real essence of the interview is lost in an online format. The interviews were conducted online due to distance constraints and pandemic situations, which are the study's major limitations. Apart from that, as the researcher did not use sophisticated data analysis tools, such as NVivo, the quality of analysis could have been compromised, which is also one of the critical limitations of the research under consideration (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

5.7.4 Future Research

The research under consideration focuses on the automobile sector and further narrows down on a two-wheeler company. Hence the findings cannot be generalised. Thus, there is a necessity to conduct similar research on different companies before generalising the results. Furthermore, the sample is minuscule; hence, future analysis should be performed with a larger sample size because a small sample size prevents the findings from being extrapolated.

A study by Roscigno (2019) has suggested that discrimination and sexual harassment impact the workplace environment, further impacting productivity and profitability. However, the study could not find any literature in the case of the automobile sector about discrimination and sexual harassment factors. Hence future research should focus on discrimination and sexual harassment factors in the automobile sector.

As per the finding by Paul et al., (2009), competition can severely impact mental health. For example, the current global landscape is highly competitive for the automobile industry, and this competition looks set to increase, which may have a significant toll on employees' mental health (Mohammad Nazir & Shavarebi, 2019). Hence, future research should focus on employees' mental health, looking for ways to mitigate the effects of depression, anxiety, stress, and self-harm arising from competition (Paul et al., 2009). In addition, there is also enormous scope to conduct intervention studies where meditation and focus-based training can be applied to mitigate the effects, as mentioned earlier, of competition.

References

Abraham, S., 2012. Job Satisfaction as an Antecedent to Employee Engagement. *SIES Journal of Management*, 8(2).

Acemoglu, D., 2012. Introduction to economic growth. *Journal of economic theory*, 147(2), pp.545-550.

Agnew, T., & Royal, M. (2011). *The Enemy of Engagement* (1st ed., pp. 78-88). [London]: AMACOM Books.

Ajala, E.M., 2012. The influence of workplace environment on workers' welfare, performance and productivity. *The African Symposium*.

ALDamoe, F.M.A., Yazam, M. and Ahmid, K.B., 2012. The mediating effect of HRM outcomes (employee retention) on the relationship between HRM practices and organisational performance. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 2(1), p.75.

Ali, A.Y.S., Ali, A.A. and Adan, A.A., 2013. Working conditions and employees' productivity in manufacturing companies in sub-Saharan African context: Case of Somalia. *Educational Research International*, 2(2), pp.67-78.

Ali, A.Y.S., Ali, A.A. and Adan, A.A., 2013. Working conditions and employees' productivity in manufacturing companies in sub-Saharan African context: Case of Somalia. *Educational Research International*, 2(2), pp.67-78.

Ali, A.Y.S., Ali, A.A. and Adan, A.A., 2013. Working conditions and employees' productivity in manufacturing companies in sub-Saharan African context: Case of Somalia. *Educational Research International*, 2(2), pp.67-78.

AL-Qahtani, B.J., 2010, January. Improving Safety Behavior Using the ADKAR Model. In the Middle East Health, Safety, Security, and Environment Conference and Exhibition. Society of Petroleum Engineers.

Andrew, O.C. and Sofian, S., 2012. Individual factors and work outcomes of employee engagement. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 40, pp.498-508.

Anitha, J., 2014. Determinants of employee engagement and their impact on employee performance. *International journal of productivity and performance management*, 63(3), p.308.

Ansoff Matrix. (2015). Retrieved 16 November 2020, from <http://ansoffmatrix.com/>

Ariely, D. and Jones, S., (2008). *Predictably irrational*. 1st ed. New York: Harper Audio, pp.55-59.

Bajpai, N., 2011. *Business research methods*. Pearson Education India.

Bakker, A.B. and Demerouti, E., 2014. Job demands–resources theory. *Wellbeing: A complete reference guide*, pp.1-28.

Bill, G. (2007). *True North* (2nd ed., pp. 33-37). California: John Wiley & Sons.

Braun, V., Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3, 77–101. doi:10.1191/1478088706qp063oa

Brun, J., & Cooper, C. (2009). *Missing Pieces 7 Ways to Improve Employee Well-Being and Organizational Effectiveness* (3rd ed., pp. 27-29). London: Palgrave Macmillan.

Bruch, H. and Vogel, B., (2011). *Fully charged : how great leaders boost their organization's energy and ignite high performance*. 1st ed. Boston: Harvard Business Review, pp.77-79.

Bryman, A. and Bell, E., 2015. *Business research methods*. Oxford University Press, USA.

Business Today. (2020). Why implementing Industry 4.0 is becoming an imperative. Available: <https://www.businesstoday.in/current/economy-politics/why-implementing-industry-4-is-becoming-an-imperative/story/286721.html>. Last accessed 1st March 2020.

Business Standard. (2020). HERO MOTOCORP LTD. (HEROMOTOCO) - DIRECTOR REPORT. Available: <https://www.business-standard.com/company/hero-motocorp-237/annual-report/director-report>. Last accessed 14th Dec 2020.

Business Today. (2021). Hero MotoCorp share hits 52-week high post Q3 earnings. Available: <https://www.businesstoday.in/markets/company-stock/hero-motocorp-share-hits-52-week-high-post-q3-earnings/story/430422.html>. Last accessed 14th Feb 2021.

Chandani, A., Mehta, M., Mall, A. and Khokhar, V., 2016. Employee engagement: A review paper on factors affecting employee engagement. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 9(15).

Chandrasekar, K., 2011. Workplace environment and its impact on organisational performance in public sector organisations. *International journal of enterprise computing and business systems*, 1(1), pp.1-19.

Chapman, G., & White, P. (2012). *The 5 languages of appreciation in the workplace* (3rd ed., pp. 69-70). New York: Moody Publishers.

Chouddhury, S. and Mohanty, M. K. 2018. A Conceptual Model of Employee Engagement - From the perspective of the Manufacturing Industry. *Research Review International Journal of Multidisciplinary*, 3(7)

Chowdhury, R.G., 2014. A Study on The Impact of Leadership Styles on Employee Motivation and Commitment: An Empirical Study of Selected Organisations In Corporate Sector. Department of Business Management. India, Padmashree Dr DY Patil University. Doctor of Philosophy, 426.

Clifton, D & Buckingham, M. (2001). The revolutionary Gallup program that shows you how to develop your unique talents and strengths. In: *Now, Discover Your Strengths*. New York: Gallup Press. 61-75.

Cody, J. (2015). How labor manages productivity advances and crisis response A comparative study of automotive manufacturing in Germany and the US. www.global-labour-university.org

Collis, J. and Hussey, R., 2013. *Business research: A practical guide for undergraduate and postgraduate students*. Palgrave macmillan.

Cooper, D.R., Schindler, P.S. and Sun, J., 2013. *Business research methods* (Vol. 12). New York: McGraw-Hill Irwin.

Csikszentmihalyi, M. (2008). *Flow* (3rd ed., pp. 37-40). New York: Harper Perennial Modern Classics.

Dalal, R.S., Baysinger, M., Brummel, B.J. and LeBreton, J.M., 2012. The relative importance of employee engagement, other job attitudes, and trait affect as predictors of job performance. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 42, pp. E295-E325.

Davies, I.A. and Crane, A., 2010. Corporate social responsibility in small-and medium-size enterprises: investigating employee engagement in fair trade companies. *Business Ethics: A European Review*, 19(2), pp.126-139.

Davidescu, A. A. M., Apostu, S. A., Paul, A., & Casuneanu, I. (2020). Work flexibility, job satisfaction, and job performance among romanian employees-Implications for sustainable human resource management. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(15). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12156086>

DNA. (2010). Hero, Honda split after 26 years. Available: <https://www.dnaindia.com/business/report-hero-honda-split-after-26-years-1482149>. Last accessed 10th March 2020.

Drake, T.J., 2018. *Assessing employee engagement: A comparison of the job engagement scale and the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale* (Doctoral dissertation, Colorado State University Libraries).

Drucker, P. (2001). *Essential Drucker* (8th ed., pp. 77-80). Saint Louis: Routledge.

Drucker, P., & Maciariello, J. (2009) *The Daily Drucker: 366 Days of Insight and Motivation for Getting the Right Things Done* (7th ed., pp. 40-45). New York: HarperCollins.

Drucker, P. (2011). *Managing for results*. London: Routledge.

Duran, M., & Sanchez, J. (2021). Employee Engagement and Wellbeing in Times of COVID-19 : A Proposal of the 5Cs Model. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(5470), 2–15.

Dutton, J., Spreitzer, G., Achor, S., Waltzer, L., Coolidge, J., & Whipple, G. (2014). *How to be a positive leader* (2nd ed., pp. 78-85). Oakland: Berrett-Koehler Publishers.

Economic Times. (2013). Hero Honda launches Karizma ZMR . Available: <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/hero-honda-launches-karizma-zmr/articleshow/5038924.cms?from=mdr>. Last accessed 1st Feb 2020.

Economic Times. (2016). India's growth at 7.6% in 2015-16 fastest in five years Read more at: <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com> Available: <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/economy/indicators/indias-growth-at-7-6-in-2015-16-fastest-in-five-years/articleshow/52522153.cms?from=mdr>. Last accessed 14th Dec 2020.

Economic Times. (2020). Global two-wheeler market to grow to 62.6 million by 2025: Report. Available: <https://auto.economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/two-wheelers/motorcycles/global-two-wheeler-market-to-grow-to-62-6-million-by-2025-report/74968396>. Last accessed 01st Dec 2020.

Economic Times. (2020). Covid-19: Hero MotoCorp advances monthly payments to contract workers. Available: <https://auto.economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/two-wheelers/motorcycles/covid-19-hero-motocorp-advances-monthly-payments-to-contract-workers/74777138>. Last accessed 1st April 2020.

Fairlie, P. (2011). Meaningful Work, Employee Engagement, and Other Key Employee Outcomes : Implications for Human Resource Development. *Advances in Developing Human Resources*. 6 (3), 61-75.

Galli, L. (2019). An Evidence-Based Take on Engagement and Surveys: Interview with Paul Fairlie, Founder & CEO of Heliosophy. Available: <https://scienceforwork.com/blog/paul-fairlie-heliosophy/>. Last accessed 01st Dec 2020.

Ghosh, M. (2020). Hero MotoCorp announces major changes in top management. Available: <https://www.livemint.com/news/india/hero-motocorp-announces-major-changes-in-top-management-11595328623182.html>. Last accessed 02nd Dec 2020.

Gitahi, N.S., 2014. Effect of workplace environment on the performance of commercial banks employees in Nakuru town(Doctoral dissertation, Kabarak University).

Graves, D., (2006). *A sea of faces*. 1st ed. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann, pp.78-82.

Greener, S., 2008. Business research methods. BookBoon.

Greenfield, T., 2016. Research methods for postgraduates. John Wiley & Sons.

Gruman, J., & Saks, A. (2011). Performance management and employee engagement. *Human Resource Management Review*, 21(2), 123-136. doi: 10.1016/j.hrmmr.2010.09.004

Gottman, J., & DeClaire, J. (2002). *The Relationship Cure* (1st ed., pp. 45-55). New York: Harmony.

Hair Jr, J.F., Wolfinbarger, M., Money, A.H., Samouel, P. and Page, M.J., 2015. *Essentials of business research methods*. Routledge.

Hanaysha, J., 2016. Improving employee productivity through work engagement: Evidence from the higher education sector. *Management Science Letters*, 6(1), pp.61-70.

Hechanova, R.M., and Cementina-Olpoc, R., 2013. Transformational leadership, change management, and commitment to change: A comparison of academic and business organisations. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 22(1), pp.11-19.

Hero MotoCorp. (2019). Annual Report 2018-19. Available: https://www.heromotocorp.com/en-in/uploads/Annual_Reports/pdf/20190715054601pdf266.pdf. Last accessed 10th Dec 2020.

Hero MotoCorp. (2020). About us. Available: <https://www.heromotocorp.com/en-in/about-us.php#:~:text=Hero%20MotoCorp%20currently%20has%20an,million%20units%20of%20two%2Dwheelers>. Last accessed 1st Jan 2021.

Hero MotoCorp (2020). Annual Report 2019-2020. Available: https://www.heromotocorp.com/en-in/uploads/Annual_Reports/pdf/20200717171801-pdf-207.pdf. Last accessed 1st Dec 2020.

Hero MotoCorp. (2021). REMUNERATION AND BOARD DIVERSITY POLICY. Available: <https://www.heromotocorp.com/en-in/about-us/key-policies/remuneration-policy.html>. Last accessed 2nd Feb 2021.

Hess, U. (2016). Nonverbal Communication. *Encyclopedia of Mental Health: Second Edition*, February, 208–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-397045-9.00218-4>

- Hetzner, S., Heid, H. and Gruber, H., 2015. Using workplace changes as learning opportunities: Antecedents to reflection in professional work. *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 27(1), pp.34-50.
- Hiatt, J., 2006. ADKAR. 2nd ed. Loveland, Colorado: Prosci Learning Center Publications, pp.55-57.
- Hill, L. (1996). Building Effective One-on-One Work Relationships. Available: <https://store.hbr.org/product/building-effective-one-on-one-work-relationships/497028>. Last accessed 02nd Dec 2020.
- Hindu. (2011). Hero Honda ropes in Wolff Olins for new brand identity. Available: <https://www.thehindu.com/business/companies/Hero-Honda-ropes-in-Wolff-Olins-for-new-brand-identity/article14941838.ece>. Last accessed 01st March 2020.
- Horovitz, B. (2009). Campbell CEO Conant nears his 'extraordinary' goal. Available: <https://abcnews.go.com/Business/story?id=6726806&page=1>. Last accessed 10th Dec 2020.
- Iqbal, A., 2010. Employee turnover: Causes, consequences and retention strategies in Saudi organisations. *The Business Review*, Cambridge, 16(2), pp.275-281.
- Iqbal, A., Ijaz, M., Latif, F. and Mushtaq, H., 2015. Factors affecting the employee's performance: A case study of banking sector in Pakistan. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 4(8), pp.309-318.
- Jain, R. and Kaur, S., 2014. Impact of work environment on job satisfaction. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 4(1), pp.1-8.
- Jensen, B., & Klein, J. (2014). *Hacking work* (1st ed., pp. 55-65). New York: Portfolio
- Kabat-Zinn, J., (2005). *Full catastrophe living*. 2nd ed. New York, N.Y.: Bantam Dell, pp.44-46.
- Kahneman, D., & Egan, P. (2011). *Thinking, fast and slow* (4th ed., pp. 88-98). New York: Random House Audio.
- Karunakar, B. (2017). Indian Passenger Vehicle Industry: Strategic Analysis with Focus on the Big Four Firms. *NMIMS Journal of Economics and Public Policy*, II (1), 47–72.

Kaushik, V., & Walsh, C. A. (2019). Pragmatism as a research paradigm and its implications for Social Work research. *Social Sciences*, 8(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci8090255>

Kelchtermans, G., 2006. Teacher collaboration and collegiality as workplace conditions. A review. *Zeitschrift fur padagogik*, 52(2), p.220.

Khan, U.R. and Salahuddin, W., 2018. Impact of Workplace Environment on Employees' Performance. *RADS Journal of Social Sciencess & Business Management*, 5(1), pp.66-76.

Kincentric. (2020). 2019 Trends in Global Employee Engagement. Available: https://www.kincentric.com/-/media/kincentric/pdfs/kincentric_2019_trends_global_employee_engagement.pdf. Last accessed 03rd Dec 2020.

Kompasso, S.M. and Sridevi, M.S., 2010. Employee engagement: The key to improving performance. *International journal of business and management*, 5(12), p.89.

Koskinen, J.P., 2015. Engaged to Perform: Enhancing Employee Engagement of a Production Unit.

Kuntsi, V., 2014. Fostering work engagement through dedication: Case Ramboll (Master's thesis).

Kuranchie-Mensah, E.B. and Amponsah-Tawiah, K., 2016. Employee motivation and work performance: A comparative study of mining companies in Ghana. *Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management*, 9(2), pp.255-309.

LaBarre, P. and Taylor, W., (2014). *Mavericks at work*. 2nd ed. New York: HarperCollins, pp.77-79.

Lai, F. Y., Tang, H. C., Lu, S. C., Lee, Y. C., & Lin, C. C. (2020). Transformational Leadership and Job Performance: The Mediating Role of Work Engagement. *SAGE Open*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244019899085>

Lee, F.K., Sheldon, K.M. and Turban, D.B., 2003. Personality and the goal-striving process: The influence of achievement goal patterns, goal level, and mental focus on performance and enjoyment. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(2), p.256.

Lewchuk, W., Stewart, P., & Yates, C. (2001). Quality of working life in the automobile industry: A Canada-UK comparative study. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 16(2), 72–87. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-005X.00078>

LiveMint. (2013). Hero picks up 49.2% stake in Erik Buell Racing for \$25 million. Available: <https://www.livemint.com/Companies/TIwIxOx2Hvcq1GKKyNfUVK/Hero-MotoCorp-to-buy-492-stake-in-superbike-firm-Erik-Buel.html>. Last accessed 01st Nov 2020.

Loehr, J., (2005). *The power of full engagement*. 2nd ed. New York: Simon & Schuster, pp.55-57.

MacKay, R. B., & Chia, R. (2013). Choice, Chance, and Unintended Consequences in Strategic Change: A Process Understanding of the Rise and Fall of NorthCo Automotive. *Academy of Management Journal*, 56(1), 208–230.

Mariscal, M.A., López-Perea, E.M., García-Herrero, S., López-García, J.R. and Herrera, S., 2018. Data on the working population in Spain related to training, workplace conditions and accident rates. *Data in brief*, 21, pp.1810-1817.

Meyer, J. P., Stanley, L. J., & Parfyonova, N. M. (2012). Employee commitment in context: The nature and implication of commitment profiles. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 80(1), 1–16. doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2011.07.002

Miglani, S. (2019). The Growth of the Indian Automobile Industry: Analysis of the Roles of Government Policy and Other Enabling Factors. 439–463. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-8102-7_19

Mohammad Nazir, N., & Shavarebi, K. (2019). A review of global automotive industry's competitive strategies. *World Journal of Science, Technology and Sustainable Development*, ahead-of-print(ahead-of-print). <https://doi.org/10.1108/WJSTSD-10-2018-0060>

Moreland, J., 2013. Improving job fit can improve employee engagement and productivity. *Employment Relations Today*, 40(1), pp.57-62.

MotorCyclesData. (2020). Global Motorcycles Market grew up in double digit in October 2020. Available: <https://www.motorcyclesdata.com/2020/12/22/world-motorcycles-market/>. Last accessed 14th Dec 2020.

Nandi, S. (1994). As Bajaj Auto's motorcycle sales top, the industry moves into high gear. Available: <https://www.indiatoday.in/magazine/economy/story/19941130-as-bajaj-autos-motorcycle-sales-top-the-industry-moves-into-high-gear-810340-1994-11-30>. Last accessed 10th Oct 2020.

NDTV. (2021). Hero MotoCorp Ltd. Available: https://www.ndtv.com/business/stock/hero-motocorp-ltd_heromotoco/reports. Last accessed 1st Jan 2021.

Nielsen, K., & Randall, R. (2012). The importance of employee participation and perceptions of changes in procedures in a teamworking intervention. *Work & Stress*, 26(2), 91–111. doi:10.1080/02678373.2012.682721

Nowell, L. S., Norris, J. M., White, D. E., & Moules, N. J. (2017). Thematic Analysis: Striving to Meet the Trustworthiness Criteria. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*.

Obeng, A. F., Zhu, Y., Quansah, P. E., Ntarmah, A. H., & Cobbinah, E. (2021). High-Performance Work Practices and Turnover Intention: Investigating the Mediating Role of Employee Morale and the Moderating Role of Psychological Capital. *SAGE Open*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020988557>

Osborne, S. and Hammoud, M.S., 2017. Effective employee engagement in the workplace. *International Journal of Applied Management and Technology*, 16(1), p.4.

Osborne, S. and Hammoud, M.S., 2017. Effective employee engagement in the workplace. *International Journal of Applied Management and Technology*, 16(1), p.4.

Outlook. (2020). 'Diversity' Journey at Hero MotoCorp Surpasses Significant Milestone With 1000 Women Employees. Available: <https://www.outlookindia.com/newscroll/diversity-journey-at-hero-motocorp-surpasses-significant-milestone-with-1000-women-employees/1600447>. Last accessed 2nd Dec 2020.

Paul, G., Kirsten, M., Rebecca, B., Alison, M., & Corinne, G. (2009). The dark side of competition: How competitive behaviour and striving to avoid inferiority are linked to depression, anxiety, stress and self-harm. *Psychology and Psychotherapy*, 82(Pt 2), 123–136. <https://doi.org/10.1348/147608308X379806>

Parding, K. and Berg-Jansson, A., 2018. Conditions for workplace learning in professional work: Discrepancies between occupational and organisational values. *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 30(2), pp.108-120.

Parker, D., Charlton, J., Ribeiro, A. and D. Pathak, R., 2013. Integration of project-based management and change management: Intervention methodology. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 62(5), pp.534-544.

Pedersen, D.E., Minnotte, K.L., Kiger, G. and Mannon, S.E., 2009. Workplace policy and environment, family role quality, and positive family-to-work spillover. *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*, 30(1), p.80.

Pencavel, J., 2014. The productivity of working hours. *The Economic Journal*, 125(589), pp.2052-2076.

People Matters. (2020). Driving blue-collar productivity: Hero MotoCorp's way. Available: <https://www.peoplesmatters.in/article/performance-management-systems/driving-blue-collar-productivity-hero-motocorps-way-20562>. Last accessed 10th Dec 2020.

Polek-Duraj, K.O.R.N.E.L.I.A., 2013. Level of working conditions in relation to employees productivity on the basis of sawmills in Opole region. *Annals of Warsaw University of Life Sciences-SGGW. Forestry and Wood Technology*, 84.

Rath, T. and Harter, J., (2010). *Wellbeing*. 1st ed. Mumbai: Simon & Schuster India, pp.55-57.

Rechtschaffen, S. (2002). *Time shifting* (1st ed., pp. 75-78). New York: Broadway Books.

Rich, B.L., Lepine, J.A. and Crawford, E.R., 2010. Job engagement: Antecedents and effects on job performance. *Academy of management journal*, 53(3), pp.617-635.

Robertson, I.T., Jansen Birch, A. and Cooper, C.L., 2012. Job and work attitudes, engagement and employee performance: Where does psychological well-being fit in?. *Leadership & Organisation Development Journal*, 33(3), pp.224-232.

Roscigno, V. J. (2019). Discrimination, Sexual Harassment, and the Impact of Workplace Power: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2378023119853894>, 5, 237802311985389.

Rothmann, S. and Rothmann Jr, S., 2010. Factors associated with employee engagement in South Africa. *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 36(2), pp.1-12.

Russell, M. B., Attoh, P. A., Chase, T., Gong, T., Kim, J., & Liggans, G. L. (2020). Examining Burnout and the Relationships Between Job Characteristics, Engagement, and Turnover Intention Among U.S. Educators. *SAGE Open*, 10(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020972361>

Sageer, A., Rafat, S. and Agarwal, P., 2012. Identification of variables affecting employee satisfaction and their impact on the organisation. *IOSR Journal of business and management*, 5(1), pp.32-39.

Sahni, J. (2021). Employee Engagement Among Millennial Workforce: Empirical Study on Selected Antecedents and Consequences: <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211002208>, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211002208>

Sarangi, S. and Srivastava, R.K., 2012. Impact of organisational culture and communication on employee engagement: An investigation of Indian private banks. *South Asian Journal of Management*, 19(3), p.18.

Saunderson, R. (1997). *How to Focus on Success: Create a Laser-Like Focus for Achieving Your Success* (1st ed., pp. 85-90). Toronto: Hushion House.

Saunders, M.N., Lewis, P., Thornhill, A. and Bristow, A., 2015. *Understanding research philosophy and approaches to theory development*.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P & Thornhill, A. 2012. *Research methods for business students*, 6.

Saunders, M.N., 2011. *Research methods for business students*, 5/e. Pearson Education India.

Satata, D. B. M. (2021). Employee Engagement as An Effort to Improve Work Performance: Literature Review. *Ilomata International Journal of Social Science*, 2(1), 41–49. <https://doi.org/10.52728/ijss.v2i1.152>

Schaufeli, W.B. and Bakker, A.B., 2010. Defining and measuring work engagement: Bringing clarity to the concept. *Work engagement: A handbook of essential theory and research*, pp.10-24.

Seligman, M. E. P. (2002). *Authentic happiness: using the new positive psychology to realize your potential for lasting fulfillment*. New York, Free Press.

Sekaran, U. and Bougie, R., 2016. *Research methods for business: A skill building approach*. John Wiley & Sons.

SESEI. (2020). *Indian Automobile Industry*. Available: http://www.sesei.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/Automotive-Sector-Report_-Final.pdf. Last accessed 24th Dec 2020.

Shah, P. (2020). *Covid-19 Relief: Hero MotoCorp manufactures over 5,000-litres of sanitiser to fight the pandemic!* Available: <https://www.financialexpress.com/auto/industry/covid-19-coronavirus-relief-hero-motocorp-manufactures-over-5000-litre-sanitiser-to-fight-the-pandemic-ration-kits-food-supplies-donations/1933714/>. Last accessed 02nd Dec 2020.

Shalini,P and Nasima,A. (2018). *The Antecedents of Employee Engagement in An Automobile Industry*. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics*. 119 (18), 61-75.

Shantz, A., Alfes, K., Truss, C. and Soane, E., 2013. *The role of employee engagement in the relationship between job design and task performance, citizenship and deviant behaviours*. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 24(13), pp.2608-2627.

Sharma, M.S. and Sharma, M.V., 2014. *Employee engagement to enhance productivity in current scenario*. *International Journal of Commerce, Business and Management*, 3(4), pp.595-604.

Shepherd, M.L., Harris, M.L., Chung, H. and Himes, E.M., 2014. *Using the Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability, Reinforcement Model to build a shared governance culture*. *Journal of Nursing Education and Practice*, 4(6), p.90.

Shuck, B., Reio Jr, T.G. and Rocco, T.S., 2011. *Employee engagement: An examination of antecedent and outcome variables*. *Human resource development international*, 14(4), pp.427-445.

Simha B.S and Vardan B.V, 2015. *Enhancing “Performance and Retention” through Employee Engagement*. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 5(8), 1-6.

Spencer, A.J., Buhalis, D. and Moital, M., 2012. A hierarchical model of technology adoption for small owner-managed travel firms: An organisational decision-making and leadership perspective. *Tourism management*, 33(5), pp.1195-1208.

Statista. (2020). India: Estimated total population from 2015 to 2025(in millions). Available: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/263766/total-population-of-india/#:~:text=The%20statistic%20shows%20the%20total,to%20approximately%201.38%20billion%20people.&text=India%20currently%20has%20the%20s>. Last accessed 04th Dec 2020.

Steger, M., Frazier, P., Oishi, S. and Kaler, M., (2006). The meaning in life questionnaire: Assessing the presence of and search for meaning in life. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 53(1), pp.80-93.

Tan, T.F. and Netessine, S., 2014. When does the devil make work? An empirical study of the impact of workload on worker productivity. *Management Science*, 60(6), pp.1574-1593.

Times Now. (2021). Hero MotoCorp rolls off 100 millionth two-wheeler. Available: <https://www.timesnownews.com/auto/bike-news/article/hero-motocorp-rolls-off-100-millionth-two-wheeler-from-haridwar-plant/710162>. Last accessed 01st Dec 2020.

Thayer, R., (1997). *The origin of everyday moods*. 1st ed. New York: Oxford University Press, pp.33-35.

Unsworth, K. L., Dmitrieva, A., & Adriasola, E. (2012). Changing behaviour: Increasing the effectiveness of workplace interventions in creating pro-environmental behaviour change. *Journal of Organisational Behavior*, 34(2), 211–229. doi:10.1002/job.1837

Vance, R.J., 2006. *Employee engagement and commitment: A guide to understanding, measuring and increasing engagement in your organisation*. SHRM Foundation.

Weintraub, J. (2009). *Engagement Toolkit for Managers and Leaders*. Available: https://hr.harvard.edu/files/humanresources/files/engagement_toolkit_leaders_managers.pdf. Last accessed 14th Dec 2020.

William, G.Z., 2003. *Business research methods*. Thomson South-Western publications.

WorldBank. (2020). GDP growth (annual %) - India. Available: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.KD.ZG?locations=IN>. Last accessed 02nd Dec 2020.

Worline, M., Dutton, J. and Sisodia, R., (2017). *Awakening compassion at work*. 1st ed. Oakland (CA): Berrett-Koehler Publishers, pp.43-45.

Younger, J., Ulrich, D., & Brockbank, W (2012). *HR from the Outside In: Six Competencies for the Future of Human Resources*. London: McGraw-Hill Education. 41-45.

Yusuf, R. M., Fidyawan, S., & Wekke, I. S. (2017). Ulrich model on practices of human resource strategic roles. In *Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences* (Vol. 12, Issue 6, pp. 1657–1661). <https://doi.org/10.31227/osf.io/ysnu8>

Zamawe, F. C. (2015). The Implication of Using NVivo Software in Qualitative Data Analysis: Evidence-Based Reflections. *Malawi Medical Journal*, 27(1), 13. </pmc/articles/PMC4478399/>

Zarban, A., 2018. *The Impact of Perceived Leadership Styles on Hotel Employee Job Engagement*. Thesis. Rochester Institute of Technology

Zikmund, W.G., Babin, B.J., Carr, J.C. and Griffin, M., 2013. *Business research methods*. Cengage Learning.

Appendix 1: Consent Form

CONSENT FORM

Project Title: Changes in workplace conditions on employee engagement and Business productivity performance: case study of Hero Moto Corp.

Name of researcher: Poonam Dhaka

PARTICIPATION IN THIS RESEARCH STUDY IS VOLUNTARY

- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any queries to my satisfaction;	Yes/No
- I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequences of any kind;	Yes/No
- I understand that any information recorded in the investigation will remain confidential and my identity will remain anonymous in any reports or publications resulting from the study;	Yes/No
- I understand that I am free to contact researcher involved in the research to seek further clarification and information;	Yes/No
- I can request a copy of the transcript of my interview and may make edits I feel necessary to ensure the effectiveness of any agreement made about confidentiality;	Yes/No
- I consent to be a participant in the project;	Yes/No
- I consent to being audio recorded as part of the project;	Yes/No

**Please retain a copy of this consent form.*

By signing this consent form, you are indicating that you fully understand the above information and agree to participate in this study.

Participant name:

Signature: _____ **Date** _____

Interview er name:

Signature: _____ **Date** _____

Contact Information

This research was granted ethical approval by the University of the West of Scotland Ethics Committee.

If you have any further questions or concerns about this study, any comments to make now or later, or if you would like a copy of the published results of this study, please contact:

Researcher: Poonam Dhaka Email: [REDACTED]

Appendix 2: Ethical Form

Changes in workplace conditions on employee engagement and Business productivity performance: case study of Hero Moto Corp.

Poonam Dhaka

Doctorate in Business Administration, University of the West of Scotland

Information of Participants

Thank you considering participating in this case study. The information sheet outlines the purpose of study and provides a description of your involvement and rights as a participant, if you agree to take part.

1. What is the research about?

The aim of this study is to analyse the role of employee engagement in initiating organisational change and its impact on firm performance on employees working in Hero Motor Corporation India.

2. Do I have to take part?

Participation is voluntary. If you do decide to take part, I will ask you to sign a consent form and return in advance of the interview or sign in meeting.

3. What will be my involvement?

If you agree to participate an interview will be arranged at a place and time convenient to you. The interview will last about 40-60 minutes.

4. How do I withdraw from the study?

You can withdraw at any point of study, without giving any reason. If any question during the interview make you feel uncomfortable, you do not have to answer them, and you can withdraw from the interview at any time for any reason.

5. What will my information be used for?

I will use the collected information solely for doctoral academic research purpose.

6. Will my taking part and data be confidential? it will be anonymised?

The records from this study will be kept confidential and destroyed once the study will be completed. Your data will be anonymised- your name will not be used in any reports and

publications resulting from the study. All digital files, transcripts and summaries will be given codes and stored separately from any names or other direct identification of participants. Any hard copies of research information will be kept in locked files.

7. What are the possible benefits of taking part in this study?

Participants will understand the purpose of study

8. Expenses and payments.

There will be no expenses and payment of taking part in the study.

9. Who has reviewed the study?

The study has been reviewed by the supervisor and other senior faculty of my course.

Appendix 3: Interview and Responses

Question 1:

Interview Question: How can you identify if an employee is engaged or not?
Respondent 1: <i>An employee or colleague seems to be engaged if they have been completely productive in the organisation and their effort has provided positive results. Moreover, if an employee is focused in the job they do and if they are happy with what they are doing, then it can be said that the employee is completely engaged in the organisation.</i>
Respondent 2: <i>The colleagues are usually well engaged if they fundamentally enjoy the work they do and they enjoy the time they have spent at work leading to positive scenario in the organisation.</i>
Respondent 3: <i>Engaged employees tend to help each other whenever there is any need and help required. The engaged employees also take greater initiatives at work and they assume more responsibility for aligning their needs with the goals of the organisation whereas the disengaged employees lessly work hard and either don't take any initiatives or take very less initiatives.</i>
Respondent 4: <i>An engaged employee will be much more dedicated and busier with their work will generate good results for the organisation. Also, an engaged employee would have a positive attitude at work while working on their tasks at hand.</i>
Respondent 5: <i>A non-engaged employee will get stressed about their work and shifts. They will also reflect a sense of lack of motivation in their work.</i>
Respondent 6: <i>Truly engaged employees usually look beyond tasks and work towards a larger goal of an organisation to achieve it. Also, they focus on the keeping the organisation on top priority and want the organisation to achieve and succeed.</i>
Respondent 7:

If an employee is not engaged, he/she starts misleading the projects and has a very less interest towards work as they lack intent. Moreover, the employee also starts showing lack of communication i.e. they become withdrawn and stops sharing anything with colleagues and managers about the work they are doing. A non-engaged employee also regularly complains about work and other people in the organisation. They also deliver very low quality of work and lack ownership of whatever they do.

Respondent 8:

The way an employee works and their presence of mind while they do any tasks at hand identifies whether an employee is engaged or not.

Respondent 9:

If an employee is non engaged, he/she starts complaining about the work and everything they do. They also have poor communication and lack of networking skills and have very low quality of work which are usually the signs of a non-engaged employee.

Respondent 10:

The responsibilities allocated as per the tasks at hand and the deadlines associated with it determines if an employee is engaged or not.

Respondent 11:

By observing the attitude and the working style of an employee can state the engagement level in the organisation.

Respondent 12:

The organisation uses an online ticketing process which is updated daily where the management can track the progress of an employee and they can also check if the employee is perfectly engaged or not.

Respondent 13:

If an employee does not participate in company task & takes unplanned leaves.

Respondent 14:

The productivity starts affecting as engagement either increases or decreases.

Respondent 15:

If the employees work and the working time is efficient or not.

Respondent 16:

If the employee is enthusiastic, has enhanced performance, has positive experience for others, have a collaborative outlook and looks for ways to improve.

Respondent 17:

An employee can be monitored if they are engaged or not by identifying the amount of time they spend on their phone and social media during their working hours at office.

Respondent 18:

By noticing their behavioural pattern and by observing them closely.

Respondent 19:

If the employee is engaged, they will have good and open communications and would present a positive experience for others. They would look at the bigger picture and have a collaborative outlook. They also look for and shares ways to improve while exceeding the goals and expectations. They would also focus on personal and professional development.

Respondent 20:

By observing the actions and working style of an employee.

Question 2:

What strategies do you use to keep employees motivated?

Respondent 1:

The key strategy is to communicate the main goals clearly to the employees. Another strategy is to set appropriate tasks but also setting us realistic targets according to the timeframe. Providing development opportunities is one of the key strategies to keep employees motivated as it helps in both professional and personal development of an employee. Appreciating the performance and work done by an employee is another strategy to keep them engaged. Also, creating a collaboration culture in the office space is also an important strategy that we follow.

Respondent 2:

We usually let the employees know that we trust them and depend on them which gives them a sense of belongingness and have a sense of responsibility. Another strategy we use is to set smaller weekly goals for the employees. We also motivate the employees by giving them a purpose in whatever they do. We are also very transparent with employees about what's

happening at the highest level so that there are no surprises, and everyone has a chance to ask questions and give feedback.

Respondent 3:

To keep employees motivated we have created a very friendly working environment and maintain a friendly relationship. We also acknowledge the achievement of the employees and find happiness in even small achievements of our colleagues. The department also reward employees for their achievements and encourage the employees at each step. The department tends to have positive communication amongst the employees which is the key to success.

Respondent 4:

One of the main strategies that we use is to statistically update the team on what the project is achieving and what is the current and ongoing performance of the project. We motivate the employees by reassuring them if there are tasks which are delayed or if we fail to achieve any task at time. We also praise the employees by providing them incentives whenever there is any appreciation at place.

Respondent 5:

The strategies which we use in our team is by appreciating the employees for the work they do also by rotating the work between the employees so that they know what others are doing and they also learn the overall work within the organisation.

Respondent 6:

The management has created a friendly working environment for all the employees, and they reward them on regular basis whenever employees achieve something. We have a positive communicative environment within the team which is the key thing and encourage friendly competition within the employees to make them competitive and strive for more. The management also defines a career path for the employees which helps and motivate them to go beyond the normal and achieve higher goals set..

Respondent 7:

One of the key strategies we follow is no discrimination at work at all which is achieved by following fair work policies for everyone. Also, the salary given to the employees is based upon their skills and hard work. Another strategy followed is by creating fun events and parties for

the employees to make them socialise within the team which helps in creating healthy relationships.

Respondent 8:

The strategy which we follow in the team is pinpointing whenever the issue is so that everyone is aware and can work together to resolve the issue. Another strategy we use is by not taking the issue to the senior management as it disrupts the working environment, however we tend to resolve the issue within so that there is trust built up and maintained and the relationship within the working environment strengthens. The key to all of this is effective communication within the team which is being directly done with the employees.

Respondent 9:

There are various strategies which we follow in the team to engage the employees. One strategy is to be always friendly with the team. Another one is providing incentives to the employees to recognise the work they have done. We provide regular trainings for professional growth of the people and take regular feedbacks to improve and excel further. We organise regular meetings to discuss any concerns and issues if the team has. This helps in identifying the existing problems within the team and resolving them accordingly. This indeed helps in helping to each other whenever anyone needs any kind of help.

Respondent 10:

The strategy which we mainly use is to recognise the work which employees have done and guide them as a leader if they have failed to accomplish a task by providing them as much support as possible and provide appreciation as per the company policies wherever applicable.

Respondent 11:

Motivational talks are the strategy which we use to motivate and build confidence among the employees to keep them engaged.

Respondent 12:

Apart from fun activities every month there is an employee of the month contest where their contribution is evaluated by comparing the feedbacks and other factors.

Respondent 13:

The employees are appreciated by giving final rewards, long service rewards etc.

Respondent 14:

The employees are effectively motivated by having an effective communication with them and taking constant feedback.

Respondent 15:

The organisation usually understands the importance of the employee and make the employee understand how important they are to them.

Respondent 16:

The organisation provides friendly working environment to all the employees, they also provide rewards to them and acknowledge the handwork they have done by providing incentives and awards.

Respondent 17:

Normally the organisation supports the employees in achieving their tasks in order to keep them motivated.

Respondent 18:

The team tries to always keep the employees motivated by talking to them and letting them know that they believe in them.

Respondent 19:

Firstly, make the organisation a perfect place to be in. Being respectful, honest, and supportive to employees and awarding employee rewards. Giving the employees a room to grow and sharing positive feedback. Also, by being transparent, offering flexible schedules and providing meals if possible.

Respondent 20:

Many strategies are used such as casual get togethers, supporting colleagues in their work and providing help whenever required. Most importantly, maintaining supportive & positive attitude towards our fellow colleagues which in turn increases their productivity. Also guiding them correctly if they make any mistake.

Question 3:

What strategies do you use to keep employees engaged in the organisation? You can mention multiple strategies.

Respondent 1:

We provide regular trainings to the employees and take regular feedbacks from them. We also provide the workload for which an employee is capable and gives them sufficient time to manage that workload effectively. We aim to extend help to them whenever required or they are in need and appreciating the work they have done whenever it is under our capacity.

Respondent 2:

We get to know the employees and their working style and provide them with tools and knowledge to succeed in the organisation. We give them timely updates on the performance of the company and how the company is doing at regular times. We give room to each employee to grow for their professional benefit. We recognise the teams hard work they have done and support them whenever they need any help and reward them for their hard work. We widely encourage teamwork within our team and give opportunities to everyone in the team to lead from the front so that they can improve their leadership qualities.

Respondent 3:

Our management has made the workplace a pleasant and comfortable place to work. We widely encourage being respectful to others, being honest and supportive to everyone in the team. We also offer employee rewards whenever someone has gone beyond to achieve something.

Respondent 4:

There are various strategies which we follow in the team to engage the employees. One strategy is to be always friendly with the team. Another one is providing incentives to the employees to recognise the work they have done. We provide regular trainings for professional growth of the people and take regular feedbacks to improve and excel further. We organise regular meetings to discuss any concerns and issues if the team has. This helps in identifying the existing problems within the team and resolving them accordingly. This indeed helps in helping to each other whenever anyone needs any kind of help.

Respondent 5:

The team always follow a positive attitude with everyone by effectively communicating and conveying tasks to each other. We listen to the problems of each employee and organise motivational events to keep up the moral of the people

Respondent 6:

The management tends to register the performance of everyone in the team and provide promotions to everyone accordingly. A special rewards scheme is in place to reward the highest rating performers in the team.

Respondent 7:

The strategy which we follow in the team is pinpointing whenever the issue is so that everyone is aware and can work together to resolve the issue. Another strategy we use is by not taking the issue to the senior management as it disrupts the working environment, however we tend to resolve the issue within so that there is trust built up and maintained and the relationship within the working environment strengthens. The key to all of this is effective communication within the team which is being directly done with the employees.

Respondent 8:

We set smaller weekly goals for the employees. We are very transparent with employees about what is happening at the highest level so there are no surprises, and everyone has a chance to ask questions and give feedback. We motivate the individual rather than the whole team. We also let the employees lead the team in various projects.

Respondent 9:

The team identifies the top performers in the team and reward them. Transparency is promoted within the team so that everyone has a clear understanding of what everyone is doing instead of having any vague information. We allow everyone to provide honest feedback for improvement and we take it seriously to make any changes suggested which is under the company guidelines. We make ourselves accountable for any mistakes we have done and recognise the issues to improve upon those mistakes.

Respondent 10:

I give task as per their role and capability. Fixing a timeline for everyone and monitoring on regular basis about the progress. Taking reviews on regular time frame and discuss issues and take suggestions from the team to motivate them for better performance.

Respondent 11:

Recognising and appreciating the employee by offering the opportunity to make a difference. Job rotation is in place so that everyone knows everything about what others do in the team and have better understanding of how the team operates.

Respondent 12:

Main strategy to keep employees engaged is to keep them updated on multiple projects and try to involve them with multiple projects.

Respondent 13:

There are a lot of strategies used such as coaching the employees for success, providing the employees with right tools they need to work, engaging the high potential employees into dedicated organisational tasks and clearly defining the organisations goals to them.

Respondent 14:

The organisation uses effective communication and take constant feedback from employees.

Respondent 15:

The organisation usually assigns the roles and responsibilities based on their capability, they take care of the personal benefits of the employee and appreciates the impact an employee has created on the organisation.

Respondent 16:

By communicating constantly and giving employees the tools, they need and by acting fairly, respectfully and creating trust among them.

Respondent 17:

There are various strategies used such as work recognition, organising recreational activities for the employees, and conducting learning activities.

Respondent 18:

There are various strategies which they use such as sending thank you cards to the employees, appreciating them of the work they have done, playing frequent fun games, giving responsibilities to the employees and having one to one meeting with them.

Respondent 19:

By recognising and appreciating them and offering the opportunity to make a difference. Providing education and training opportunities and implementing job rotations.

Respondent 20:

Maintaining a healthy work culture & positive attitude towards all. Support in all areas required & appreciate their hard work.

Question 4:

What strategies mentioned in the previous question didn't work or wasn't much effective? Why?

Respondent 1:

Managing the workload of the employees was sometimes difficult due to untimely deadlines. Sometimes the training which is provided theoretically does not help much in the practical world.

Respondent 2:

The strategy which sometimes did not work is leading from the front whenever required. This is because some of the members of the team take disadvantage of the freedom and leadership when provided to them. They usually do not work with the team and make other team members follow them.

Respondent 3:

Be a respectful and supportive colleague strategy did not work as it was not much effective as the support is useless until the employees need it.

Respondent 4:

Providing incentives sometimes do not work as some of the employees think the incentives are underrated but we must follow the company guidelines due to which the moral is sometimes down for the employees.

Respondent 5:

Talking to them and extending help did not work as well because there wasn't much availability and maybe there was a hesitation in making the formal relationship informal.

Respondent 6:

Promoting employees or providing a promotion is not much effective as the results are not seen immediately.

Respondent 7:

Sometimes over trusting the employees is not very effective because you totally rely on them and it has led to failure of projects.

Respondent 8:

Most of the strategies worked well and nothing seemed to fail till now.

Respondent 9:

Sometimes it is difficult to implement transparency at a wider scale as it can offend some underperforming employees.

Respondent 10:

Designate with authority does not work sometimes because many people do not work as a team and they point out flaws in other people due to their personal disliking or personal issues.

Respondent 11:

Implementing job rotation was not much effective as it does not work until and unless the employee is interested in it.

Respondent 12:

Sometimes keeping employees on multiple projects is overwhelming and may affect their efficiency.

Respondent 13:

The Respondent have not experienced any case as such.

Respondent 14:

All the strategies used by the organisation were effective.

Respondent 15:

The Respondent have not experienced any case as such.

Respondent 16:

Open communication because sometimes employees become over friendly and create indiscipline.

Respondent 17:

Recognition of the work they have done sometimes did not work as the employees felt not awarded as per the work they have done.

Respondent 18:

Sometime the fun activities conducted do not work as the employees are so much drained of the work, they do that they are not in a mood to play and engage in such activities.

Respondent 19:

Job rotation does not work sometimes as some employees can be less motivated to do certain jobs and can cause further disruptions in the organisation.

Respondent 20:

By giving just the financial hikes, one cannot retain employees as retaining them requires a lot of motivation and support in terms of individual learning & growth.

Question 5:

Are there any strategies used by the organisation to increase employee engagement? Were there any challenges? If yes, how were the challenges overcome?

Respondent 1:

Yes, there are many strategies used by the organisation. They provide regular trainings to the employees; they have an appraisal system in place to reward the deserving employees. Regular team meetings are organised to discuss any issues and listening to any concerns if the employees have. There were a few challenges sometimes as there were some guidelines set by the organisation which had to be followed by the employees, but they disapproved of it.

Respondent 2:

The company organises parties and social gatherings every quarter so that the teams and colleagues get along with each other and know each other well. In these gatherings the achievements of the organisation are also discussed. The management also shares about the progress and how well the organisation is performing as compared to its market competitors. With this strategy, employees usually attend social gatherings for free food and drinks, but they also get to know about the important information which is shared.

Respondent 3:

There are many strategies which are used such as surveying employees about motivators, empowering employees, using exit interviews, evaluating the managers performance and regular feedback from the employees.

Respondent 4:

Appreciating the employees for their work and rewarding this is one of the main strategies. However, there are challenges with it in some aspect as it is sometimes misunderstood as favouritism by some people. To overcome this type of challenge, the departments sometimes decide based on work which everyone does and further do a group voting to decide.

Respondent 5:

Yes, the department organised a thank you bonus which was vouchers and a slice of cake for everyone. The challenge was organising it for a lot of people and managing them.

Respondent 6:

There is a monthly performance report prepared by the department for all the colleagues. However, there is sometimes lack of focus by the management on senior people in the team.

Respondent 7:

Total Employee Engagement (TEI) is a strategy used by our organisation. Under this, a team is built from various sections and a particular problem is chosen in which everyone equally contributes to solve the problem. The main challenge is to contribute equally as a team after having different technical knowledge and communication skills for everyone.

Respondent 8:

There were not many strategies used by our department apart of best employee performance rewards which had no challenges to follow.

Respondent 9:

Yes, the organisation focused on to create culture of collaboration by installing new customised software/apps and arranging events for all employees. There were some issues related to bullying by some managers which were dealt by using anonymous surveys and followed by one-to-one meeting with the relevant departments.

Respondent 10:

Yes, the management assign the task with prior discussion and assign authority to take decision at some extent.

Respondent 11:

Multiple strategies are used such as rewarding the employees, providing a friendly workspace for everyone. As improving engagement requires high levels of communication, on our

information-saturated world, it's difficult to cut through the noise. Getting the attention of the employees is a challenge and soliciting input also creates vast amount of feedback that can overwhelm the engagement team.

Respondent 12:

The Respondent is unsure about any such strategies.

Respondent 13:

The organisation conducts internal surveys to spread awareness among the employees.

Respondent 14:

There were not any challenges faced in the organisation.

Respondent 15:

The Respondent have not experienced any case as such.

Respondent 16:

The organisation usually increases employee engagement by rewarding the employees.

Respondent 17:

Recreational activities during COVID-19 were difficult but the team managed to overcome this problem by introducing a half day fun activity virtually.

Respondent 18:

They started this thing called Thankyou cards where in you can write a message for someone and keep it at their desk. The initiative itself was a challenge but when one person started a rhythm was set in and people could express. There were happy tears as well.

Respondent 19:

Staff interaction and communication. The main challenge was to implement a system which would improve employee's interaction and communication. To achieve this my organisation installed a social software for internal employees only.

Respondent 20:

Nothing known to the Respondent.

Question 6:

When do you feel disengaged at work?

Respondent 1:

There is various instance when disengagement is felt such as when there is excessive workload, and it is accomplished on it but there is no appreciation of it. When there is a lot of mental pressure and stress, the mind feels to be disengaged. Another one is when we are not getting paid for the overwork we do and lastly when there is no appreciation when we work out of the office hours.

Respondent 2:

Disengagement is felt when the work and tasks are too easy to follow or when there are no challenges and no competition with other colleagues within the team.

Respondent 3:

The employees do not feel engaged when there is poor communication between the people in the team. Also, when there are regular breaks from the routine and there is complacency.

Respondent 4:

When there is a lot of pressure, we feel disengaged.

Respondent 5:

There is disengagement when the tasks are repetitive, and we have to follow the same structure, pattern and routine every day.

Respondent 6:

If there is no interest in the job we are doing or if the job is too easy, there is a sense of disengagement.

Respondent 7:

The Respondent states that when there is a lack of new challenges at work, they feel disengaged doing the same type of work. Also, when there is lack of learning and lack of motivation, the morale comes down easily.

Respondent 8:

The Respondent does not feel disengaged at all.

Respondent 9:

There are various times when disengagement is felt such as when there is very poor management, when there is lack of personal growth, when there is lack of training and lack of appreciation for the work we do.

Respondent 10:

There is disengagement when the seniors do not allocate new tasks and do not involve in team discussions.

Respondent 11:

The Respondent feel disengaged because of personal work ethic and when the job is too easy or when are not being challenged enough.

Respondent 12:

When a project is complete, and we are waiting for clients' feedback and there is no other project in pipeline for team. At this time, we try to get involved with other project or provide consultation for other projects.

Respondent 13:

Usually, the employees are disengaged for not getting appreciation of all the hard work and good work they do.

Respondent 14:

The Respondent feels disengaged when they are under pressure.

Respondent 15:

When the targets assigned to the employees are low.

Respondent 16:

When there is same type of work to be done again and again and when the employee must do overtime.

Respondent 17:

The Respondent usually feel disengaged when there are certain team meetings in which they are not full involved.

Respondent 18:

This usually happened when the employee feels out of place and not trusted by the management.

Respondent 19:

Management behaviours towards the subordinates make a difference and if managers don't show concern and care towards the employees then the environment doesn't feel to be friendly and thus we feel disengaged.

Respondent 20:

Whenever they feel that they are being overburdened by a lot of tasks.

Question 7:

Did your organisation use any strategy/motivation to engage you back?

Respondent 1:

The organisation provided appraisals and vouchers as a kind gesture to boost motivation.

Respondent 2:

Yes, the organisation started rewarding people who performed well, and this encouraged other colleagues to participate and make the projects more interesting with their new ideas.

Respondent 3:

The managers organised and coordinated volunteering opportunities and prioritised mental and physical health.

Respondent 4:

The management organised some stress relief games and motivational speech classes. They also started celebrating birthdays and organised team parties from time to time.

Respondent 5:

The project heads switched the working areas for everyone and tried to give new tasks to everyone.

Respondent 6:

Motivation was provided by providing regular trainings and creating a friendly work environment for everyone.

Respondent 7:

The company provides new e-learning platforms, trainings, and time to time health learning quiz competitions to motivate employees back and give rewards and incentives for the same.

Respondent 8:

Yes, the organisation takes feedbacks and try to solve the issues for the employees and listen to their queries.

Respondent 9:

Yes, the organisation provides frequent trainings and provides incentives and rewards to recognise top performers.

Respondent 10:

The team has not done much to engage the employees back.

Respondent 11:

The department has created a friendly competition for everyone within the team and have created a career path for everyone to motivate them.

Respondent 12:

Mostly the training session where they send the employees to different branch for a week to work in a different environment.

Respondent 13:

Yes, there are various strategies which the Respondent did not feel right to disclose.

Respondent 14:

Yes, there are various strategies which the Respondent did not feel right to disclose.

Respondent 15:

Yes, there are various strategies which the Respondent did not feel right to disclose.

Respondent 16:

Yes, there are various strategies used.

Respondent 17:

Yes, the organisation tried to involve the employees in more team meetings and conversations.

Respondent 18:

The organisations ask the employees about their hobbies and what they are good at which lifts the mood of an employee and ask them to showcase their hobby in front of everyone.

Respondent 19:

The organisation took the employees feedback and tried to resolve the problems and issues they were facing.

Respondent 20:

Nothing so far.

Question 8:

What strategies do the organisations use to renew employee engagement?
Respondent 1: <i>The organisation organises office parties, provide gift vouchers, organise office outings on regular basis. They also do effective division of workload, have created recreational environments, and organise training sessions for all the employees.</i>
Respondent 2: <i>The team asks for feedbacks, hold regular social gatherings, provide nice and clear working environment and clarify targets and goals to achieve for everyone.</i>
Respondent 3: <i>The organisation identifies top performers and reward the achievers.</i>
Respondent 4: <i>The management has made changes in the employee policies and have increased the annual increments in the salary for employees.</i>
Respondent 5: <i>The team leads switch the working positions for everyone and have improved the way everyone works.</i>
Respondent 6: <i>The department organises out station trips for the teams occasionally.</i>
Respondent 7: <i>The organisation communicates deliberately and regularly to employees to renew their engagement. They invite employees for feedback and act on it. The organisation defines its goals and purpose and share it with the employees. They empower the employees and recognise the good work they do.</i>
Respondent 8: <i>The department usually do not do anything to renew employee engagement.</i>
Respondent 9:

The organisation provides the chances to provide honest feedbacks of how the management and team works.

Respondent 10:

It is not yet clear to the Respondent as it depends on the seniors and HR and they have not really done anything yet to renew employee engagement.

Respondent 11:

The organisation communicates deliberately and regularly while inviting employees to provide any kind of feedback and thus act on it. They empower the people and recognise the good work they do.

Respondent 12:

They try to make us study past projects to get intel what were shortcomings or positive points on that project that can help us in future.

Respondent 13:

The organisation usually implements annual rewarding schemes and provide incentives to the deserving employees.

Respondent 14:

The organisation started something called IMAD awards which means I make a Difference.

Respondent 15:

Usually, trainings are provided to the employees.

Respondent 16:

They usually organise seminars to motivate and renew employee engagement.

Respondent 17:

Participations of the employees in more and more team activities and tasks.

Respondent 18:

They have a poll session and a suggestion box put in place where the employees can drop in their suggestions.

Respondent 19:

Communicate deliberately and regularly. Invest in wellbeing. Invite feedback – and act on it. Define the organisation's purpose and sharing it. Empowering the people recognising good work.

Respondent 20:

Not known to the Respondent.

Question 9:

What is the effect of disengaged employees on organisational performance?

Respondent 1:

In terms of organisational performance there is very less overall productivity in the project, the office environment becomes very dull and boring as it leads to more pressure on the other employees to work harder. There is less motivation across because of which there is a negative flow of energy overall. All of this leads to stricter deadlines and rules across the organisation for other employees and the pressure rises from both the clients end and the senior management end.

Respondent 2:

It impacts the main goal of the organisation or project on which the whole team is working. This affects the targets set by the organisation which becomes difficult to meet. There is lack of progress on the overall project and this ultimately leads to poor performance of the team.

Respondent 3:

Disengaged employees are more likely to work hard or meet expectations for their role which decreases the overall productivity. A disengaged workforce directly impacts customer experience in a negative way. There is a decrease in morale and company culture because of a disengaged mindset.

Respondent 4:

The disengaged people are less likely to work hard as they usually become demotivated and thus does not meet any targets or expectation of their roles. These kinds of employees cause more errors and defects in their work impacting the whole project.

Respondent 5:

Disengaged employees work slow and slows down the progress of the organisation as they do not work as per their full potential and thus impact customer service as well.

Respondent 6:

Due to disengaged employees the organisations usually suffer huge financial losses as the productivity goes down and there is not much motivation left in them.

Respondent 7:

Actively disengaged employees cause disruption and dissatisfaction within the company leading to less involvement in the projects and ultimately affecting the overall productivity of the organisation.

Respondent 8:

These types of employees leave a negative impact in the working environment and the whole team working in that environment which impacts the performance of the employees.

Respondent 9:

The reputation of the organisation goes down due to disengaged employees as the organisation struggles to achieve their goals leading to dissatisfied customers and clients.

Respondent 10:

There are project delays, and the organisation is unable to meet the expected deadlines due to degradation of the qualitative work which employees do.

Respondent 11:

Disengaged employees creates a negative working environment in the team which affects the people working in the team as the morale goes down and there is lack of motivation. This also leads to clashes within the workspace and cause delivery delays of the project because of which Service Level Agreement with the client can be affected leading to monetary or goodwill loss of the organisation.

Respondent 12:

The disengaged employees lower down the organisational efficiency and demoralises the team.

Respondent 13:

They have poor productivity and have more rejections towards the work they do and usually do no achieve the targets on time.

Respondent 14:

They demotivate other employees which make them unproductive.

Respondent 15:

There is a decrease in the organisational performance when the employees are disengaged.

Respondent 16:

Organisational performance decreases qualitatively as well as quantitatively.

Respondent 17:

Disengaged employees causes attrition which means that the strength and effectiveness of the organisation is reduced by sustained pressure.

Respondent 18:

The employees perform very moderately which is not good for organisational performance.

Respondent 19:

Disengaged employees are less likely to work hard, feel motivated, or meet expectations for their role, and they cause more errors and defects in work performance. Disengagement costs money.

Respondent 20:

It is a very adverse effect on the growth of a company. Unhappy employees would never be able to produce their best at work.

Question 10:

What is the effect of disengaged employees on personal performance?

Respondent 1:

The personal performance of the employee is affected if an employee is disengaged as the personal growth becomes very slow after such negativity at work. The person always feels unhealthy and unsatisfied towards work and is not much reliable or trustworthy. The employee is also in complaining mode most of the times towards the work he does or towards the project/team he is working with and ultimately becomes an unreliable team member. The person also shows lack of leadership is does not portray effective team member skills as they are mostly ready with excuses towards all the work which is assigned to them and thus becomes a bad listener or seeker and becomes a liability for the company.

Respondent 2:

The stress levels of the employee increase which leads to low productivity and output for the organisation. This ultimately impacts the overall development of the employee as their personal development and growth is highly impacted.

Respondent 3:

The employee tends to not get involved in team building activities and they become very slow and lazy at work which increases the errors in everything they do and affects their overall performance in the team.

Respondent 4:

The employee keeps on complaining about everything in the team whether it is about the work they do or if it is about the organisation. They become very disturbing for the whole team and lowers down their own growth and self-development.

Respondent 5:

Disengaged employees start making errors in the work they do and get stressed about everything.

Respondent 6:

These employees are not able to provide effective customer service and client services and are not much enthusiastic or happy about the work they do which brings down their own personal growth and goodwill.

Respondent 7:

The employees disrupt the environment of workspace which ultimately lowers down the productivity of the project and downgrades the performance of teammates.

Respondent 8:

Personal performance is affected if the employees are dis engaged and creates lack of enthusiasm among the employees as well which lower down the energy levels.

Respondent 9:

If the employees are disengaged their accuracy to work and the sharpness of evaluating the tasks start decreasing and the performance gets affected which is not good in the long run.

Respondent 10:

Disengaged employees are less likely to work hard as they are usually demotivated to do anything. Moreover, the morale of the employees is also impacted and decreased, and the confidence level goes down as well.

Respondent 11:

The performance of employee is impacted if an employee is dis engaged as the energy levels are firstly down. This in turn starts affecting the project and the employee itself has very less input which directly affects their personal growth and development, and their productivity sees a drastic downfall.

Respondent 12:

It affects badly with team leaders and bosses and when assessed it affects their incentives and other benefits.

Respondent 13:

They are less likely to work hard, focus on looking for a new job and leads to financial loss to the organisation.

Respondent 14:

They mainly underperform when they are disengaged.

Respondent 15:

The performance of an employee is usually low if they are disengaged.

Respondent 16:

In terms of personal performance there is a lot of self-satisfaction among the employees.

Respondent 17:

Disengaged employees feel demotivated as they are not involved in all the tasks.

Respondent 18:

The employees become demotivated which makes the work transactional for them.

Respondent 19:

Disengaged employees are on the lookout for new jobs or opportunities, feel less motivated and rarely expect other expectations.

Respondent 20:

They have lack of interest at work which leads to decreased efficiency and productivity.

Question 11:

What is the effect of disengaged employees on co-workers?

Respondent 1:

When the colleagues start feeling disengaged, there is a direct effect on the co-workers as this puts a lot of additional pressure on them. Moreover, the office environment becomes very dull as there is negative influence all around which creates additional workload on the co-workers. Also, there are conflicts within the team as the disengagement creates problems between the co-workers.

Respondent 2:

Disengaged employees make the task 100 times more errors than their engaged colleagues which means there is a lot of productivity lost. Furthermore, disengaged employees generally spend less time working as they are involved in conversations and chats, take more breaks, procrastinate, spend time on social media, etc. So, this all affects the performance of the co-workers as well.

Respondent 3:

The disengaged employees are usually known for their bad behaviour. They disrupt and destroy the environment and atmosphere of a good working place for the co-workers working along.

Respondent 4:

Disengaged employees disturb the whole working environment and make co-workers uncomfortable which impacts the overall team and project.

Respondent 5:

The co-workers feel demotivated if they have colleagues who are disengaged in the team as they feel that they do not have enough support from their colleagues.

Respondent 6:

Disengaged employees make the co-workers feel uncomfortable and less motivated to engage and work.

Respondent 7:

Co-workers are directly affected by disengaged employees. Their mindset makes them loose the project and impact the healthy habits at work due to disengaged workforce. Also, while disengaged employees tend to lookout for jobs outside the organisation, they influence other team members and co-workers who accompany them and sometimes leave the organisation along which decreases the productivity of the organisation.

Respondent 8:

Disengaged employees are less likely to work hard which decreases the morale of the whole team and thus there is underperformance noticed from everyone.

Respondent 9:

The co-workers feel discomfort working along with the disengaged employees as their discomfort level rises and the co-workers start pointing out personally to their colleagues.

Respondent 10:

Disengaged employees can have a net negative impact on the workplace as the co-workers are less likely to work hard and ultimately feel demotivated.

Respondent 11:

The co-workers feel really disturbed when they have disengaged co-workers working along with them as the disengaged colleagues disrupt the whole working environment and try to have negative influence on the people working with them. This disrupts the whole environment, and the co-workers feel frustrated which effects the productivity of the project and impacts the whole organisation.

Respondent 12:

The morale of the team gets down and they get burdened because of the extra workforce.

Respondent 13:

The co-workers feel demotivated and usually have hot arguments with the colleagues. Sometimes disengaged employees go groupism with the co-workers and spread negativity across the whole organisation.

Respondent 14:

They get low morale which is very dangerous for the organisation and for the employee's personal growth.

Respondent 15:

The co-worker's performance is usually low.

Respondent 16:

Co-workers usually get demotivated when they have disengaged colleagues in the team.

Respondent 17:

The co-workers in the team and organisation also feel demotivated because of the disengaged employees.

Respondent 18:

There is a very stiff energy at the entire workplace which makes the co-workers disengaged as well.

Respondent 19:

It has negative effects on collaboration, workplace ethics, efficiency of group work which apparently affects negatively to the co-workers and their productivity.

Respondent 20:

There is a negative energy being spread among the employees which affects others productivity as well.

Question 12:

How does the attitude of an employee change when they are disengaged?

Respondent 1:

Disengaged employees do not see any growth opportunities at workplace. They moreover have lack of curiosity to learn new things and grow as a better professional.

Respondent 2:

The attitude changes drastically as the employees become irritated at work and do not socialise or engage much with their co-workers. They are lost in everything they do and become very rude whenever there are told off for anything. They also carry a carefree attitude and become rebellious if someone tries to explain them anything.

Respondent 3:

The employees have various changes in their attitude such as they have a social withdrawal from the society and have very less participation in any activity. They usually take a lot of breaks

at work and find ways to be off from work by taking longer duration breaks. Their quality decreases for the work they do which results in low productivity at work. They also do not value time as they usually arrive late at work and are the first to leave.

Respondent 4:

These types of employees usually talk very less and have very less interaction with anyone. Whenever they talk, they either talk negative or just talk about some problem and find ways of not working. They also complain most of the time about the company policies and about the senior staff or co-workers.

Respondent 5:

They have a moody kind of attitude and are not easy go to people with an unstable behaviour at work.

Respondent 6:

Actively disengaged employees will make themselves known through their bad attitude. They stop caring about their place and position in the company. They watch out for employees who are undermining others, are always criticising more than contributing and always participate in toxic workplace gossips.

Respondent 7:

Disengaged employees feel lonely most of the times and have a very negative effect on the workplace.

Respondent 8:

They have a lot of behavioural changes and are mostly out of the conversations or do not actively engage in team activities.

Respondent 9:

These types of employees have a rise in absenteeism and ignore normal working timings of the company. Their productivity and quality of work take a downturn most of the times and they lack enthusiasm to meet targets and tasks.

Respondent 10:

Disengaged employees usually start interfering in the work of others and start wasting time as well. They also tend to disturb and distract others from the work they do.

Respondent 11:

The changes in attitude are mostly visible in the way they socialise with people as they are more about complaining rather than being productive at work. They are usually a negative influence for everyone in the organisation and always try to ruin the reputation of the organisation.

Respondent 12:

They try to disturb the environment and keep slacking in the office are.

Respondent 13:

The employees start to have negligence to the tasks given to them and have an increased absenteeism in the company.

Respondent 14:

The employee become disinterested and starts blaming others for their mistakes.

Respondent 15:

The employees feel irritated at work.

Respondent 16:

The employee will not show much interest in the tasks and work assigned to them.

Respondent 17:

The employees become rude and have a negative attitude with others in the team.

Respondent 18:

The employee become transactional in everything they do.

Respondent 19:

They do not act responsibly or in an appropriate manner, they sometimes show bad attitude, they feel left out in the company and try to act out.

Respondent 20:

Lack of interest would lead to less innovation and no new ideas which decreases the productivity.

Question 13:

What role does trust play in influencing employee engagement? Why?

Respondent 1:

Employees who trust the organisations they work in tend to demonstrate behaviours such as sharing information and working well in teams. These employees also have higher levels of job satisfaction, are more likely to recommend their employer to others and are less likely to leave the organisation.

Respondent 2:

Trust plays an important role as the employees feel connected and motivated. They also feel a sense of belongingness leading to increased productivity and output. Employees also feel empathetic towards the team and their co-workers.

Respondent 3:

Putting trust in employees give them confidence and they put extra effort in their work.

Respondent 4:

Trust plays a key role in influencing employee engagement as it makes them work hard and they sort of rely on the management and trust whatever they say or do.

Respondent 5:

Trust plays a huge role as it is a really important factor in engagement because it makes employees comfortable in the working conditions and they work collaboratively.

Respondent 6:

Employees who feel trusted are empowered to get work done to their best quality leading to increased productivity and growth for the organisation.

Respondent 7:

If the management shows trust in employees and make them understand that they depend on them, then the employees would fill the shoes and work much harder than anyone can imagine. A vote of confidence goes a long way. Let them know you trust them to do the best job possible and they will really disappoint the company.

Respondent 8:

Trust plays a vital role in influencing employee engagement by bringing change, new ways to motivate them by providing career growth opportunities and trainings.

Respondent 9:

Trust plays the major role but before trusting personal liking and disliking comes in front of the process of choosing the right employee of potential. Trust gives the confidence to keep things in between the concern persons and give confidence that this person has the capability to perform and meet the targets.

Respondent 10:

When employees have trust in their employers or management, they are much more likely to work together towards achieving the same ultimate business goals and deadlines.

Respondent 11:

Trust is one of the key factors in influencing employee engagement as building trust is firstly a difficult process and if the management manages to do that then the employees can take the organisation to greater heights. If an employee has trust on the management, they work harder with a vision to achieve a goal which ultimately leads to achieving the goals of the organisation.

Respondent 12:

It is main role as if an employee can trust the organisation and their team then they will be able to communicate properly that will get them properly engaged and caught up with the team.

Respondent 13:

If a workplace can foster a strong sense of trust within their organisation, they can see several benefits including: Increased productivity amongst staff. Improved morale amongst employees and staff. The ability to work more effectively as a team, rather than individuals.

Respondent 14:

Trust is very important as it is the foundation of employee engagement.

Respondent 15:

When there is trust, the employees feel secured at the workplace.

Respondent 16:

When the employees feel that they can trust the management, they are more likely to freely initiate and put forward their thoughts and suggestions in the team.

Respondent 17:

Trust plays a great role in increasing the motivation levels of an employee.

Respondent 18:

Trust plays a very important role as it is the foundation of any relationship so the impacts hugely on employee-to-employee relationship.

Respondent 19:

Employees who feel trusted are empowered to get work done to their best ability. They know they will be supported in learning what they do not know and in optimising what they know best. Employees who feel trusted are empowered to get work done to their best ability.

Respondent 20:

Trust plays a very vital role in this. It is because the employee is trusting the management of the company that his/her voice is being heard and changes will happen for good.

Question 14:

How does leadership influence employee engagement?

Respondent 1:

Leadership plays an important role as employees feel motivated which leads to high satisfaction levels and the productivity is increased. Employees genuinely feel connected and satisfied when the leadership in the organisation is effective.

Respondent 2:

Visionary leaders who create a culture of engagement maintain employee trust, drive optimal levels of productivity, increase overall satisfaction and retention, and can position the company for success. It is in these times that employees look to organisational leaders for guidance.

Respondent 3:

Leadership is the most important key through which there can be increased employee engagement. A leader listens the thoughts and opinions of all employees and act on it.

Respondent 4:

Employee engagement is created by the organisation's Leadership Body but organisational culture, also created by leaders, plays an important role for workers. Leaders have different ways and strategies to engage their employees. Very important aspect of employee commitment: trusting the leader and fully cooperating with the person who creates a safe environment for everyone. Workers become productive, adaptable, and easily set over-achieving goals because

they work in a safe environment and trust their leaders. When workers make a mistake, they receive, instead of public criticism, support, and coaching. Thus, they are encouraged to make better decisions.

Respondent 5:

Leadership provides a job to inspire and motivate the others in the team to work to the very best of their abilities. Being an effective leader demands several qualities and characteristics that encourage those around them to succeed.

Respondent 6:

With good leadership the leaders act as role model for the employees to which they can look up to as the leaders lead by example. A good engaging leader has more productive and interested employees.

Respondent 7:

A good leadership influence the employees to work effectively as right guidance is given to them which makes the employees feel secured.

Respondent 8:

Leadership puts positive influence on the employees it is like an army fighting for the king. Even if the king is not there the army will fight for him. Similarly, with great leadership the employees produce much productivity even if the leaders are away for some time.

Respondent 9:

A leader always engages all the employees and keep the team together as they understand the potential of the team and motivated them to work beyond their potential.

Respondent 10:

Leadership influences effective communication among the employees and efficient managerial styles always build trust and respect which is an important factor towards a positive approach.

Respondent 11:

Effective leadership plays a vital role in influencing employee engagement as a good leader would always bind the team and support them in everything they do. A good leader would always motivate the employees to work harder and always take responsibility of failures. This makes a

positive environment in the team and the employees morale is boosted to work together as a team and take the organisation to greater heights.

Respondent 12:

It influences greatly as proper leadership will keep the team morals high and motivate them to work properly.

Respondent 13:

Visionary leaders who create a culture of engagement maintain employee trust, drive optimal levels of productivity, increase overall satisfaction and retention, and can position the company for success.

Respondent 14:

A leader is the one who guides the team in both good and bad times.

Respondent 15:

Leader should have a positive attitude and should keep all the employees engaged.

Respondent 16:

Leadership can sometimes play a negative role as the employee could feel dominant by the leader in the team.

Respondent 17:

Leaders are the building blocks of an organisation as the employees look up to them and learn from them.

Respondent 18:

A leader is a great influencer in employee engagement as the leader sets goals for everyone and influence them to achieve those goals.

Respondent 19:

Leadership in an organisation is to maintain employee trust, drive optimal levels of productivity, increase overall satisfaction and retention, and can position the company for success. Workers become productive, adaptable, and easily set over-achieving goals because they work in a safe environment and trust their leaders.

Respondent 20:

Leadership influences employee engagement in a good manner as a good leader will always lead people right

Appendix 4: Respondent Profile

Sr No	Name of the participants	Contact Number	Department	Designation	Qualification	Experience
1	Rahul ****	+91- *****	maintenance and utilities	assistant manager	automobile engineering	5 Yrs.
2	Laxman **	+91- *****	maintenance and utilities	officer	automobile engineering	3 Yrs.
3	Amar ***	+91- *****	maintenance and utilities	manager	electrical engineering	10 Yrs.
4	Suresh ***	+91- *****	maintenance and utilities	officer	electronic engineering	2 Yrs.
5	Dhruv***	+91- *****	maintenance and utilities	officer	electrical engineering	1 Yrs.
6	Ishaan***	+91- *****	manufacturing engineering	group supervisor	automobile engineering	12 Yrs.
7	Jaya***	+91- *****	manufacturing engineering	assistant engineer	electronic engineering	5 Yrs.
8	Aditya***	+91- *****	manufacturing engineering	assistant engineer	automobile engineering	5 Yrs.
9	Shaan***	+91- *****	manufacturing engineering	intern	manufacturing engineering	6 Months
10	Deven***	+91- *****	manufacturing engineering	intern	electrical engineering	8 Months
11	Farid***	+91- *****	quality assurance and quality systems	qc head	automobile engineering	15 Yrs.
12	Varun***	+91- *****	quality assurance and	officer	electrical engineering	3 Yrs.

			quality systems			
13	Dhara***	+91- *****	quality assurance and quality systems	officer	automobile engineering	4 Yrs.
14	Shashi***	+91- *****	quality assurance and quality systems	intern	manufacturing engineering	6 Months
15	Seema***	+91- *****	quality assurance and quality systems	intern	electronic engineering	6 Months
16	Akshat***	+91- *****	packaging and dispatch	manager	automobile engineering	10 Yrs.
17	Priyanka**	+91- *****	packaging and dispatch	officer	Logistics engineering	3 Yrs.
18	Arun***	+91- *****	packaging and dispatch	officer	manufacturing engineering	4 Yrs.
19	Charu***	+91- *****	packaging and dispatch	officer	package engineering	3Yrs.
20	Darsh****	+91- *****	packaging and dispatch	intern	automobile engineering	6 Months

